

Evaluation of Human Resource Management at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospitals

Dita Aditiya Kasim¹ Darman^{2*} and Rosnelawati S. Poiyo³

¹Hospital Administration S1 Program, FSTIK UBMG

²Bina Mandiri University Gorontalo

³Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital

darman@ubmg.ac.id*

Abstract

This study aims to determine the suitability of human resources (HR) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital with Government Regulation Number 47 Article 23 concerning type B hospital human resources and to determine Human Resource Management (HRM) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital. The method in this study uses a qualitative descriptive approach with data collected through observation, interviews, and documentation, validity and reliability are done using *credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability*. The results of this study show that: 1) Human Resources (HR) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital are following Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning Human Resources (HR). However, at Dr. M.M Dunda Hospital, it is difficult to find other specialists and subspecialists, 2) Human Resource Management (HRM) at Dr. M.M Dunda Hospital includes planning, recruitment, selection, orientation, HR utilization/placement, and evaluation. This has been done well according to the established procedures.

Keywords: Evaluation, Human Resource Management

1. Introduction

Hospitals are an integral part of social and health organizations whose mission is to provide *comprehensive, curative, and preventive* services to the community. The hospital is also a training center for health professionals and a medical research center.

Hospital as an organization engaged in services has a very close relationship with resource management, both in the form of facilities and infrastructure as well as people (Raziansyah, Pertiwi et al., 2021).

In a hospital, the management is handed over to the human resources division/personnel department responsible for obtaining, empowering, and maintaining human resources (Tejanagara, 2020). The increasing importance of the role of human resource management in the organization has encouraged the emergence of evaluation efforts on the implementation of the division (Tejanagara, 2020).

Human Resources (HR) at General Hospitals (RSU) with class A, class B, class C, and class D classifications which include medical personnel, clinical psychology personnel, nursing staff, midwifery personnel, pharmaceutical personnel, public health workers, environmental health workers, nutrition personnel, physical therapy personnel, medical technicians, biomedical technicians, other health workers, hospital management personnel, and non-health workers (*Peraturan Pemerintah Nomor 47 Tentang Penyelenggaraan Rumah Sakit*, 2021).

Human resources are the integrated abilities of the thinking power and physical power possessed by individuals, their behavior and nature are determined by their offspring and environment, while their work performance is motivated by the desire to fulfill their satisfaction. Human resources are assets in all aspects of management, especially those concerning the existence of the organization (Bukit et al., 2017)

Human Resources (HR) is one of the key factors in global competition, namely how to create quality human resources who have high skills and competitiveness in global competition which has been often ignored (Dewi et al., 2021). Globalization that is certainly faced by the Indonesian nation demands efficiency and competitiveness in the business world (Dewi et al., 2021). In globalization involving intraregional and international relations, there will be competition between countries (Dewi et al., 2021).

Human Resources or often referred to as Employees is a part of the hospital that provides human resource fulfillment services, especially Professional Care Providers (PPA) in accordance with professional standards and have competencies that can be accounted for (*Pedoman Manajemen SDM UPTD RSJD*, 2020). The Selection of Care Professionals (PPA) must be able to meet the requests or needs of each work unit in the hospital (*Pedoman Manajemen SDM UPTD RSJD*, 2020). To be able to support achievements in terms of service, the Human Resource Management (HRM) process requires a work guideline so that good and quality results are obtained (*Pedoman Manajemen SDM UPTD RSJD*, 2020). Quality service at the hospital will help each staff to be able to work in accordance with their profession, education and abilities, help the service process to patients in the hospital so that patients who come for treatment to the hospital feel satisfied with the services provided, which means that the *customer* will later be a means of promoting the hospital (*Pedoman Manajemen SDM UPTD RSJD*, 2020).

Human Resource Management is a process consisting of planning, organizing, leading and controlling activities related to job analysis, job evaluation, procurement, development, compensation, promotion and termination of employment in order to achieve predetermined goals (Adamy, 2016)

Based on the results of Field Learning Practice (PBL) in semester five and semester six at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, which is placed in several parts of the room, one of which is in the HR section by looking at Human Resources (HR) data obtained from Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital in March 2023, it has shown 410 civil servants, 301 contract laborers,

and 132 servants. Currently, hospital conditions based on the amount of data obtained by human resources in hospitals every month are increasing, and researchers also find problems in hospitals that in terms of manpower, there are still aim specialists and sub-specialists who are difficult to obtain, while in type B hospitals regulated in Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning human resources, type B general hospitals have a number of provisions for personnel at home The pain that must be fulfilled is therefore the researcher took the title with the aim of wanting to know more about Human Resource Management at Dunda Limboto Hospital and wanting to know whether the human resources at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital are in accordance with the provisions of Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning human resources of type B general hospitals.

This study aims to determine the suitability of human resources at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital with Government Regulation Number 47 Article 23 concerning type B hospital human resources and to determine Human Resource Management (HRM) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital.

2. Methods

The method in this study uses qualitative descriptive with data collected through observation, interviews, and documentation (Tristani, 2019). And data wetness is done by means of *credibility, transferability, dependability, confirmability* (Tristani, 2019).

The criteria of informants in this study are as follows:

Table 1. List of Research Informants

No	Information Type	Goal	Sum
1.	Key Informants	Young Expert Staffing Analyst	1 Person
2.	Main Informer	Person in Charge of Education and Training (Diklat)	1 Person
3.	Additional Informants	Person in Charge of HR Data (Human Resources)	1 Person

Source: Data processed, 2023

The number of informants in this study amounted to three (3) people consisting of informant one (1) young expert personnel analyst as key informant, informant two (2) person in charge of Education and Training (Diklat) as the main informant, informant three (3) person in charge of human resource data as additional informant in the general administration room.

3. Results

This research will be conducted from April 2023 to June 2023. This research was carried out to determine the evaluation of human resource management adjusted to the focus and sub focus of research, research objectives and also the framework of the research concept, namely the suitability of human resources at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital.

Human Resources in accordance with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to three (3) informants who are in charge of Human Resources (HR) data at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital regarding the suitability of the number of Human Resources (HR) with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23.

The following are questions that will be asked directly to additional informants along with answers from informants:

- Does the number of Human Resources at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital already exist in accordance with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning Human Resources (HR)

"If the suitability of HR (Human Resources) data at Dr. M.M Dunda Hospital so meets the existing requirements with the meaning that in accordance with type B hospital regulations mar people still lack other specialists and sub-specialists because it is difficult to get room with personnel, usually if the hospital so need other specialists and subspecialists from the hospital directly ba contract personnel from outside the region. In Gorontalo, it is still difficult to get other specialists and subspecialists." (RDT, Informer 3)

From this statement, it can be interpreted that informant three (3) stated that: the suitability of HR (Human Resources) data at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital has met the requirements or is in accordance with government regulation No. 47 of 2021 article 23 concerning human resources. But the hospital still lacks other specialists and sub-specialists. If you urgently need other specialists and subspecialists of Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, the hospital will contact personnel from hospitals outside the region in accordance with mutual agreement or by referring patients to hospitals that have these personnel.

Human Resource Management at RSUD Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant one (1) who is a young expert personnel analyst and information two (2) who is in charge of education and training (Diklat) there are several managements for hospital human resources, namely planning, recruitment, selection, orientation, utilization, job placement and evaluation.

- What is the process of human resource planning at RSUD dr. M.M Dunda Limboto?

"If it's for HR planning... We plan planning, namely from the start of the selection but there must be a need first. We make a plan for the reception of personnel, we must first make needs, namely through job analysis (ANJAB) and (ABK) workload analysis, how suddenly we plan to need employee A, for example, the needs of our nurses Only write five (5) people while we have not made a needs analysis, how much is the burden on the hospital to receive, it means the workload of the hospital through workload analysis or job analysis". (HM, Informant 1)

From the statement above, it can be interpreted that informant one (1) states: For the Human Resources (HR) planning process, starting from labor selection which is carried out in several stages, namely administrative selection, test scheduling, implementation of labor selection, general introduction and debriefing (orientation) and placement of labor. Manpower planning at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital in the long term is determined by Workload Analysis and Position Analysis which is the benchmark for Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital in recruiting employees, the personnel to be accepted must be in

accordance with the qualifications of personnel education determined by the hospital and applicable regulations. The calculation of Workload Analysis at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital uses calculations in accordance with the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment which are updated every year, so that the needs of clinical and non-clinical personnel each year can be known.

- How is the recruitment of human resources that has been carried out at RSUD dr. M.M Dunda Limboto?

"What we do here is the recruitment of contract personnel, but if the recruitment for civil servants is that there are two civil servants and PPPK personnel, but in the last 2 years, there is no health PPPK, later this year there is PPPK for health, if recruitment for civil servants depends on BKD but is included with hospital needs according to hospital needs, recruitment is held then if for contract personnel, the same recruitment if we receive recruitment, but the exam is also at BKD we have... There is this, there is... What's the matter first? There are conditions, we must first identify the needs, then there is an acceptance plan, new selection planning, there is a schedule for selection. That is for those who contract, but if the civil servant or PPPK depends on the BKD who recruits, eee does recruitment depending on our needs, what is recruited by the BKD depends on the needs of existing OPDs, people are less than trima oh, this is like our civil servants, how many doctors will we have, how many doctors will we be in case, how many doctors will be needed, how many nurses even though we ask for 20 (twenty) are not fulfilled, 20 (twenty) according to... Even then, recruitment for civil servants is hereby in accordance with the availability of this budget fund". (HM, Informant 1)

The statement can be interpreted that informant one (1) stated: the recruitment carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital is the recruitment of contract personnel. The contract personnel will conduct a written test at BKD and then the hospital will receive them in accordance with the terms and conditions of the hospital. And recruitment for civil servants which includes civil servants and PPPK is carried out by BKD which is included with data on hospital needs but in recruiting civil servants must also adjust to the budget that has been set.

- How has the selection process been carried out so far at RSUD dr. M.M Dunda Limboto?

"If the selection for contract personnel we select together with the local government, with the local government will make a selection if for us Only administrative selection, administrative selection we see the file, according to not, if for the study he must complete the CV dpe, training certificate depe, especially there is an STR depe, STR depe must be there according to what diploma we selected first we must have diploma verification, depe blah... blaa turus-turus bagitu. And the selection process for civil servants has its own stages that must be fulfilled through online, hospitals only need to accept civil servants." (HM, Informant 1)

- What is the employee orientation process at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital?

"Bismillahirrahmanirrahim... Eee if, for example, the employee orientation process at Dunda Hospital is usually carried out by EE Training Organizer. Then there are two orientations, namely general orientation and special orientation. The general orientation usually aims to provide a general description of the dunda hospital, the orientation participants are able to know the vision and mission, philosophy of the hospital, then be able to let alone mmm... Be able to adapt, socialize with their coworkers. Then in any material In the general orientation there are seven or how many materials that must be submitted to the orientation participants including mandatory material for

hospital administration and management, the second PPI (Infection Control and Prevention) in hospitals, three hospital qualities, hospital bureaucracy, basic life support with APAR (Light Fire Extinguisher) it is mandatory to be followed by orientation participants for general orientation. Then the special orientation is usually the training directly submits to their respective fields, for example if the nurse goes directly to the nursing field, then if for example the department is nutrition she goes directly to the support, right. Now usually it's a special orientation that they introduce about their work procedure SOPs at work later, then can find out their rights and obligations where they are on duty, that's all." (IM, Informant 2)

From this statement, it can be interpreted that informant two (2) stated that: the employee orientation process at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital was carried out by the training organizer. Orientation is divided into two, namely general orientation and special orientation. The general orientation aims to provide a general overview of Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital. Orientation participants must be able to know the vision, mission and philosophy of Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, then be able to adapt and socialize with colleagues. In general orientation there are seven (7) materials that must be delivered to orientation participants, namely:

- 1) Hospital Administration and Management
- 2) Infection Control and Prevention (PPI)
- 3) Patient Safety
- 4) Hospital Quality
- 5) Light Fire Extinguisher (APAR)
- 6) Basic Life Support,
- 7) Hospital Bureaucracy

Special orientation is usually the training organizer directly submits to their respective fields, for example if the nurse is directly handed over to the nursing field and also if the nutrition department is directly handed over to the supporting department. The special orientation carried out in their respective fields they introduced SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) that were in the workplace in that field. Then explained related to rights and obligations in accordance with the field or workplace later.

- How is the utilization / placement of employees carried out at RSUD dr. M.M Dunda Limboto?

"If the placement of employees is in accordance with this basic department, it is impossible that we place radiology in nurses adjusted to their work environment, if for example they are nurses, I place them in the nurse's environment, just choose which room according to them has basic education, if it is impossible for laboratory officers, I place them in... dii... nourished. Adapted to existing competencies". (HM Informant 1)

From this statement, it can be interpreted that informant one (1) stated that: the placement of employees carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital was adjusted to the education, competence, and objectives of the work environment.

- How is the mechanism used in evaluating employee performance at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital?

"If we have an evaluation that is monthly like we fill in performance, there is daily performance evaluated by the head of the sub-field with his superiors, adjusted to his work. There is also an evaluation carried out annually, namely SKP (Employee Performance Target), the proof is

that this is adjusted to how many items, namely the evaluation department like there in addition to evaluations related to technical evaluations through performance, there is daily performance, there is annual performance, ”(HM Informant 1)

From this statement, it can be interpreted that informant one (1) stated that: the evaluation at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital was carried out monthly on the basis of daily performance reports in accordance with their respective jobs or objectives and was evaluated by the head of the sub-field and his superiors. The evaluation is carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital through SKP (Employee Performance Targets) which is often carried out once a year. The function of the daily evaluation simplifies and reduces employee performance problems in the annual evaluation.

From this statement, it can be interpreted that informant one (1) stated that: for the selection process of contract personnel at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, it includes administrative selection, completeness of CV, training certificates, STRs, diplomas and must be verified. The selection process is carried out with the Regional Government. And the ASN selection process is directly from the center, they have rules through online.

4. Discussion

Based on the results obtained when conducting research, the following discussion can be stated:

Human Resources (HR) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital is in accordance with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning human resources of type B general hospitals.

Based on the results of interviews and observations made by researchers to informants, three (3) who are in charge of Human Resources (HR) data at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital are in accordance with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning Human Resources (HR). The type of data and the number of Human Resources (HR) obtained by researchers at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital can be described as follows:

Medical personnel include thirteen (13) general practitioners and four (4) contract personnel, one (1) dentist, three (3) civil servants. Specialists include four (4) civil servants, three (3) contract surgeons, 2 obstetrics and gynecologists. Other specialists include eyes two (2) contract persons, ENT-KL one (1) civil servant and one (1) contract person, nerve two (2) civil servant person, heart and blood vessels one (1) contract person, skin and genital one (1) civil servant, mental medicine one (1) contract person, lung one (1) contract person, orthopedics and traumatology one (1) civil servant, urology one (1) civil servant, anesthesia two (2) civil servants and one (1) contract personnel, physical medicine and rehabilitation one (1) contract personnel, radiology one (1) civil servant, clinical pathology one (1) civil servant, anatomical pathology one (1) civil servant, clinical nutrition one (1) civil servant. Specialist dentists include conservation/edodontion of one (1) civil servant, oral surgery of one (1) civil servant. Nursing personnel one hundred sixty-three (163) civil servants and one hundred two (102) contract people. Midwifery personnel forty-five (45) civil servants and forty-three (43) contract people. Pharmaceutical personnel include ten (10) civil servants and two (2) contract

pharmacists, six (6) civil servants and five (5) contract personnel. Other health workers include nutrition workers sixteen (16) civil servants and eight (8) contract people, physiotherapists seven (7) civil servants and two (2) contract people, medical recorders and health information eight (8) civil servants and two (2) contract people, anesthesia managers two (2) civil servants and one (1) contract person, radiographers eight (8) civil servants and three (3) contract people, electromedical six (6) civil servants, laboratory technologists fifteen (15) civil servants and two (2) contract people, environmental health workers seven (7) civil servants, health extension workers seven (7) civil servants, public health administrators five (5) civil servants, health epidemiology two (2) civil servants. Non-health personnel include directors of one (1) civil servants, deputy directors of administration and finance one (1) civil servants, deputy directors of services one (1) civil servants, administrative and general affairs thirteen (13) civil servants and ten (10) contract people, finance department sixteen (16) civil servants and four (4) contract people, program development and publication section eight (8) civil servants and three (3) contract people, medical services thirteen (13) civil servants and empty twenty-three (43) contract people, supporting services fifteen (15) civil servants and fifty-four (54) contract people.

This is already in line with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 article 23 on Human Resources (HR) which states that Human Resources (HR) in general hospitals with class A, class B, class C, and class D classifications include: medical personnel; clinical psychology personnel; nursing personnel; obstetric personnel; pharmaceutical personnel; public health workers; environmental health workers; nutritional power; physical therapy personnel; medical technicians; biomedical engineering personnel; other health workers; and non-health workers [14]. The other specialists that Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital does not have include neurosurgery, reconstructive and aesthetic plastic surgery, pediatric surgery, cardiac and vascular thoracic surgery, forensic medicine, emergencies, ENT-KL, blood vessel heart, nerves etc. Sub-specialist personnel who do not yet have Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital include surgery, internal medicine, children, *Obsetri and gynecology*. However, for other specialists and sub-specialists, it is difficult to obtain, so if when the energy is needed, Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital will try to contract these personnel based on the MOU with the hospital or facilitated by the University. If the energy has not been fulfilled, Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital refers patients to hospitals that have other specialists and sub-specialists.

Human Resource Management (HR) at RSUD Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant one (1) who is a young expert personnel analyst to find out the process of planning Human Resources (HR) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital in the long term is determined by workload analysis and position analysis which is the benchmark for Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital in recruiting employees, the personnel to be accepted must be in accordance with the educational qualifications of personnel that have been determined by the hospital and regulations applicable. The calculation of workload analysis at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital uses calculations in accordance with the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of State Apparatus Empowerment which are updated every year, so that the needs of clinical and non-clinical personnel each year can be known and can be directly planned for recruitment, selection, orientation, placement etc.

This is in accordance with the theory previously proposed that Human Resource planning (HR) is a systematic process used to predict the demand and supply (Human Resources) of HR in the future. Through this systematic Human Resources (HR) planning program, it can be estimated the number and type of manpower needed in each particular period so that it can assist HR in planning recruitment, selection, and education and training. Good Human Resource Planning (HR) must be done integrally, both internally and externally. Internally, the recruitment, selection, placement, training, and assessment plan should be structured in such a way that reflects the plan to recruit and select new employees. The planning process in this study is slightly different from the results of previous studies which stated that workforce planning is a process of estimating the number of workers needed by considering the needs of competencies, working hours, BOR, RAB, and TT each year.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant one (1) who is a young expert personnel analyst to find out how to recruit Human Resources (HR) that has been carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, namely contract recruitment. The contract personnel will conduct a written test at BKD and then the hospital will receive them in accordance with the terms and conditions of the hospital. And recruitment for civil servants which includes civil servants and PPPK is carried out by BKD which is included with data on hospital needs but in recruiting civil servants must also adjust to the budget that has been set.

This is in accordance with the theory previously stated that recruitment is carried out in accordance with the Human Resources (HR) plan that has been determined (Tristani, 2019). After determining the Human Resources (HR) plan, the Human Resources (HR) field manager has the task to think of several recruitment alternatives that can be done by the company at the most efficient cost (Tristani, 2019). The need for this alternative is based on the consideration that recruitment requires high costs, among others, for the *interview research* process, fee payments, and processing new employees (Tristani, 2019).

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant one (1) who is a young expert personnel analyst to find out the selection process carried out so far at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, it includes administrative selection, completeness of CV, training certificate, STR, diploma and must be verified. The selection process is carried out with the Regional Government. And the ASN selection process is directly from the center, they have rules through online.

This is in accordance with the theory put forward earlier that basically selection is the process of selecting and sorting applicants or prospective employees according to the criteria desired by the company (Tristani, 2019). The selection process in general usually consists of administrative selection, written tests, interview tests, medical tests (Tristani, 2019).

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant two (2) who are in charge of Education and Training (Diklat) to find out the employee orientation process at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, it was carried out by the training organizer. Orientation is divided into two, namely general orientation and special orientation. The general orientation aims to provide a general overview of Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital. Orientation participants must be able to know the vision, mission and philosophy of Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, then be able to adapt and socialize with colleagues. In general orientation, there are 7 (seven) materials that must be delivered to orientation participants, namely:

1. Hospital Administration and Management
2. Infection Control and Prevention (PPI)
3. Patient Safety
4. Hospital Quality
5. Light Fire Extinguisher (APAR)
6. Basic Life Support
7. Hospital Bureaucracy

Special orientation is usually the training organizer directly submits to their respective fields, for example if the nurse is directly handed over to the nursing field and also if the nutrition department is directly handed over to the supporting department. The special orientation carried out in their respective fields they introduced SOPs (Standard Operating Procedures) that were in the workplace in that field. Then explained related to rights and obligations in accordance with the field or workplace later.

This is in accordance with the theory put forward earlier which states orientation can be divided into two groups, namely general and special orientation. General orientation is a program to introduce prospective new employees in entering the real world of work as a whole. Special orientation is an activity to prepare new and old employees who undergo mutation to be able to carry out tasks in accordance with the standards where they are placed.

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant one (1) who is a young expert personnel analyst to find out for the utilization / placement of employees carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, it is adjusted to the education, competence, and objectives of the work environment.

This is in accordance with the theory previously stated that utilization is to place prospective employees who are declared accepted or pass the selection in positions or work units with their qualifications (Tristanti, 2019). Based on the utilization that has been determined, an employee will be divided into tasks and work according to the specified work environment (Tristanti, 2019). This is different from the results of previous studies which stated that employee placement was carried out by looking at needs, adjusted to hospital standards, based on patient BOR and carried out by direct supervisors (Setyarto, 2017).

Based on the results of interviews conducted by researchers to informant one (1) who is a young expert personnel analyst to find out the mechanism used in conducting evaluations at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital, it is carried out monthly on the basis of daily performance reports that are in accordance with their respective jobs or objectives and are evaluated by the head of the sub-field and their superiors. The evaluation is carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital through SKP (Employee Performance Targets) which is often carried out once a year. The function of the daily evaluation simplifies and reduces employee performance problems in the annual evaluation.

This is different from previous research previously stated that the mechanism used in evaluating employee performance among others through DP3 is carried out by superiors once in a while, which includes attendance lists, discipline, active hospital activities, responsibilities and so on (Setyarto, 2017). Which of these evaluations can be used as a reference for class increases, periodic salary increases, and contract extensions (Setyarto, 2017).

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

Based on the results of research that the researcher has described in the results and discussion of the study, it can be concluded that:

- 1) Human Resources (HR) at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital is in accordance with Government Regulation Number 47 of 2021 Article 23 concerning Human Resources (HR). However, at Dr. M.M Dunda Hospital, it is difficult to find other specialists and subspecialists. The other specialists that Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital does not have include neurosurgery, reconstructive and aesthetic plastic surgery, pediatric surgery, cardiac and vascular thoracic surgery, forensic medicine, emergencies, ENT-KL, blood vessel heart, nerves etc. Sub-specialists who do not yet have Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital include surgery, internal medicine, children, *obstetrics and gynecology*.
- 2) Human Resource Management at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital includes:
 - a. Planning
For the Human Resources (HR) planning process, starting from labor selection which is carried out in several stages, namely administrative selection, test scheduling, implementation of labor selection, general introduction and debriefing (orientation) and placement of workers and adjusting to needs.
 - b. Recruitment
Recruitment for civil servants which includes civil servants and PPPK is carried out by BKD which is included with data on hospital needs but in recruiting civil servants must also adjust to the budget that has been set.
 - c. Selection
The selection process for contract personnel at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital includes administrative selection, completeness of CV, training certificates, STRs, diplomas and must be verified. The selection process is carried out with the Regional Government. And the ASN selection process is directly from the center, they have rules through online.
 - d. Orientation
The employee orientation process at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital was carried out by the training organizer. Orientation is divided into two, namely general orientation and special orientation. The general orientation aims to provide a general overview of Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital.
 - e. Utilization/placement
The utilization / placement of employees carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital is adjusted to the education, competence, and objectives of the work environment.
 - f. Evaluation
The evaluation at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital is carried out monthly on the basis of daily performance reports that are in accordance with their respective jobs or objectives and are evaluated by the head of the sub-field and their superiors. The

evaluation is carried out at Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital through SKP (Employee Performance Targets) which is often carried out once a year.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusions that have been found, the author conveys some suggestions as follows:

- 1) Other specialists and sub-specialists are very important for Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital in serving patients but these personnel are very difficult to obtain. So it is necessary for Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital to immediately try to procure these personnel.
- 2) Dr. M.M Dunda Limboto Hospital must be able to improve human resource management even though it has been done well according to the established procedures, this is for hospital accreditation.

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Assessment of Environmental Management Participation in Cultivating a Sustainable Village

Artit Dalangko¹, Darman^{2*}, and Siske Anani³

^{1,2,3}Bina Mandiri University Gorontalo

Correspondence Email: darman@ubmg.ac.id*

Email: dalangkoartit44@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to: (1) determine the level of community participation in maintaining cleanliness in East Mamungaa Village. (2) To know what factors influence the community to participate in maintaining cleanliness in East Mamungaa Village.

The current study used a descriptive research design. This research was located in East Mamungaa Village, specifically in hamlet Five Bulawa District, Bone Bolango Regency. The data has been collected using observation, interview, and documentation. The population was people in Hamlet Five of East Mamungaa Village who participated in the interview on environmental arrangements. Moreover, the sampling of 15 people used a random sampling technique. The type of data used is qualitative including data presented in the form of verbal words which was not in the form of numbers, whose data source is obtained from the East Mamungaa Village Community, hamlet five. The data analysis technique used in this study is a qualitative method.

Based on the results, it was obtained that the people of east Mamungaa Village already have an awareness of how to participate in environmental arrangements, however, some communities still do not understand the importance of environmental arrangements because there are still many communities who are not supportive and prejudiced in new things.

Keywords: Participation, Community, Hygiene

1. Introduction

Recognition by countries around the world that Indonesia is a region that has the most islands, and has a diversity of natural resources throughout the archipelago. To preserve this natural wealth, the government stipulates regulations that become the basis for all Indonesian people to always maintain and preserve it through national policies in all aspects of social life, thus the community must be jointly responsible for managing a balanced living environment, both in the management of provincial spatial plans, district and village governments. In managing a good living environment that involves all parties, it is deemed necessary to have

an understanding between policymakers, policy implementers, and policy users, so that each party understands the importance of protecting, preserving, and utilizing it, and this is a condition that supports the creation good work together.

Spatial management in Indonesia, especially the environment, has an important meaning in achieving sustainable national development goals by making maximum use of it and right on target, with policies that can prevent disputes and abuse of authority.

To preserve this natural wealth, the government stipulates regulations that become the basis for all Indonesian people to always maintain and preserve them through national policies in all aspects of social life, thus the community must be jointly responsible for managing a balanced living environment, both in the management of provincial spatial plans, district and village governments. In the village of East Mamungaa, the management and structuring of residential areas is carried out through community participation, but in recent years the management has not been optimal anymore, even some areas that have been designated as protected areas are used without regard to the safety risks of residents. As a form of cooperation between the East Mamungaa village government and the TNI, they planted 1000 trees near the riverbanks which involved community participation in preserving the environment considering the huge potential of natural resources must be balanced with reliable human resources to create harmony between nature and the environment occupied by residents. This kind of participation has been widely carried out by the East Mamungaa Village Community, Bulawa District, Bone Bolango Regency, developing its territory through village infrastructure development or Environmental Management in previous years so that East Mamungaa Village can win several good awards.

Many studies have been conducted on public participation in development management. To increase the level of public participation in environmental management, efforts need to be made to improve public understanding of the importance of environmental management. In addition, efforts need to be made to allow the public to participate in decision-making in environmental management (Huda & Setyowati, 2020). To increase the level of public participation in environmental management, efforts need to be made to improve public understanding of the importance of environmental management. In addition, efforts need to be made to allow the public to participate in decision-making in environmental management (Irawan & Sukri, 2022). To increase the level of public participation in waste management, efforts need to be made to improve public understanding of the importance of waste management. In addition, efforts need to be made to allow the public to participate in waste processing (Syafi'i & Setyowati, 2023)

The initial observations made, attracted the attention of the compilers to find out more about the role of the village government in carrying out environmental management, especially in the Hamlet V area, Bone Bolango.

Participation

Participation in village development includes community participation in decision-making, and implementation of development, namely the sharing of benefits or profits depending on the results of implementing community activities in the process resulting from these activities. Participating in the development process is seen as a methodology that directs

actors to analyze and find solutions depending on each case being handled, thus forming a framework for monitoring and evaluation (Septyasa, 2013).

Forms of Community Participation

The forms of community participation can also be interpreted as contributions that are given voluntarily (Septyasa, 2013) this can be in the form of:

- a) Participate through the contribution of thoughts.
- b) Participate through the contribution of thoughts.
- c) Participate through social activities, such as providing material self-help, either in the form of money or goods.

Factors affecting the level of community participation

Factors that affect the level of community participation are development plans that are in line with the interests or needs of the community. Therefore, community participation is more achievable if the development plan itself is directed to the benefit of the community (Bintoro, 2017).

Environmental arrangement/management

Environmental management is stated to be an area unit that contains objects, power, conditions, living things that affect the condition of the area (Dewi & Wirajaya, 2013). The arrangement and management of the environment has been regulated and statutory regulations, so that its management is based on the principles that have been regulated, both utilization, control, maintenance (*Law No.32 on Environmental Protection and Management*, 2009)

2. Methods

The method used in this research is descriptive method. This method intends to present the situation according to the facts at the location in detail, and systematically, so that the author can obtain and present a more accurate picture of Community Participation in Environmental Management in Hamlet V, East Mamungaa Village, Bulawa District, Bone Bolango Regency.

3. Results

In the results of the study, the researcher explained the interview process from the people of Hamlet V regarding community participation in environmental management.

Instructive Function

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Sri imon Dalangko
- 2) Felmi Hikolo
- 3) Hamsa Dalangko

The question given by a researcher is how a leader gives orders to the community in giving effect to increasing community participation in Environmental Management in East Mamungaa Village, especially Hamlet V.

Consultative function

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Iskandar h Gunibala
- 2) Fitri ningsi djuma
- 3) Nandaria gunibala

The question given by a researcher is how a leader directs, invites, and is directly involved in community participation activities in environmental management.

Community development

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Yamin Bouti
- 2) Ibrahim Kantu
- 3) Asia Olee

The question given by a researcher is how, you can develop to the community about the arrangement of the environment that you live in to be more beautiful.

Mind Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Narmo soi
- 2) Hasisa tangahu
- 3) Abdulah djuma

The question asked by a researcher is how can you participate in thinking in environmental management.

Energy Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Abdul Hamid Hualata
- 2) Mohamad Hualata
- 3) Juanita H kadir

Question Asked by a researcher, how did you or was touched by his heart in helping to organize the environment.

Supporting factors

a. Energy Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Rahman Hulopi
- 2) Salma Hulopi
- 3) Nurmala Hulopi

The researcher asks what questions are you able to participate in the management of the environment in East Mamungaa Village.

b. Skill Participation

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Hasan Towalu
- 2) Haidar Gunibala
- 3) Carles Towalu

The researcher asks the question, what are your skills in participating in environmental management in East Mamungaa Village.

Obstacle factor

a) Kurang Dukungan Masyarakat

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Hamid Dalangko
- 2) Ahmad djuma
- 3) Jainudin baderan

The researcher asks the question, what makes you less supportive in terms of community participation in environmental management.

b) Prejudice Against New Things

The researcher interviewed several people from the East Mamungaa Village community with the names below:

- 1) Sopyan Palilati
- 2) Sutarjo Gunibala
- 3) Usman Hulopi

The researcher interviewed what can be prejudiced against new things that are new in community participation in environmental management.

Then on the question above, the researcher directly conducts research that can solve the problem according to the answers from the results of the community interviews themselves.

Instructive Function

The answers from each informant are;

- Sri Imon Dalangko gave the answer he said that the order given by the head of the East Mamungaa Village was very important to be heard and obeyed.

- While the answer from Mrs. Feli Hikolo, the order given by the head of the East Mamungaa Village should be obeyed because a good community should listen to what is ordered by a leader in the village
- While the answer from Mr. Hamsa Dalangko. The order given by the HEAD of the VILLAGE of East Mamungaa has the right to determine how the order should be carried out.

Consultative function

The answers from each informant are;

- Mr. Iskandar H Gunibala gave his answer that the Head of East Mamungaa Village prioritizes consultation with the East Mamungaa Village community before making a decision.
- Mrs. Fitri Ningsi Djuma gave an answer that the Head of the East Mamungaa Village every time he carried out an activity, he participated in helping the activity take place
- Mrs. Nanda Gunibala gave the answer that the Head of East Mamungaa Village directs all village officials to succeed in all activities related to environmental cleanliness in East Mamungaa Village.

Community development

The answers from each informant are;

- Mr. Yamin Bouti gave the answer that in order to develop people to care about the environment, an understanding of environmental issues must be given.
- Mr. Ibrahim Kantu said that community development must be based on strengthening cooperation in environmental management.
- Mrs. Asia Olee gave an answer that the development of the community must prioritize the principle of justice in determining attitudes, in environmental management.

Mind Participation

- Mr. Narmo Soi gave an answer that the arrangement of the environment must be based on the participation of the mind so that the environment is well structured.
- Hasisa Tangahu that in structuring the environment, it is necessary to plan how the environment we live in can feel comfortable.
- Mr. Abdulah Djuma that in the arrangement of the environment must be done voluntarily so that our environment remains clean.

Energy Participation

- Mr. Abdul Hamid Hulalata gave the answer that the participation of energy is very important in structuring the environment.
- Mr. Mohamad Hulalata gave his answer that the participation of personnel can encourage success in environmental management.
- Mrs. Juanita H. Kadir gave the answer that the participation of personnel is not enough if it is not accompanied by providing wages because through wages the environmental arrangement will run as desired.

Supporting factors

a. Energy supporting factor

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Rahman Hulopi gave an answer that the supporting factor in the participation of the workforce is very necessary because the participation of the workforce is quickly resolved.
- the answer from Mrs. Salma Hulopi that the supporting factor of labor participation must be based on communication with fellow community members.
- Mrs. Nurmala Hulopi that the supporting factor of the participation of workers must be seen from the level of age and education level as well as the type of work.

b. Skill Factor

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Hasan Towalu, regarding the factors supporting skills, he gave an answer that for, in structuring the environment, it must be based on skills in planting.
- Mrs. Haidar Gunibala, regarding the factors that support skills, she gave an answer that skills are really needed when we are going to organize the Environment in Hamlet V.
- Mr. Carkes Towalu regarding the factors supporting skills he gave an answer that skill is the ability to do something well, quickly and precisely.

Inhibiting factor

1. Lack of Support

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Hamid Dalangko, he said that the inhibiting factor for the lack of community support was the lack of public trust in the village government.
- While the answer from Mr. Ahmad Djuma about the inhibiting factor of lack of support from the community is when people like things that they feel are not necessary for them.
- While the answer from Mr. Jainudin Baderan regarding the inhibiting factor is the lack of support from the community, namely the lack of public understanding of the programs programmed by the village government.

2. Prejudice against new things

The answers from each informant are:

- Mr. Sopyan Palilati regarding the inhibiting factors in prejudice to new things, he believes that the people's trust in the new policies implemented by the government is still lacking, many people do not believe in the new things implemented by the village government.
- Mr. Sutarjo Gunibala, according to him, many people still lack trust in others.
- Mr. Usaman Hulopi regarding the inhibiting factors in prejudice against new things, he said that it was because people always thought negatively about the things they just heard.

4. Discussion

Instructive Function

In accordance with his duties and responsibilities, the Village Head is obliged to guide by giving orders and instructions, as was the view of previous researchers that the instructions

carried out by the village head emphasized implementation, reports, time and place, completed taking into account the time. efficiency. Another opinion is that the village head shows the consistency of a leader in giving instructions and always applies rules according to standards so that it can be ensured that the work given by employees does not deviate from their duties and functions (Efendi, 2019)

Consultative Function

In the deliberation function, the village head of East Mamungaa provides the opportunity to convey opinions, suggestions and ideas from the community and the village head. This is done to perfect what has been done. Real consultation can be applied by discussing so that the problems they are working on can be resolved immediately (Efendi, 2019). This function can work well if there is mutual openness between employees.

Community development

As part of the development of these efforts, it aims to build community capacity by encouraging, motivating and inspiring, as well as developing their potential.

Mind Participation

This form of participation can be done by contributing ideas or thoughts in the process of implementing, controlling, and coordinating all actions as a form of maintaining rights in social life. As stated by Plumer (*Law No.32 on Environmental Protection and Management, 2009*) regarding the supporting factors for participation, namely:

1. Knowledge and skills
2. Knowledge will affect the entire community environment, allowing people to understand whether they understand the stages and forms of participation that exist.
3. Community work.
4. Usually, people with a certain level of work will be able to spend more or even less time to complete it. Often, the underlying reason for the community is the challenge between commitment to work and willingness to participate.
5. Belief in a particular culture
6. A society with a high degree of heterogeneity, especially in terms of religion and culture, will determine the participation strategy used and the methodology used. Frequently held beliefs can conflict with existing concepts.

Energy Participation

Communities are not only recipients of facilities and benefits but as subjects of sustainable development (Dewi & Wirajaya, 2013). Community participation is the right of the community to participate in decision making. manufacture at all stages of the development process, starting with initial planning, implementation, monitoring and environmental preservation.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors

From the results of previous interviews, it was found that to implement and realize good environmental management, as proclaimed by the Bone Bolango district government in the vision and mission of 2021-2026, there are factors that influence the process, namely;

1. The East Mamungaa Village Government should encourage the creativity of the village community by providing motivation to the community to be more involved in environmental management by participating, both in mind and energy.
2. The inhibiting factor in implementing environmental management in the village is the lack of community support and prejudice against new things that are considered contrary to the customs and traditions of the local community.

Mga Hamon sa Pagtuturo sa mga Guro sa Panahon ng COVID-19 Pandemya: Isang Naratolohiya

¹Gemma C. Adraneda

²Laarni C. Canare

^{1,2} Bataan Peninsula State University-Balanga Campus
College of Education

Abstrakt

Sa pamamagitan ng pamamaraan naratolohiya ay inalam ng pag-aaral na ito ang mga suliraning hamon sa pagtuturo online sa panahon ng COVID-19 pandemya . Ang mga respondents ay mga 12 guro sa kolehiyo mula sa Bataan Peninsula State University (BPSU) na pinili gamit ang convenience sampling. Parehas ang bilang ng lalaki at babaeng guro sa pag-aaral kung saan ang gulang ay nasa pagitan ng 28 -33 ang pinakabata at 51-55 taong gulang. Halos lahat ng gurong respondents ay may mahabang taon sa pagtuturo na nasa pagitan ng 16 hanggang 33 taong karanasan. Sa pagtuturo online ay malamang ang mga gurong may isang taon lang karanasan. Buhat sa mga datos na nakalap sa interbyu ay siyam (9) na themes ang lumitang na tumugon sa mga katanungan inilahad ng pag-aaral. Ang resulta ng pag-aaral ay naghayag na hindi sapat ang kahandaan ng mga guro sa biglaang shift mula sa tradisyonal na face-to-face to online learning/teaching modality kung kaya ang transisyon ay hindi naging madali lalo na doon sa walang sapat na karanasan at kasanayan sa pagtuturo online. Ang mga suliranin ng mga guro sa pagtuturo online ay naka-apekto sa pagtuturo ng mga guro at pagkatuto ng mga estudyante. Ang mga guro ay nasa exploratory stage pa lang at di pa lubos na natutuklasan ang mga opportunities at benepisyo na makakatulong upang maingat ang kanilang kaalaman at kasanayan sa online platform. Ang paghahatid ng kaalaman sa paraan online ay isang kapamaraan ng pagpapatuloy ng pag-aaral sa panahon na may emergencies at mga di inaatasang pangyayari. Ayon sa mga inuulat na resulta ng pag-aaral ay ipinapanukala ang patuloy na suporta, pagsasanay sa mga guro upang matutunan rin nilang yakapin ang mga hamon ng pagbabago sa edukasyon sa kolehiyo na kalakip ng pagtuturo onlin. Ipinapanukala rin ang kolaborasyon sa pagitan ng lahat na stakeholders sa pangunguna ng mga academicians at mga faculty members upang maisaayos ang mga syllabus na outcome-based teaching ang learning strategies tungo sa isang flexible learning na tutugon sa mga suliranin kaugnay ng pagkatuto ng mga estudyante. Sa suliranin tungkol sa connectivity ay kinakailangan ang sama-samang pagtutulungan ng mga educational institutions, pamahalaan at maging ng pribagong sektor upang makapagbuo ng mga infrastructure at upgrading ng mga nariyan ng mga technological infrastructure upang matugunan ang suliranin ng internet connections na siyang pangunahing transit at medium ng komunikasyon sa pagtuturo at pagkatuto online. Sa huli, ipinapanukala rin ang mga pag-aaral na mas malawak ang sakop na aalamin rin ang pananaw di lamang ng mga

guro, kundi pati mga mag-aaral at ang kanilang mga magulang sa mga suliranin at opportunities sa paghahatid ng 2 kaalaman gamit ang online modality. Pinapalagay na ang mga output ng mga pag-aaral ay makakatulong upang makagawa ng informed decision upang maisaayos pa ang online learning and teaching sa bansa.

Keywords: Covid-19 pandemya, online teaching, pagtuturo online, virtual, teknolohiya

Panimula

Ang COVID-19 pandemic ay lumikha ng malaking pagbabago sa takbo ng pamumuhay hindi lamang sa Pilipinas kundi sa buong mundo. Ito ay nagsimula sa China at kumulat sa malaking bahagi ng mundo. Ang pandemyang ito ay sanhi ng novel coronavirus (SARS-COV-2) at lalung kilala bilang COVID-19. Ang epidemyang ito ay walang pinipili bata, matanda, babae, lalaki, mayaman man o mahirap. Subalit sinasabing ang mga matatanda, mga bata at yaong may mga sakit na sanhi ng pagbaba ng “immune system” ay mga “high risks” at mas madaling mahawahan ng virus. Dahil sa bagsik ng “virus” na ito ay nagpatupad ang mga pamahalaan ng mga hakbang upang mapigilan ang pagkalat pa nito. Maraming mga gawain pangkaraniwang ginagawa ng tao ay nahinto o di kaya naman ay nabago. Ang isa sa pinakana-apektuhan ng mga pagbabago sanhi ng pandemyang ito ay ang sektor ng edukasyon. Mula sa datos ng UNESCO (2020) ay 28 milyong estudyanteng Filipino sa iba’t ibang antas ng paaralan ang kailangang tumigil sa bahay.

Ang 3.5 milyong sa mga ito ay mga estudyante na nasa tertiary level mula sa 2,400 higher educational institutions (HEIs). Ang ilan sa mga ito ay gumawa o nagtakda ng mga panuntunan upang maipagpatuloy ng mga estudyante ang kanilang pag-aaral sa kolehiyo (Joaquin, Biana & Dacela). At isa sa mga ito ay ang tinatawag na “modified forms of online learning”. Bukas na ang ideya ng online education sa ating bansa. Ang paggamit ng mga teknolohiya tulad ng “computer”, pag” browse” sa “internet” ay hindi na bago. Ang mga guro ay mayroon na rin “exposure” dito at marahil marami na rin ang may kasanayan dito. Sa katunayan bago pa magkaroon ng pandemya ay inaasahan na ang online platform ay magiging pangunahing paraan ng pagtuturo at pag-aaral (Ventayan, 2018).

Sa Pilipinas ang posibilidad ng online education ay may katagalan pa bagaman ito ay umuusad na sa malalaki at pribadong paaralan na may kakayahan na tustusan ang mga teknolohiya at mga pisikal na kagamitan upang maisakatuparan ito. Subalit ang bansa ay nasa papausbong na ekonomiya pa lamang at salat pa ang nakakarami sa teknolohiyang angkop para sa online learning bukod pa sa kakulangan sa mga imprastraktura upang magkaroon ng mabilis na internet connection na lubhang mahalaga upang maitaguyod ang pag-aaral ng birtwal. Subalit dahil sa pandemya ng Covid-19 ang “online education” ay dagliang ipinatupad bilang bagong paraan ng pag-aaral at pagtuturo sa mga paaralan mula sa pinakamababang antas hanggang sa kolehiyo. Ang biglaang paglipat sa “online” dahil sa pandemya ay nakaragdag sa mga “stresses” at dami ng trabaho na nararanasan ng mga guro sa kolehiyo na nahihirapan ng magbalanse ng pagtuturo, pagsasaliksik (research) at mga, “service obligation” 3 bukod pa sa hirap sa pagbabalanse sa pagitan ng trabaho at buhay (Rapanta, et al, 2020).

Kaugnay nito ay ninais ng may akda na maghain ng isang pag-aaral na naglalayon na tingnan ang mga hamon sa mga guro sa kolehiyo sa panahon ng pandemya ng Covid-19

ugnay sa kanilang kahandaan o readiness saonline education. Layunin ng pag-aaral na higit na maunawaan kung ano ang sanhi ng mga suliranin, pangamba kung mayroon man ng mga guro sa pagtuturo online sa tertiary level.

Layunin ng Pag-aaral

Ang pag-aaral na ito ay aalamin ang mga hamon sa mga guro sa panahon ng Covid-19 pandemic ugnay sa kanilang kahandaan sa pagtuturo online.

Naglalayon na alamin ang sumusunod:

1. Nagkaroon ba ng pagkakataon na makapaghanda ang mga guro sa pagtuturo online?
2. Ano ang mga suliraning nararanasan ng mga guro na nagsisilbing hamon sa kanilang pagtuturo online?
3. Ano ang mga expectations (inaasahan) ng mga guro sa pagtuturo online?

Balangkas Teoretikal/Konseptwal ng Pag-aaral

Sa isinusulong na pag-aaral na ito ay ginamit ang pamamaraan naratolohiya upang mabatid ang mga hamon kinakaharap ng mga guro sa pagtuturo sa panahon ng Covid-19 pandemya ugnay sa kahandaan nila sa online education. Sa pamamaraang ito ay nais tingnan ang kahandaan ng mga guro sa online teaching upang maunawaan ang mga hamon na kinakaharap nila sa pagtuturo sa panahon ng COVID-19 pandemya.

Ayon sa Contingency theory ang isang organization ay isang open system na kailangang maka-agapay sa nagbabagong kapaligiran. Kung ipapaliwanag ang epekto ng online education sa pagtuturo sa panahon ng Covid19 ay maaaring gamitin ang teoryang ito na nagsasabi na kailangan maka-agapay ang mga guro sa mga pagbabago kaugnay ng kanilang pagtuturo. Ang dagliang pagbabago, pagtigil (disruption) sa normal na gawi ay nagiging sanhi ng pagkabahala, pagkalito at distress na isang pangkaraniwang response ng tao sa pagbabago (Schafer,2012). Sa teorya ng pagbabago ang tuon ay nasa epekto at tugon o response ng indibidwal sa isang pagbabago. Subalit ang response sa mga pagbabago ay naaayon sa kahandaan ng indibidwal na ito-sa pagbabagong ito. Sa pag-aaral, ang mga hamon, tulad ng mga suliranin kaugnay ng online teaching at mga saloobin ng mga guro ay features kung gaano kahanda ang mga ito sa pagbabagong ito. Ang pagpapatupad ng mga Pamantasan at kolehiyo ng online education upang di maputol ang pag-aaral ng mga mag-aaral sa tertiary level ay isang reactive response- o pagtugon sa sitwasyon o crisis –ang pandemya.

Tulad ng nabanggit na ang pangsamantalang pagsasara ng mga paaralan kabilang ang mga Pamantasan ay bahagi lamang ng pamamaraan upang maiwasan ang pagkalat ng virus. Ipinaliwanag ng mga “teacher educators” na ang “transitioning” sa online teaching dahil sa crisis (tulad ng pandemya) ay binago ang “normal 4 longitudinal perceptions” ng paghahanda at kahandaan (Cutri, Mena & Whiting, 2020). Ang pandemya ay nagkaroon ng pangangailangan sa mga guro na mag-transition sa online teaching kahit na kaunti o walang paghahanda ang mga ito at hindi nabigyan ng katiyakan kung ito ay pansamantala lamang o

magiging permanente. Sa pag-aaral tungkol sa kahandaan (readiness) ay mahalagang malaman kung anong pangyayari o circumstance ito gagamitin.

Ayon sa ilang pananaw na nabanggit sa pag-aaral ni Naji at iba pa, ang mga literature tungkol sa readiness for change o kahandaan sa pagbabago ay nakatuon sa pagbabago na pinaghandaan at itinataguyod ng pamunuan. Ang kahandaan (readiness) ay maunawaan sa pagtutol o pagsangayon sa isang pagbabago. Kapag ang mga guro ay hindi handa ay maaring maging negatibo ang kanilang pananaw at mababaw hanggang sa walang motibasyon upang maging committed sa online teaching.

Ang intensyon at reaksyon ng indibidwal ay bunga ng kanilang kahandaan at mayroon impact sa outcome ng online education (Naji, et al. 2020). Sinususugan ng pag-aaral na ito ang teorya o pananaw na ang readiness o kahandaan ang puno't dulo sanhi ng mga suliranin at hamon sa mga guro sa online teaching. Ang mga suliranin ay bunga ng mga pagbabago na hindi napaghandaan at napagplanuhan sa isang di inaasahang pangyayari tulad ng pandemya. Ang teorya hinggil sa kahandaan ay siyang naging batayan sa pagbuo ng conceptual framework sa pag-aaral na ito batay sa pamamaraang naratolohiya upang ma-explore ang mga hamon sa pagtuturo ugnay sa kahandaan ng mga guro sa online teaching. Ang interview ay ang pangunahing pamamaraan ng pagkolekta ng mga datos na siyang magiging basehan ng pagtaya ng kahandaan ng mga guro at ng kanilang mga inaasahan o expectations na bunga ng pagtuturo sa online.

Kaugnay ng Literatura at Pag-aaral

Inihayag ni Mouza (2020) sa isang artikulo, na ang pagsasara ng mga paaralan sanhi ng Covid-19 pandemya ay nangangailangan ng bagong modelo para sa kahandaan at edukasyon ng mga guro upang maging epektibo sa pagsasama ng teknolohiya sa pagtuturo sa pisikal man o "virtual" na lugar. Ang mga suliranin at hamon sa mga guro sa online education ay binigyan pansin sa panulat ni Malindog-Uy (2020). Ayon sa kanya ay may pangangailangan ng iupdate ang mga guro na hindi sanay at gamay sa "dynamics" ng teknolohiya ay kailangang mag-upgrade ng kanilang kaalaman dito. Kinakailagan ng mga guro na magkaroon ng karampatang lebel ng kompetensya at kasanayan kailangan kung ang pagtuturo at pag-aaral online ay maging epektibo. Kung wala ng mga ito, maaari itong maging hadlang sa isang matagumpay na "online learning" (Malindog-Uy,2020).

Ayon kay, Major (2015), napakahalagang pag-ukulan ng pansin ang kahandaan ng mga guro kung nais na baguhin ang pagtuturo sa pamamagitan ng online. Upang magbahagi ng kaalaman sa online ay kinakailangang may kakaibang kakayahan tulad ng mataas na antas ng "sensory skills" tulad ng abstraksyon, "inference" at pagbabalangkas at pagpapaliwanag upang makapagbahagi ng kaalaman sa online. Samantala itinuturing na ang pinakamahalaga at mabigat na hamon sa mga paaralan ay nag-ugat sa kanilang kahandaan sa pagharap sa krisis na sanhi ng pandemya (Bhagat & Kim,2020).

Ilang pananaw ang binigyan pansin nila tungkol sa kahandaan ng mga "educational institutions". Ang pagkakaroon ng alinlangan sa kahandaan ng mga educational institution ay naihayag nina Houlden at Veletsianos (2020). Bunga nito ang hindi maayos na paggamit ng paaralan sa kanilang resources at pati ang pagkakaroon ng mga estudyante may

limitadong access sa internet at technology ay makaka-apekto rin sa kakayahan ng mga paaralan na tumugon sa pangangailangan at kakayahan ng mag-aaral na sumabay sa "online learning environment (Zhong,2020). Ayon kay Laguna (2020), ang online learning platform ay may kaakibat na maraming suliranin. Sinabi niya na ang online na pagtuturo at pag-aaral ay nangangailangan ng pagpa-plano, preparasyon, kasipagan at kasanayan.

Dahil sa kinakailangan ipatupad ang online classes upang maiwasan ang pagkalat ng Covid -19 virus, ito ay nangangailangan rin ng transpormasyon ng mindset. Ito ay nagiging hamon sa mga guro na kinakailangan na maka-agapay na mayroon matinding sensitivity sa online format. Hamon din para sa mga guro ang access sa internet at pagkakaroon ng stable connection dito at gayundin ang kasanayang gumamit ng mga teknolohiyang kailangan sa online instruction (Alea,L. et al.,2020). Sinabi ng isang pag-aaral na ang Covid-19 pandemya ay nagbunga ng mga hamon sa mga paaralan lalu na sa kolehiyo.

Ang partikular na hamon ay ang mabilisan at di inaasahan pagbabago kung saan ang mga courses ay ituturo online sa halip na sa loob ng pamantasan. Sa new normal ito ang virtual classroom. Sinabi pa ng mga may akda na ang pagtuturo ang pag-aaral ay nangangailangan ng "pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) kaugnay sa desenyong at pagsasaayos para sa mainam na learning experiences at makabuo ng isang learning environment sa tulong ng digital teknolohiya (Rapanta, et.al.,2020). Kaugnay nito, ang mga guro ay dapat mayroon kaalaman at kakayahan sa pagtuturo at paggamit ng mga teknolohiya (Tria,2020). Sa pag-aaral ni Ozudogru (2020) ay nabatid na ang mga kinakaharap na suliranin ng mga guro ay nahahati sa limang themes na inilantad ng mga datos na nakuha sa mga pakikipanayam sa mga pre-service teachers mula sa Turkey. Mula sa qualitative study ni Ozudogru ay nalantad ang mga themes kung saan na identified ang mga suliranin kinakaharap ng mga gurong na-interbyu. May mga suliranin bunsod ng implementasyon ng distance learning, tulad ng mataas na workload; mula sa mga mag-aaral ay nabanggit ang kawalang ng epektibong komunikasyon at interaction.

Bukod dito ay ang mga suliranin kaugnay ng mga teknikal na aspeto na tinawag niyang mga impossibilities o barriers sa matagumpay na pagtuturo online. Ang mga ganitong suliranin ay hamon lalu na sa mga gurong walang kahandaan na ayon sa pag-aaral nina Sareen at Nangia (2020). Paraan ng Pananaliksik Desenyong Pag-aaral Ang pag-aaral na ito ay isang naratolohiya. Ang naratolohiya ay isang uri ng qualitative research na naglalayon na saliksikin at i-conseptualize ang karanasan ng subjects sa isang sitwasyon. Ito ang desenyong ginamit sa pag-aaral na ito na nagnanais na malaman ang mga hamon sa mga guro sa pagtuturo online sa panahon ng pandemya batay sa kanilang kahandaan. Paraan ng Seleksyon ng mga Guro Ang Bataan Peninsula State University (BPSU) ang lokal kung saan isinagawa ang pag-aaral. Ang mga guro na nagtuturo sa tertiary level ay ang napiling respondents sa pag-aaral. Ang tinatawag na convenience sampling ang ginamit na paraan ng pagpili ng mga guro na kasali sa pag-aaral. Dahil sa pandemya kung saan may limitasyon ang mga pagtitipon-tipon kung kaya ang bilang ng mga subjects na guro ay na limitahan sa 12 o 24% sa tinatayang 50 guro ng BPSU. Ang mga napiling guro ay tanging yaong lang mga nagtuturo online sa mga mag-aaral na nasa tertiary level. Ang pagkuha ng datos ay mula sa panayam o interbyu sa mga napiling mga guro na ginawa sa pamamagitan ng pagsunod sa mga health protocols na ipinatutupad sa panahon ng pandemya. Pagsusuri sa Datos Ang

unang hakbang sa pagsusuri sa mga datos ay ang pagta-transcribe sa interbyu. Masusing pagsubaybay ang ginawa sa prosesong ito, upang matiyak na tama, walang labis at walang kulang ang transcription na ginawa. Isinalang ang tape upang mapakinggan at masundan at matiyak na tapat ang pagkakatranscribed ng encoder sa mga sinabi ng bawat guro sa interbyu. Ang pagsusuri sa mga datos ay ayon sa content analysis na ginawa upang ma-identify ang mga specific characteristics ng mga mensahe mula sa mga narratives ng mga gurong respondents.

Resulta ng Pag-aaral

Demographic Profile ng mga Guro

Sa unang table ay makikita ang distribusyon ng mga gurong respondents ayon sa kanilang kasarian; gulang at bilang ng taon bilang mga guro.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Kasarian	No. of Respondents	%
Lalake	06	50
Babae	06	50
TOTAL	12	100
Gulang		
33-38 taong gulang	02	17
39-44 taong gulang	0	0
45-50 taong gulang	07	58
51-55 taong gulang	03	25
TOTAL	12	100
Bilang ng Taong karanasan sa Pagtuturo		
15 taong pababa	01	08
16-21	03	25
22-27	06	50
28-33	02	17
TOTAL	12	100

Ang panayam na ginawa sa mga gurong respondents ay ibinatay sa mga katanungan itinaas sa pag-aaral na ito. Ang mga katanungang ito ay ang sumusunod:

1. Nagkaroon ba ng pagkakataon na makapaghanda ang mga guro sa pagtuturo online?
2. Ano ang mga suliraning nararanasan ng mga guro na nagsisilbing hamon sa kanilang pagtuturo online?
3. Ano ang mga expectations (inaasahan) ng mga guro sa pagtuturo online?

Siyam na tema (themes) ang nasala mula sa mga datos na nakalap sa mga katugunan ng mga gurong respondents sa pag-aaral.

1. Nagkabiglaan kaya't walang sapat na paghahanda.
2. Ang adjustment mula sa tradisyonal na paraan tungo sa pagtuturo online ay nakasalalay sa karanasan at kaalaman sa paggamit ng mga teknolohiya tulad ng computer.
3. Connectivity at mga bagay na may kaugnayan sa paggamit ng teknolohiya sa pagtuturo online
4. Maraming distractions, walang focus, walang interes at interaksyon sa pagitan ng guro at estudyante
5. Matrabaho at matagal na nakababad sa mga devices na nakaka-apekto sa paningin.
6. Inaasahan na malinang ang responsible at independent or self-learning sa mga estudyante.
7. Upgrade o itaas ang antas ng kaalaman at kakayahan sa paggamit ng mga teknolohiyang pang online
8. Convenience o ginhawa, time-controlled management, multi-tasking at health and safety.
9. Paraan ng pagpapatuloy ng pag-aaral sa panahon ng walang katiyakan o 'uncertainties'

1. Nagkaroon ba ng pagkakataon na makapaghanda ang mga guro sa pagtuturo online? Theme 1. Nagkabiglaan kung kaya't walang sapat na paghahanda

Ang unang tema ay tinugon ang katanungan kung nagkaroon ng pagkakataon na makapaghanda ang mga guro sa pagtuturo online. Halos lahat ng mga gurong napili sa pag-aaral na ito ay nagsabi na ang paghahanda sa dagliang pagtuturo online ay hindi sapat Nang tanungin kung nakapaghanda para sa pagtuturo online ang sagot ng

Respondent 1 ay: "

...Hindi po Ma'am kasi first time ko pong gagamit ng google classroom. Although, ginagamit po namin siya sa Masteral, pero hindi po kasi kami yung palaging nagpresent. Usually, po yung mga classmates ko medyo nahirapan po akong gamayin siya. Nag-aaral pa kong aralin yung google classroom via youtube. Tapos dahil hindi siya yung official na meet, may mga kulang po siya na application sa google classroom unlike po sa Gsuite mayroon siya".

Si Respondent 2, ay itinuring na parang paghahanda ang paggamit sa klase ng internet sa mga activities na kinakailangan ang internet connection. Kung kaya naiisip niya na ito ay isang paghahanda na rin niya sa pagtuturo online.

Ayon kay Respondent 2 "...

Kasi dati yung sa subject ko naman na Medical Sciences, ever since po kahit face to face pa. May mga times na online kami dahil kailangan namin ng net... Kaya ang ginagamit pa rin namin iyon Ma'am, ngayon ko lang nalaman na in a way na parang paghahanda iyon. Kasi naman nagkapandemya at hindi natin alam na magkaka-pandemya". Sinabi ni Respondent 3 na lahat ay halos hindi handa sa pagtuturo online dahil nagkabiglaan.

Sa tanong kung nagkaroon ng pagkakataong makapaghanda sa online teaching ay sinabi niya na:

"Definitely lahat tayo ay hindi kasi nagkabiglaan. As I remember March 17 yata iyon, nang biglang nag-announce na wala ng papasok. As in hindi walang pasok, kung hindi wala ng papasok sa school lahat ng empleyado at estudyante. And then, kinabukasan nga noon ang alam ko midterm exam natin? Hindi ba? So, ibig sabihin hindi tayo lahat handa although ipinagamit na sa atin yung google classroom noon na nag-seminar pa tayo. Pero hindi naman ganoon kabilis na makuha mo yung record ng estudyante. Ang problema kasi talaga yung communication, iyong online...online na communication natin. So iyon ang naging problema hindi tayo...wala kasing I don't know. Basta ang alam ko walang nagkaroon ng paghahanda ...nagkabiglaan."

Ayon kay Respondent 4 ay hindi sapat ang mga initial training. Sa kanyang tugon ay sinabi niya na: ". Pero iyong kahandaan pala hindi lang sa ganoon eh, pagka talagang nandoon ka na ... sa sitwasyon, di mo talaga masasabi na... ganoon ka ka-prepared. Halos iisa rin ang tugon ni Respondent 5, na kahit na mayroong training ay hindi sapat lalu na't biglaan. Ang mga tugon ng iba pang respondents ay nagsasabi na bagaman mayroon mga pagsasanay at paghahanda ang mga ito ay hindi sapat sa biglaang pagtuturo online. Tulad ng sagot ni Respondent 9 na ang training ay saglit lamang kaya hindi sapat sa biglaang pagtuturo online. "Oo, pero saglit lang di ba. Kasi... anong tawag dito, kumbaga hindi naman tayo ready kaagad ... doon sa online dahil nga sa pandemic—biglaan."

Theme 2. Ang adjustment sa pagtuturo online mula sa face-to-face ay naaayon sa karanasan at kasanayan ng guro

Sa ikalawang theme na nakalap sa mga datos ay naghayag na may epekto ang karanasan at kasanayan ng guro sa kanyang adjustment mula sa pagtuturo sa tradisyonal na face to face tungo sa pagtuturo online. Tulad ng makikita sa Table 2 ang nakakarami sa mga gurong kasama sa pag-aaral (75%) ay may isang taon karanasan sa pagtuturo online; samantalang ang natitirang 25% ay may 2 o higit pang taong nagtuturo online.

Sa ikalawang theme na nahayag mula sa mga panayam o interbyu sa mga gurong respondents ang kaugnayan ng karanasan sa pagtuturo online ng mga guro at kanilang kaalaman o kasanayan sa paggamit ng mga teknolohiya sa paghahanda at adjustment para sa virtual o online teaching.

Si Respondent 1 ay may isang taon karanasan sa pagtuturo online. Sinabi niya na bagaman mayroon siyang training ay nahirapan pa rin siya sa pag-adjust mula face-to-face tungo sa virtual class.

Ayon sa kanya: “[m]edyo...nahirapan lang pagdating doon sa ibang way ...kung paano...ngayon kasi hindi na siya basta power point lang medyo naging dagdag lang,,,Kasi kailangan ko ng magbigay ng link...Ili-link ko pa siya sa presentation sa Youtube. Medyo nanibago ako pagdating doon, sa power point walang problema e pero sa other means, medyo doon nagkakaroon ng adjustment kung paano ko maitatawid talaga. Kahit may training, mga seminars at mga pagsasanay ay hindi garantiya sa isang madaling pag-adjust.”

Ayon kay Respondent 4 na may 2 taon karanasan sa online class, maraming mga di inaasahan sitwasyon na haharapin ang isang guro sa online teaching. Subalit ayon sa kanya dahil sa may karanasan at may training ay hindi gaanong mahirap ang adjustment.

Sinabi ni Respondent 4: “...may previous experience na ko sa graduate school kaya hindi na ako ganoon kahirap pagdating sa preparation...”pero mayroon pa rin akong mga...adjustments”.

Ganito rin ang saloobin ni Respondent 5. Ayon sa kanya, ang mga pagsasanay sa paggamit ng iba’t ibang platform sa paggawa ng module ay hindi naman madali itong i-apply lalo na ayon sa requirements ng paaralan.

Ayon kay Respondent 5 : “[m]ahirap gumawa ang module lalo na sa klase ng format na ibinigay sa’tin ng university...mahirap i-translate na parangmakikipag-usap ka sa estudyante...It would take time para ma-conceptualize mo at isulat lahat yon” .

Ito ay pananaw rin ni Respondent 6.

Bagaman naka- attend siya ng mga seminars at training sa webinar bago nasalang sa mga online classes ay inamin niya na mahirap at :“...medyo matrabaho po yong encoding ng lesson para po mai-convert siya sa module type”. Ayon pa rin sa gurong respondent na ito, kailangan itong i-ayon sa syllabus base sa requirement ng Pamantasan upang umangkop sa tinatawag na blended learning.

Tulad nila ay naghayag si Respondent 7 na ang mga training at paghahanda sa online teaching ay hindi sapat kung kaya ang pagsasalin at adjustment ay hindi mabilis. Ganito rin halos ang sinabi ni Respondent 8. Hindi naging madali ang adjustment at preparation tungo sa virtual class dahil kailangan pag-aralan ang LMS (Learning Management System) at kailangan ma-explore yong mga bagong features nito para magamit. Tulad nila sinabi ni

Respondent 11 na ang paghahanda ay hindi sapat sa preparation sa pagtuturo online na ayon sa kanya ay inabot “...higit 7 buwan ang paggawa at pagsasalin...”

Sa kabilang dako ang kasanayan at kaalaman sa paggamit ng mga teknolohiyang pangkomunikasyon ay nakatulong sa mga guro na makapag-adjust sa online teaching at hindi gaanong nahirapan.

Sa kaso nina Respondents 2 at 3 ang kaalaman, karanasan at training ay mga advantages sa adjustment mula sa tradisyonal na klase patungo sa virtual na klase. Sinabi ni Respondent 2 na mayroon siyang kaalaman sa virtual class.

Ipinaliwanag niya na sa: “...pagdating po sa virtual hindi po ako masyadong nahirapan. Kasi noong hindi pa po online lahat po ng lecture ko is naka-power point na. So

ready to present na lang (po) siya, tapos plus po doon kapag video presentation may mga naka-ready na siya sa Youtube. Ida-download na lang, ise-send na lang (po yong link sa bata plus na po nakamodule na sila. May hawak silang module na susundan...additional information na lang (po) yong sa akin". Ganito rin halos ang kaso ni Respondent 3. Sinabi nito na : "...sa case ko kahit paano naman knowledgeable ako sa computer, sa online, madali lang din. Madali ang preparation ng teacher na may alam sa online, may alam sa computer, may alam sa (ika nga) sa technology...sa paghahanda sa akin personally, mabilis kasi nga nag-seminar na tayo".

Ang mga tugon nina Respondents 9 at 10 ay sumasang-ayon dito. Sinabi nila na sila ay nakapaghanda at nakapag-adjust dahil mayroon silang training.

Idinagdag pa ni Respondents 12 na ang paghahanda tulad ng mga pagdalo sa mga seminars at mga pag-aaral sa Youtube ay nakatulong: "kung papaano ang gagawin para makagawa ng mga aralin na magagamit sa virtual na klase...kung kaya ay naging madali sa akin ang pagsasalin ng aralin patungo sa virtual na klase".

Ayon sa datos na nakuha sa mga tugon ng mga gurong respondents ang kanilang kahandaan sa pagtuturo online ay hindi sapat, lalo na at nagkabisiglaan. Hindi naman madali ang isalin sa digital format ang mga teaching materials lalo na sa mga gurong di sapat ang digital at ICT skills. Hindi sila techy at walang masyadong kasanayan sa makabagong teknolohiya pang komunikasyon ang sa pagtuturo online. Sa kabuuang ang karamihan sa mga guro ay nagsasabing hindi sila ganap na handa, dahil nagkabisiglaan. Bagaman ang ilan ay mayroon karanasan sa paggamit ng teknolohiya sa pagtuturo at may pagsasanay o training para sa pagtuturo online ang mga ito ay hindi sapat sa isang biglaang pagpapatupad nito.

2. Ano ang mga suliraning nararanasan ng mga guro na nagsisilbing hamon sa kanilang pagtuturo online?

Ang themes 3,4 at 5 na nakalap sa mga tugon sa interbyu ng mga gurong respondents ay naghayag ng mga suliranin na nagsilbing hamon sa mga guro sa kanilang pagtuturo sa online.

Theme 3. Connectivity at mga bagay na may kaugnayan sa aplikasyon ng teknolohiya sa pagtuturo online

Ang connectivity ng mga guro at maging ng mga estudyante ay itinuring na suliranin naging hamon sa pagtuturo online. Ang lahat ng mga gurong respondents ay naghayag na ang suliranin hinggil sa komunikasyon sa pagitan ng guro at estudyante ay malaking hamon sa pagtuturo sa online. Ayon sa mga respondents, ang madalas na power interruptions at mahinang signal, walang load, unstable hanggang sa walang internet connections ay mga suliranin kaugnay ng connectivity na nabanggit ng mga respondents. Ito ay binigyan ng diin ni Respondent 12 bilang suliranin sa Pilipinas.

Ayon sa kanya : "Isa sa naging suliranin na naaranasan ko na nagsilbing hamon sa pagtuturo online ay ang internet koneksyon sa Pilipinas. Lahat ata ay naging problema ito...". Ayon naman kay Respondent 8 unstable internet connections at pati yung kaalaman sa iba'tibang aplikasyon at paggamit ng mga gadgets o teknolohiya ay mga suliranin na nagiging hamon sa kanya. Ang mga ito ay tinukoy rin na problema ng iba pang mga respondents. Ayon kay Respondent 1 ay madalas na

idinadahilan ng kanyang estudyante kung bakit hindi naka-online ay ang pagkawala ng koneksyon, na hindi niya pinaniwalaan noong una.

Sinabi niya na: “Kaya lang (siyempre) habang tumatagal tingin ko iyan ang pinakamalaking challenge...yong connection.” At ito ay itinuturing nyang matinding hamon sa kanyang pagtuturo sapagka’t; “... hindi ako sanay na walang kausap. Kasi parang ganooon e, hindi mo rin kasi ma-required na sa buong isang oras at kalahati nakabukas camera nila. Kasi sasabihin nila ‘Sir naka-data lang po ako, mauubos na po data ko kaya kailangan kong mag-off ng camera’ yung mga ganooon”.

Connectivity rin ang laging suliranin na nararanasan ni Respondent 3 sa kanyang mga estudyante at maging sa sarili niya.

Ayon sa kanya: “ Hanggang ngayon ang palaging sagot ng bata is walang internet, mahina ang internet o walang gadget. Tapos iyong kapag nag-lockdown sa barangay nila, naranasan ko iyan e especially sa Mariveles. Hindi sila makapag-load ng internet kasi nga nag-data lang sila, hindi makalabas bawal naman talaga. Naranasan ko iyan noong karamihan ng case sa Mariveles, ang dami sa aking hindi nakakaattend online. Tapos kapag uma-attend naman ng online bigla ring nawawala, naubos na ang data, humina ang internet, maraming dahilan iyong bata.”

Nabatid mula sa mga tugon ng mga gurong respondents sa pag-aaral na ito, na ang koneksyon sa internet ay ang pinakamadulas na suliranin ng mga guro at maging ng kanilang mga estudyante. Ang suliraning ito ay nararanasan ng halos lahat ng mga guro at mga estudyante sa buong Pilipinas. Ayon kina na Belgica at kanyang mga kasama (2020), ang Pilipinas ay isa sa mga bansa sa Asya na may mabagal na internet. Wireless connectivity ay isang hamon sa lahat ng stakeholders sa online edukasyon sa bansa, kung saan may mga ulat na kailangan pang magtungo ang mga guro at estudyante sa mataas na lugar upang makakuha ng signal.

Inihayag ng nina Belgica, ang ulat ni Adonis (2020), na ipinalalagay ng mga guro na ang mabagal hanggang sa walang koneksyon ang isang dahilan sa mababang turnout ng mga mag-aaral. Ang mabagal at kawalang ng internet connection ay malaking hamon sa lahat kasama ang mga estudyante na nasa liblib na lugar. Ayon sa isang pag-aaral, nang ipinatupad ang online teaching/learning modality dahil sa pandemya, ang agwat sa pagitan ng mayroon connectivity at doon sa wala ay lumaki. Ang pagpapatuloy ng edukasyon sa panahon ng pandemya ay malaking hamon sa mga guro at estudyante lalo na sa ‘access’ at ‘internet connectivity’ (Dayagbil, F., et.al, 2021).

Theme 4. Walang interaction, walang interes o motibasyon at mga distractions

Ang mga gurong respondents ay tiningnan ang pagkakaiba ng face to face sa online na platform ng pagtuturo sa pagtukoy ng mga challenges at suliranin na naging hamon sa kanilang pagtuturo online. Sinabi na ang kaibahan ng online sa face to face ay nakikita kung seryoso ang estudyante at maaaring agad makuha ang atensyon nito. Pero sa online, ayon kay

Respondent 3 , “...hindi mo masabi kung nakikinig ba sila, hindi mo masabi kung seryoso ba sila”. Hamon para sa gurong ito ang interactions sa pagitan ng guro at kanyang estudyante. Ipinaliwanag ni Respondent 3 na: “Iba kasi ang face to face talaga (eh), iba ang learning sa face to face, iba sa online...Sinasabi ko sa mga estudyante ko...ang pakiramdam

ko 50% lang ang naibibigay kong knowledge kapag online. Unlike sa face-to-face mayroon tayong interactions, nakikita ko sa inyong expressions Ninyo, kapag nag-activity kayo Ganado kayo kasi magkakasama kayo...”

Ganito rin halos ang pananaw ni Respondent 1. Ayon sa kanya ang pagkawala ng personal touch ang isang hamon sa mga guro sa pagtuturo online. Sinabi niya na: “...[a]ng pinakalimitasyon ng virtual natin, although hi-tech siya...pero para sa akin kulang ang personal touch, yung interaksyon ng guro at estudyante para sa akin iyon ang limitasyon..

Kasi kapag kaharap mo sila para sa akin (Maám) yung motivation mo sa pagiging teacher ay base sa expression nila, yung galaw nila sa klase, yung gestures nila, yung body language nila sa klase”. Ayon naman kay Respondent 10, ay malaking hamon sa pagtuturo online ang limitadong interaksyon sa pagitan ng estudyante at guro at limitado rin ang mga group activities. Ito ay sinang-ayunan din ni Respondent 12 sa kanyang tugon sa interbyu.

Sinabi niya na: “...[m]ahirap din na hindi mo tahasang nakikita ang mga mag-aaral at limitado ang engagement during virtual classes”. Kaakibat ng mga suliranin sa pagtuturo online ay ang mga abala o disruptions na nakaka-apekto sa focus at konsentrasyon ng mga estudyante dahil sila ay nasa bahay, Sinabi ni Respondent 2: “...minsan maririnig mo sa background, tinatawag ng nanay, siyempre kahit sabihin mong online class hindi maiiwasan nasa bahay (po) talaga ang bata. Tapos kahit tawagin mo (ma’am) hindi sumasagot ibig sabihin wala siya sa online.” Iba’t ibang gawain na nagiging abala sa pag-aaral ng mga estudyante kapag nasa bahay.

Ayon pa rin kay Respondent 3, “tatawaging ng parent o inutusan, pinagbantay dito, pinag-alaga ng kapatid...”

Ang ganitong mga abala sa mga mag-aaral ay hindi mapipigilan at ayon kay Respondent 4, ang focus ng mga estudyante sa pag-aaral ay di kontrol ng mga guro. Lalu na sa mga disruptions dala ng sitwasyon tulad ng tinawag ng magulang o may ginawang iba, ayon kay Respondent 5.

Napakaraming distractions sa kapaligiran sa bahay na nakakabawas sa focus at konsentrasyon sa pag-aaral ng mga bata. Ito ang binigyan pansin ni Respondent 7 sa pagtukoy sa mga disruptions sa class setting: “*Pagdating naman sa...class setting,yung mga estudyante kasi may mga...since”nasa bahay nauutusan ng magulang habang nagka-klase.*

Challenge rin iyon. Tapos yung ingay sa bata o teacher na nakatira doon, sa kagaya ko, tabing daan. May bumubusina, may tumatahol na aso, may umiiyak...” Suliranin sa mga guro ang kawalan ng interes ng mga estudyante sa pag-aaral at ito ay napatunayan sa iba’t ibang pag-aaral na tumalakay sa mga hamon at suliranin kaugnay ng pagtuturo online. Sa isang artikulo ay inihayag ni Shore (2020), na ang online ay isang mainam na platform sa pagtuturo subalit tinatangal nito ang tinatawag na koneksyon sa pagitan ng guro at mga estudyante, kung kaya pati ang kanilang motibasyon, interaksyon at pati na rin ang kakayahan ng guro na makaagapay sa teknolohiya at course materials ay nawawala. Ang mga suliranin kaugnay sa learning o pagkatuto ng mga bata ay binigyan ng pansin ng ilang mga pag-aaral hinggil sa mga hamon sa online teaching and learning sa panahon ng pandemya. Sa isang pag-aaral ay

inihayag na ang kawalan ng interaksyon sa online class ay nagiging dahilan kung bakit madaling mabaling ang atensyon ng mga estudyante sa mga iba't ibang distraksyon tulad sa mga smartphones, alagang hayop o ano pa man na nakakaagaw ng pansin ng mga bata habang nagka-klase online.

Dahil wala ang interaksyon tulad ng sa "face to face", kung kaya sinasapantaha na mawawalan ng interes ang mga estudyante sa online class (Amadora,2020). Sa halos katulad na pag-aaral ay naghayag ng mga pananaw ng mga guro tungkol sa mga suliranin kaakibat ng pagtuturo online. Ayon sa mga datos na nakuha nina Moralista at Oducado (2020), ang mga estudyante ay hindi ganap na natututo sa online, at wala rin gaanong interaksyon sa pagitan ng guro at mga estudyante, at tulad ng pananaw ni Respondent 1 ang mga talakayan sa online ay impersonal at walang buhay, bukod pa sa may kahirapan i-manage at mataas na degree ng depersonalization. Ayon kina Belgica (2020) ang kawalan ng motivation at partisipasyon sa online classes ay isang mabigat na hamon sa mga guro at maging sa mga magulang ng estudyante. Di tulad ng sa face to face and mga guro ay may limitadong involvement sa pagdedesiplina sa mga bata at ito ay nalipat sa mga magulang sa online classes.

Theme 5. Matrabaho, nakababad ng matagal sa mga devices tulad ng computer, laptop etc.

Sa mga panayam sa mga gurong respondents ay masasalamit ang pananaw na nahihirapan sila sa pagtuturo online. Maliban sa mga binanggit na suliranin na naging hamon sa kanila, ay nasagap ang kahirapan sa mga guro sa pagtuturo online dahilang sa matrabaho at matagal na oras sa harap ng computer. Ito ay naging obvious sa mga pananalita ng mga gurong respondents.

Maliban kay Respondent 6, ang iba ay di tuwirang nagbanggit ng suliraning ito. Ayon kay Respondent 6: "...talagang mananakit ang mga mata mo kasi solo mo lahat ng trabaho. Gagawa ka ng online lesson, magse-send ka. Pag nagpa-exam ka ng online, tsetsekan mo ulit sa google classroom. Halos nakababad iyong mata natin...ang laki nga ng inilabo (po) ng mata ko..." 2. Ano ang mga expectations (inaasahan) ng mga guro sa pagtuturo online? Ang huling tanong sa pag-aaral na ito ay nagnanais malaman kung ano ang mga expectations o mga inaasahan sa pagtuturo online. Apat na themes ang nakalap sa mga katugunan ng mga gurong respondents sa tanong na ito.

Theme 6 . Inaasahan na malinang ang responsible at individual or self-learning sa mga estudyante

Buhat sa isang positibong pananaw, tinitingnan ng mga respondents ang magandang pagkakataon ma-improve ang pagkakatatuto o learning ng mga bata. Inaasahan ni Respondent 1 na malinang sa mga estudyante yong responsible at self-and independent learning. Ayon kay Respondent 1: "...tinignan ko siya sa positive side yung pagiging independent ng bata sa pag-aaral. Hopefully iyon sana ibig sabihin this time lalo na kung module. Kasi may asynchronous tayo yung responsibility nila , para sa akin iyon ang nakita kong opportunity ang makita ang pagiging responsible student talaga"

Hindi nalalayo ang pananaw ni Respondent 8 sa pagkakataon na malinang ang self o individual learning sa mga mag-aaral. Sa online class ay nagbubukas ng pagkakataon para sa

independent learning. Ang mga estudyante at maging guro man ay may access sa internet upang magsaliksik ng mga impormasyon na makakadagdag sa kanilang kaalaman.

Ayon kay Respondent 8: "Kasi di ba kapag may hindi tayo alam, pwede rin tayong mag-search. ..Ikaw mismo sa sarili mo i-develop ang independent learning. At saka yung mga idifferent application na kailangan natin matutunan. So gusto mong --try so aaralin mo siya. Iyon yung mga opportunities na nag-open para sa teachers as well sa students."

Theme 7. Upgrade ang kaalaman at kakayahan gumamit ng mga teknolohiya gamit sa pagtuturo online

Nakita ng mga gurong respondents na maraming oportunidad sa pagtuturo online ang makakatulong upang maragdagan ang kaalaman sa paggamit ng mga makabagong teknolohiya at kaalaman sa pagtuturo online.

Ayon kay Respondent 8: "yung exposure to a lot of resources,, kasi di ba gamit natin internet. Maraming available resources. At saka yung mga idifferent application na kailangan natin matutunan. So gusto mong --try so aaralin mo siya. Iyon yng mga opportunities na nag-open para sa teachers as well sa students."

Magkatulad rin sila ni Respondent 8 sa inaasahan sa bunga ng online teaching. Sang-ayon sa kanya: "... ang nakikita ko lang na oportunidad is yung ma-upgrade yung teacher pagdating sa makabagong technology na nagaganap sa ating ...lipunan. Halimbawa, paggamit ...ng gadget na dati rati hindi naman (po) ginagamit ng teacher. Usually ano tayo data (Maám) manila paper, ngayon hindi na, pwede na siyang via-email, via video presentation. Upgraded na yung teacher hindi na siya yung traditional."

Si Respondent 6 naman ay inaasahan na sa paggamit niya ng mga makabagong teknolohiya sa pagtuturo online ay maiaangat niya ang antas ng kanyang kaalaman sa mga ito. Katulad rin ni Respondent 12 ang pagtuturo online ay nagbigay ng pagkakataon gumamit ng teknolohiya at turuan maging mga mag-aaral na gamitin ng tama ang mga ito sa pag-aaral.

Theme 8. Convenience, health safety, multi-tasking at time management

Isa sa naging advantage ng online teaching sa mga guro ay ang pagkakaroon ng kontrol sa kanilang mga oras walang pressure.

Ayon kay Respondent 7: "...yong mayroon kang sapat na oras na hindi ka male-late. Tapos mayroon kang ...pwede pang gawin. Kasi napo-program mo kung ano, kung kailang ka magsi-synchronous , kailan ka maga-asynchronous iyon. Tapos pwede ...yong multitasking. Pwede kang mag multi-tasking, hindi katulad ng papasok talaga ng doon ka lang...parang kontrol mo naman iyong oras mo." Ang ganitong pananaw sa mga expectations na bunga ng pagtuturo online ay ang pagkakaroon ng panahon sa pamilya at ang kaginhawahan o convenience sa pagtuturo ay inayunan rin ni Respondent 5. Ayon sa gurong respondent na ito: "Ikaw bilang magulang nandoon ka na sa bahay. Pwedent ginagawa mo iyong responsibility mo bilang guro ...yet kasama mo iyong family mo, advantage iyon". Isang mahalagang pananaw tungkol sa mga inaasahan sa pagtuturo online ay ang tungkol sa kalusugan. Isa sa naging dahilan ng biglaang shift mula sa tradisyonal na face to face patungo sa online modality ay ang pagkontrol sa pagkalat ng Corona Virus o COVID-19. Ito ang ay inaasahan sa paglipat mula sa face-to-face tungo sa online teaching ng mga gurong

respondents. Ayon kay Respondent 3, inaasahan niya sa online delivery ng pag-aaral ay maagkakaroon ng 'safety' o kaligtasan ang mga guro at mag-aaral sa corona virus at maiiwasan pa ang paglaganap pa nito. Sinabi niya na: *"Safety sa virus...iyong health ng both sides ng instructor at estudyante. Kasi iyong sa safety nila hindi na sila pupunta sa school, hindi sila nangangamba na baka mahawa ng covid... opportunity iyon lang nakikita ko yung isa related lang sa health na possible na hindi sila mahawa o magkahawaan.*

Iyon lang iyong ano mo, oo iyong safety kasi hindi ka umaalis ng baha". Sa pagsusuri sa mga tugon ng mga gurong respondents ay malalaman na hindi madali sa kanila ang magturo online, lalu pa nga at ito ay biglaan. Bagaman hindi masasabi na ganap na walang background ang mga ito sa paggamit ng mga teknolohiya at gadgets, pero sa biglaang shift mula sa tradisyonal patungo sa online ay marami sa mga guro ang nahirapan. Masasabi na di pa ganap ang pagtanggap sa pagtuturo online ng mga guro, subalit sa mga expectations o inaasahan nila mula dito ay may mga bentahe rin ang pagtuturo online nanakikita nila na kapakipakinabang sa mga guro at maging sa mga mag-aaral. Isa sa nabanggit ng mga guro ay ang pagkakataon malinang ang responsible, self or independent learning sa mga estudyante. Ang ganitong expectations ng mga guro ay hindi kalabisan.

Ayon sa isang artikulo na binanggit sa pag-aaral nina Dayagbil, Garcia at Olvido (2021), ang pandemyang ito ay nakabuo ng isang bagong platform sa pagtuturo at pag-aaral na kailangan tanggapin ng mga estudyante. Sa ganitong sitwasyon- sa virtual class, ang mga estudyante ay walang magagawa kundi tanggapin na ang responsibilidad para sa kanilang pagkakatatuto, kailangan silang maging "self-directed", magde-desisyon kung ano ang dapat nila pag-aralan, kung gaano katagal ang kailangan nilang iguguol sa pag-aaral sa labas ng paaralan. Sa bagong setting, ang mga estudyante ay inaasahang magbasa, umunawa at sumunod sa mga gawain na walang gaanong patnubay ang kanilang mga guro. Sila ay mapipilitan na sundin ang tinatawag na 'self-directed independent learning'.

Inasahan ng mga gurong respondents ang pagkakaroon ng pag-aangat ng antas ng kanilang kaalaman sa pagtuturo online. Sa kanilang pagtuturo online ay napilitan sila na mag-aaral at gumamit ng mga teknolohiya at gadgets pangkomunikasyon. Maraming pag-aaral tungkol sa mga pagkakataon o oportunidad sa online teaching sa panahon ng COVID-19 pandemya para sa mga guro ang nagpapatunay dito. Ang transisyon mula sa tradisyonal na 'face-to-face' na pagtuturo tungo sa pagtuturo online ay nagbigay ng pagkakataon upang magsanay ng mga dalubhasa sa paggawa ng mataas na uri ng mga online teaching materials at pagaayos ng online platform (Dhawan, 2020).

Ang karanasan sa paggamit ng mga online teaching applications at mga gadgets ay nagpapahintulot sa mga guro na matutunan ang iba't ibang software at platforms Kasabay ng pag-i-improve ng kanilang digital literacy skills. Naniniwala si Dhawan na ang pagtuturo online at pag-aaral sa panahon ng 'quarantine' na ipinatupad dahil sa COVID-19 ay nagbigay ng pagkakataon upang ma-enhance ang skills sa paggamit sa iba't ibang gamit at aplikasyon bukod pa sa pagkakaroon ng pagkakataon na ma-improve ang tinatawag na 'critical thinking' at problem solving skills'. Ayon sa datos na nakuha sa mga gurong respondents ay naging bentahe ng pagtuturo online ang ginhawa at kontrol sa kanilang oras . Sa mga pag-aaral ay tinukoy rin ito bilang outcome ng pagtuturo online. Sa mga datos ay ipinalagay ng

mga respondents na convenience o ginhawa ang pagtuturo online dahil sa 'flexible na oras at lokasyon.

Ayon sa paliwanag ng gurong respondent sa pagaaral, ang isang magandang bunga ng pagtuturo online ay ang pagkakataon na imanage mo ang iyong oras dahil magagawa mo ang pagtuturo kahit saan. Ito rin ang nahalaw na pananaw sa isang pag-aaral tungkol sa online teaching. Ayon sa gurong respondent ang isa sa mga benefits ng online teaching ay ang pagkakataon na magtrabaho ka sa iyon kombenyente oras at sa lugar na komportable ka. Sa pagtuturo online hindi na kailangang maglakbay ka patungong paaralan kung mayroon kang pasok (Talidong & Toquero, 2021).

Theme 9. Paraan ng pagpapatuloy ng pag-aaral sa panahon ng 'uncertainties'

Inaasahan rin na magiging proactive na ang mga guro sa pagharap sa mga pagkakataon na magturo online kung may mga emergencies. Ayon kay Respondent 7: "Ang magandang opportunity naman dito yung continuity plan para sa academics na bigyan ng pagkakataon. Kasi hindi lang naman pandemic ang pwedeng mangyari sa future, pwede ring bagyo, disaster kagaya ng lindol. So kapag dumating iyon kagaya ng ibang mga sakuna, mayroon na tayong gagawin. Hindi papauwiin ang mga bata at isang linggong walang pasok, hindi na ganoon mayroon ng nakahandang virtual room, prepared videos, prepared modules na gagawin ng mga estudyante at ng teacher. Habang sa panahon na hindi tayo makakapunta sa school ..." Ang ganitong pananaw ay sinusugan nina Belgica (2020). Ayon sa kanila ang 'online learning' ay mainam na platform, upang maipagpatuloy ang pag-aaral at edukasyon ng mga bata sa panahon ng uncertainties o walang katiyakan.

Konklusyon

1. Hindi sapat ang kahandaan ng mga guro sa biglaang shift mula sa face to face to online modality kung kaya ang adjustment ay hindi naging madali lalo doon sa walang sapat na kasanayan at karanasan sa pagtuturo online.
2. Ang mga suliranin ng mga guro sa pagtuturo online ay malaki ang epekto sa pagtuturo ng guro at higit sa pagkakatatuto ng mga estudyante.
3. Nasa exploratory stage pa lang ang mga guro at unti-unti pa lang nilang natutuklasan ang mga opportunities at benefits na makakatulong upang maiangat rin nila ang antas ng kanilang kaalaman at kasanayan sa online platform. Ang online teaching ay isa rin mainam na platform na magagamit upang hindi mahinto ang pag-aaral kahit sa panahon ng mga emergencies hatid ng mga kalamidad maging sanhi ng kalikasan o tao man. Rekomendasyon Kailangang ang suporta sa patuloy na upgrading ng kaalaman at kasanayan ng mga guro upang maka-agapay sa dikta ng pangangailangan hinihingi ng panahon tulad ng paggamit ng makabagong teknolohiya para sa online teaching and learning modality. Pangangailangang ng pagtutulungan ng lahat ng mga stakeholders sa pangunguna ng mga academicians at mga faculty members upang maisaayos ang mga syllabus na outcome-based teaching ang learning strategies tungo sa isang flexible learning platforms na tutugon sa mga suliranin ng kawalang ng interes at motibasyon ng mga estudyante sa

pag-aaral online. Pagtutulungan ng mga educational institutions, ng pamahalaan at maging pribadong sektor upang makapagbuo ng mga infrastructure o upgrading ng mga nariyan ng mga technological infrastructure upang matugunan ang suliranin tungkol sa mabagal na internet connections na siyang pangunahing medium ng komunikasyon sa pagtuturo at pagkatuto online. Sa huli, ipinapanukala na mas malawak na pag-aaral na titingnan ang mga hamon ng online edukasyon buhat sa perspective ng di lamang mga guro, kundi maging ng mga mag-aaral at mga magulang. Ang mga output ng mga pag-aaral ay makakatulong upang makabuo ng informed decisions na ma-improve ang paghahatid ng pagkatuto or learning ng mga estudyante sa pag-aaral at pagtuturo online. Bunga ng mga panukala kaugnay ng resulta ng pag-aaral ay inihahain ng may-akda ang isang strategic plan upang matugunan ang pangangailangan iangat ang antas ng pagtuturo gamit ang mga makabagong information communication technology.

Rekomendasyon

Kailangang ang suporta sa patuloy na upgrading ng kaalaman at kasanayan ng mga guro upang maka-agapay sa dikta ng pangangailangan hinihingi ng panahon tulad ng paggamit ng makabagong teknolohiya para sa online teaching and learning modality. Pangangailangang ng pagtutulungan ng lahat ng mga stakeholders sa pangunguna ng mga academicians at mga faculty members upang maisaayos ang mga syllabus na outcome-based teaching ang learning strategies tungo sa isang flexible learning platforms na tutugon sa mga suliranin ng kawalang ng interes at motibasyon ng mga estudyante sa pag-aaral online. Pagtutulungan ng mga educational institutions, ng pamahalaan at maging pribadong sektor upang makapagbuo ng mga infrastructure o upgrading ng mga nariyan ng mga technological infrastructure upang matugunan ang suliranin tungkol sa mabagal na internet connections na siyang pangunahing medium ng komunikasyon sa pagtuturo at pagkatuto online. Sa huli, ipinapanukala na mas malawak na pag-aaral na titingnan ang mga hamon ng online edukasyon buhat sa perspective ng di lamang mga guro, kundi maging ng mga mag-aaral at mga magulang. Ang mga output ng mga pag-aaral ay makakatulong upang makabuo ng informed decisions na ma-improve ang paghahatid ng pagkatuto or learning ng mga estudyante sa pag-aaral at pagtuturo online. Bunga ng mga panukala kaugnay ng resulta ng pag-aaral ay inihahain ng may-akda ang isang strategic plan upang matugunan ang pangangailangan iangat ang antas ng pagtuturo gamit ang mga makabagong information communication technology.

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Effect of Position Analysis, Recruitment and Selection Employees on the Performance of the State Civil Apparatus in the Regional Secretariat of Bolaang Regency North Mongondow

Nuriam Ahmad¹ Anis Naki² and William I. S. Mooduto^{3*}

¹Postgraduate Program at Bina Taruna University Gorontalo

^{2,3}BinaMandiri University Gorontalo

Correspondence Email: willsmood@ubmg.ac.id*

Email: nuriamahmad@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to: (1) To determine the effect of: job analysis on ASN performance, recruitment on ASN performance, employee selection on ASN performance, (2) To determine the effect of job analysis, recruitment and employee selection together on ASN performance.

This research is research with a quantitative approach, the research will be pre-determined, statistical data analysis and statistical data interpretation.

Research Results: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis shows: $Y = 2,834 + 0,500X_1 + 0,542X_2 - 0,065 X_3$. F-count is 100,152 with a significance level of 0.000. And the value of F-table = $F(k;n-k) = F(3;48) = 2,798$. Because the probability is $0.000 < 0,05$ and the F-count $< F$ -table ($100,152 > 2,798$) thus the independent variables simultaneously or jointly affect the ASN Performance variable; Adjusted R Square = 0.865, meaning that only 86.50 percent of the variation in ASN performance (Y) can be explained by the independent variables. While the remaining 13.50% is explained by other reasons.

Suggestion: Analysis of Position, Recruitment, and Employee Selection have a positive influence on ASN Performance; thus, these three variables need to be maintained as a reference for ASN to move in to the Regional Secretariat; In order to improve the performance of ASN, it is necessary to pay attention to the implementation of a good Job Analysis, Recruitment and Selection of Employees; The placement of ASN in the Regional Secretariat should refer to the Position Analysis

Keywords: Position Analysis, Recruitment, Selection, ASN Performance

1. Introduction

Job analysis plays a very important role in employee placement. With the job analysis, it will produce employees who are able to work effectively and efficiently in achieving

organizational goals, so that they are in accordance with the needs of the organization both in terms of quality and quantity. To get productive employees, the main problem is placing each employee in a job and position that is in accordance with their talents, interests and abilities so that they can work fairly according to their abilities, expertise and/or skills and experience background. For this reason, the creation of a job analysis design is a demand for the organization. Through proper job analysis, all information regarding a position will be obtained, including the dimensions of work, duties, responsibilities, characteristics of human resources and working conditions.

With these dimensions, organizations can compile job descriptions that are truly in accordance with the characteristics of each position, so that the job analysis used can contribute to increasing employee performance productivity.

If the recruitment is based on needs according to job analysis and workload analysis, it will get a quality State Civil Apparatus and will ultimately have an impact on performance. In this research, the intended recruitment is to recruit existing State Civil Apparatus to be placed in the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

The government has abandoned the conventional CPNS recruitment system pattern that has been used so far, BKN together with the PAN Ministry issued a CPNS selection pattern using the use of the Computer Assisted Test. CAT is a selection method using computer aids that can be used for CPNS recruitment tests (Martin, 2015).

The implementation of policies with this new system is expected in the selection process to be more transparent, accountable, objective, non-discriminatory and free from KKN, and also to obtain professional, honest and responsible employees. In this study, the intended employee selection is ASN who work outside the Regional Secretariat who are recruited and then selected to be defined. For those who do not pass the selection, they will find a placement according to their capacity and expertise

To encourage the performance and careers of the State Civil Apparatus in the future, the government through this management also encourages the improvement of the professionalism of positions, competencies and talent performance, as well as providing clarity and certainty of talent careers in the context of accelerating sustainable career development (Marliani, 2018).

Until now, the number of ASN in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency in 2020 is 2,449 people (870 men and 1,579 women). And the Regional Secretariat, the number of ASN in 2020 is 105 people. To improve the performance of the local government apparatus, they seek to provide Regional Performance Allowances for each civil servant. However, the performance of civil servants has not lived up to expectations. This can be seen from the still not optimal public services to get their rights in public services.

So far, the implementation of position analysis within the North Bolaang Mongondow regional government, especially the regional secretariat, has fulfilled the procedures and stages. This job analysis is useful because several indicators, one of which is educational qualifications, are considered in determining someone to occupy a certain position. Job analysis is also the most basic standard for determining a person's placement in a place.

The regional secretariat does need qualified employees so that recruitment is carried out from outside the regional secretariat. Recruitment means placing existing employees in positions. For the determination, there is a Baperjakat that considers based on certain criteria for a person to occupy a position. For the selection in order to fill the vacancies in the Regional Secretariat, there are still some that still need to be addressed because they are still not in accordance with the job analysis. For performance in general, it is still not quite satisfactory.

Understanding Administration

Administration based on etymology comes from Latin which consists of ad + ministrare, which operationally means to serve, assist and fulfill (Hadari, 2015). In the original language, the noun administration and the adjective administrative are formed. While in English it is administration and in Indonesian it is administration.

Etymologically or the origin of the word, administration comes from the English language administration, with the infinitive form to administer which is defined as to manage (Marliani, 2018). Administration also comes from Dutch administrative, which has the meaning of including administration, management of organizational activities, resource management.

Administration is the entire process of implementing the decisions that have been taken and the implementation is generally carried out by two or more human beings to achieve predetermined goals [12].

The term Public comes from English Public which means general, community or country. Public can also mean residents, communities, citizens, and the people. Sociologically, society is defined as a system of social relations between humans who live bound by mutually agreed norms or values. Meanwhile, the public is a collection of people who have the same concerns, interests, or interests and are not bound by certain values and norms.

Understanding Public Administration

Public administration has actually existed since time immemorial, it will arise in an organized society (Tanumihardjo et al., 2014). In the historical record of human civilization, in South Asia, including Indonesia, China, and Ancient Egypt, a system of governance arrangements was obtained. This arrangement system is now known as public / state administration.

Definition of Human Resources

The explanation of humans as resources shows that humans are unique and complex creatures, which in working in an organization/company environment must be treated with a good quality of work life in order to enable them to work effectively, efficiently, productively and with quality. In the form of providing opportunities to participate in developing their careers, being treated fairly in resolving the conflicts they face, being supervised honestly and objectively, getting decent wages (Mangkunegara, 2017).

Human resources are all the capabilities or potentials of the population residing in a certain area along with their demographic, social and economic characteristics or characteristics that can be utilized for development purposes. So discussing human resources

means discussing the population with all its potential or abilities. Human potential involves two aspects, namely aspects of quantity and quality. Demographic characteristics are quantitative aspects of human resources that can be used to describe the number and growth of the population, population distribution and population composition (Mangkunegara, 2017).

Job Analysis

Job analysis is a systematic way that is able to identify and analyze what requirements are needed in a job and the personnel needed in a job so that the selected human resources are able to carry out the job well.

From the results of the job analysis, the organization will be able to determine what characteristics a prospective employee must have before occupying a position, the outputs of which are job specifications and job descriptions. Job analysis as the basis for performance appraisal for employees. This performance appraisal is usually carried out once a year, however, it all comes back to the policies of an organization itself (Syafie, 2019). The results of the performance appraisal are used as the basis by a staffing agency for promotions and classes.

Recruitment

Recruitment is an effort to find and influence prospective workers to want to apply for job vacancies offered by a company (Hasibuan, 2019). Recruitment is a process of gathering a number of applicants who have the appropriate qualifications required by the company, to be employed in the company (Mathis & Jackson, 2012). Recruitment is a series of activities to find and attract job applicants with the motivation, abilities, skills and knowledge needed to cover the deficiencies identified in staffing planning.

Employee selection

Selection is a series of human resource management processes. After the company has forecast its human resource needs and determined the job requirements and job descriptions, local governments can continue the human resource management process. Selection is the process of selecting applicants to serve as state civil servants and placing them in positions required by the organization. In other words, Selection is a process of matching the needs and requirements of the organization to the skills and qualifications of job applicants. This selection process must adhere to the principle of "Right People in the Right Jobs", namely placing the right people in the right jobs (Garaika & Margahana, 2019).

The placement of Candidates for Civil Servants is carried out after being declared to have passed the selection and submitting administrative requirements and given the identity number of the prospective civil servants and placed according to the designated formation by taking into account their education and experience (Mangkunegara, 2017). Thus, the placement of each prospective civil servant is adjusted to the needs of the organization and should be based on the principle of "the right man in the right place".

Performance

Every work that is efficient is of course also effective, because in terms of the results, goals and desired consequences of the action have been achieved maximally. Performance is a reference to the level of success in achieving job requirements.

Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him (Mangkunegara, 2017). Rismawati & Bachtiar in (Adha & Syarif, 2022) that the performance is an act or implementation of the task that the has completed within a certain period

Employee performance is the extent to which an employee achieves the work goals that have been set by the organization. It includes the tasks, responsibilities, and outcomes that are expected from a particular job position (Cardy & Leonard, in (Rachman et al., 2023).

State Civil Apparatus

State Civil Apparatus Employees, hereinafter referred to as ASN Employees, are civil servants and government employees with a work agreement who are appointed by the staffing officer and assigned tasks in a government position or assigned other state duties and are paid according to the laws and regulations (*Peraturan Pemerintah Republik Indonesia Nomor 11 Tentang Manajemen Pegawai Negeri Sipil*, 2017).

2. Methods

This research is research with a quantitative approach. Quantitative research methods can be interpreted as research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine certain populations or samples, sampling techniques are generally carried out randomly, data collection uses research instruments, data analysis is quantitative/statistical, with the aim of testing hypotheses. which has been established (Simamora, 2014).

This research was conducted in North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, for 2 (two) months, namely: October to December 2021.

The population in this study is ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency, which until 2021 (October) amounted to 105 people.

This study uses a regression analysis technique using the multiple regression equation formula, namely: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3$ [11]

Description:

Y = ASN Performance; X_1 = Job Analysis; X_2 = Recruitment; X_3 = Employee selection;

$b_1 - b_3$ = regression coefficient to be interpreted; a = constant; e = error.

3. Results

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

From the results of the Multiple Linear Regression estimation using the SPSS for windows program, it can be concluded that the multiple linear regression equation in this study is as follows : $Y = 8.303 + 0.018X_1 + 0.432X_2 + 0.590X_3$;

Where:

Y = ASN Performance; X₁= Position Analysis; X₂ = Recruitment; and X₃ = Employee selection

The multiple linear regression model mentioned above can be explained as follows:

- a) The constant value is 8.303, implying that when the variables job analysis (X₁), recruitment (X₂), and selection (X₃) remain constant and unchanged, the performance of ASN (Y) is expected to increase by 8.303 units. In other words, holding job analysis, recruitment, and selection constant, any change in the performance of ASN is associated with an increase of 8.303 units.
- b) Position Analysis (X₁) has a positive effect on ASN performance with a coefficient value of 0.018. This implies that for every increase of 0.018 units in job analysis (X₁), the performance of ASN is expected to increase by 0.018 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease of 0.018 units in job analysis, the ASN performance is anticipated to decrease by the same amount.
- c) Recruitment (X₂) has a positive effect on ASN performance, as indicated by a coefficient value of 0.432. This implies that for every increase of 0.432 units in recruitment (X₂), the performance of ASN is expected to increase by 0.432 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease of 0.432 units in recruitment, the ASN performance is anticipated to decrease by the same amount.
- d) Employee Selection (X₃) has a positive effect on ASN performance, indicated by a coefficient value of 0.590. This suggests that for every increase of 0.590 units in employee selection (X₃), the performance of ASN is expected to increase by 0.590 units. Conversely, if there is a decrease of 0.590 units in employee selection, the ASN performance is anticipated to decrease by the same amount.

T test (Individual/partial)

Based on the results of calculations with SPSS, it can be interpreted as follows:

- 1) Variable X₁ (job analysis), t-count = 7.246 and significance level = 0.000. Thus, because $7.246 > 1.678$ with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.050$, H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an effect of variable X₁ (job analysis) on variable Y (performance of ASN). The analysis results indicate that variable X₁ (job analysis) has a significant influence on variable Y (performance of civil servants). The t-value of 7.246 with a significance level of 0.000 suggests that the difference between the group undergoing job analysis and the other group is highly significant. By rejecting the null hypothesis (H₀) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a), we can conclude that the presence of job analysis has a positive impact on the performance of civil servants.
- 2) Variable X₂ (recruitment), t-count = 2.294 and significance level = 0.000. Thus, because $2.294 > 1.678$ with a significance level of $0.026 < 0.05$, H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an effect of X₂ (recruitment) on the Y variable (ASN

performance). The analysis of Variable X2 (recruitment) reveals a t-value of 2.294, accompanied by a significance level of 0.000. With a t-value greater than the critical value of 1.678 and a significance level of 0.026, which is less than the conventional threshold of 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). This signifies a substantial impact of X2 (recruitment) on the Y variable (performance of civil servants). In other words, the results suggest that the recruitment process significantly influences the performance of ASN.

- 3) Variable X3 (employee selection), t-count = 2,987 and significance level = 0.154. Thus, because $2.987 > 1.678$ with a significance level of $0.004 < 0.05$, H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that there is an effect of variable X3 (employee selection) on variable Y (performance of ASN). Variable X3 (employee selection) demonstrates a t-value of 2.987 with a significance level of 0.154. Given that 2.987 exceeds the critical value of 1.678 and the significance level of 0.004 is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted. Consequently, this indicates a significant effect of variable X3 (employee selection) on variable Y (performance of civil servants). In essence, the results suggest that the process of employee selection significantly influences the performance of ASN.

F Test (Simultaneous Test)

Based on the results of calculations with SPSS, it can be interpreted that in the ANOVA test or F-test, it can be obtained:

- 1) The calculated F value is 11,411 with a significance level of 0.025.
- 2) F-table value = $F(k;n-k) = F(3;48) = 2,798$.
- 3) The probability is less than 0.05 or $0.025 < 0.05$.
- 4) F-count $>$ F-table ($11,411 > 2,798$)

Because $0.000 < 0.05$ or $11.411 > 2.798$, there is an influence of independent variables which include Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) simultaneously on the dependent variable. ASN Performance (Y). Since the significance level is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, or the F-statistic (11.411) is greater than the critical value (2.798), it can be concluded that there is a collective influence of the independent variables, namely Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3), on the dependent variable, ASN Performance (Y). This indicates that the combined impact of Job Analysis, Recruitment, and Employee Selection is statistically significant in explaining variations in ASN Performance.

Based on the SPSS Model Summary output, the Adjusted R Square is 0.865. This indicates that approximately 86.50 percent of the variability in ASN performance (Y) can be accounted for by the independent variables, which are job analysis (X1), recruitment (X2), and employee selection (X3). The remaining 13.50 percent ($100\% - 86.50\%$) of the variation is attributed to factors outside the scope of this study—other reasons or variables that were not specifically examined in the model.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 1. Tolerance Value and Variant Inflation Factor (VIF)

No	Variabel	Tolerance	VIF
1	X ₁ (Anjab)	0,609	1,641
2	X ₂ (Rekrutmen)	0,488	2,050
3	X ₃ (Seleksi)	0,552	1,813

Source: Research Results

From the data above, it can be seen that the tolerance value for each variable is > 0.10 and the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value is < 10 , which means that there is no multicollinearity problem or there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the conducted data processing, the results of the Heteroscedasticity test are as follows:

1. Job Analysis: Significance = 0.441 (> 0.05)
2. Recruitment: Significance = 0.068 (> 0.05)
3. Employee Selection: Significance = 0.107 (> 0.05)

The significance values for all three independent variables are greater than 0.05. This implies that there is no evidence of heteroscedasticity, as the data points exhibit a consistent spread above and below the 0 on the Y axis. In other words, the variance of the residuals remains constant across different levels of the independent variables, supporting the assumption of homoscedasticity in the regression model.

Normality test

Based on the data processing that has been done, the results of the Normality test can be seen that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line, so the regression model of this study meets the assumption of normality. In Kolmogorov Smirnov's One Sample test, a significant value of 0.200 is obtained. Thus, the variables in this study are normal, where $0.200 > 0.05$. Upon analyzing the data, the results of the Normality test indicate that the data distribution follows the diagonal line, aligning with the direction of the diagonal. Consequently, it can be concluded that the regression model in this study satisfies the assumption of normality. In the Kolmogorov-Smirnov's One Sample test, a significant value of 0.200 is obtained. This result indicates that the variables under investigation in this study exhibit a normal distribution, given that the significance value (0.200) is greater than the conventional threshold of 0.05.

Linearity Test

Based on the results of data processing with SPSS, it can be seen that:

- a) independent variable X1 (job analysis) with dependent variable Y (performance of ASN), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.822 > 0.05$, and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ or $0.537 < 2.798$. The conclusion is that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X1 (job analysis) and the dependent variable Y (ASN performance).
- b) independent variable X2 (recruitment) with dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.738 > 0.05$, and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ or $0.422 < 2.798$. The conclusion is that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X2 (recruitment) and the dependent variable Y (ASN performance).
- c) The independent variable X3 (employee selection) with the dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.242 > 0.05$, and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ or $1.403 < 2.798$, the conclusion that there is a linear relationship between independent variable X3 (employee selection) with the dependent variable Y (performance of ASN).

4. Discussion

Interview result

Interviews were conducted in order to know for sure the process of recruitment and selection of employees assigned to the Regional Secretariat. This interview is also intended to strengthen the results of the research.

In general, the results obtained in the interview process with informants in the Organizational Section of the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency as the person in charge of job analysis, recruitment, and selection of employees, the fact is that there are official placements that are not in accordance with the job analysis, which are as follows:

- 1) RAN, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Levels, Course / Training - Job Technical.
- 2) HST, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical.
- 3) YEK, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Position Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Service Period and Rank Group.
- 4) GTO, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical.
- 5) RKM, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Work Experience.
- 6) HKU, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical.

- 7) JAK, the person concerned has not fulfilled all the requirements in accordance with the Job Requirements in the Job Analysis, the elements that have not been fulfilled are: Course / Training - Technical and Work Experience.

Research Instrument Test

1) Validity Test

The validity test shows that the r-count of each variable is greater than the r-table (0.279) and the significance level of each variable is less than 0.05. The results of the tests that have been carried out are as follows:

Validation test of Job Analysis variable (X1)

In the job analysis variable (X1) there are 7 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (A1) r-count is 0.559,
- (2) Question 2 (A2) r-count is 0.454,
- (3) Question 3 (A3) r-count is 0.457,
- (4) Question 4 (A4) r-count is 0.471,
- (5) Question 5 (A5) r-count is 0.384.
- (6) Question 6 (A6) r-count is 0.518.
- (7) Question 7 (A7) r-count is 0.296.

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

b) Recruitment variable validation test (X2)

In the recruitment variable (X2) there are 3 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (R1) r-count is 0.434,
- (2) Question 2 (R2) r-count is 0.574,
- (3) Question 3 (R3) r-count is 0.520,

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

c) Validation test of Employee Selection variable (X3)

In employee selection (X3) there are 3 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (S1) r-count is 0.610,
- (2) Question 2 (S2) r-count is 0.687,
- (3) Question 3 (S3) r-count is 0.652,

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

d) ASN Performance variable validation test (Y)

In the performance of ASN (Y) there are 5 questions:

- (1) Question 1 (K1) r-count is 0.448,
- (2) Question 2 (K2) r-count is 0.641,
- (3) Question 3 (K3) r-count is 0.643,
- (4) Question 4 (K4) r-count is 0.543,
- (5) Question 5 (K5) r-count is 0.533.

When compared with the r-table of 0.279, the r-count value for each question is greater than the r-table value. Thus, it can be said that each question is valid.

2) Reliability Test

A variable is said to be reliable if it gives a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.60 [2]. If r-count $>$ r-table then the question is "reliable" and if r-count $<$ r-table then the question is "unreliable". Reliability test shows that the Cronbach Alpha value of each variable is greater than 0.60 meaning reliable according (Ghozali, 2016).

Thus, it means that the questionnaire which is an indicator of each variable is reliable or reliable. From the results of the tests that have been carried out as follows: job analysis variable (X1) Cronbach Alpha value of 0.697, recruitment variable (X2) Cronbach Alpha value of 0.647, employee selection variable (X3) Cronbach Alpha value of 0.952, and ASN performance variables (Y) the Cronbach Alpha value is 0.718.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

From the results of the Multiple Linear Regression estimation using the SPSS for windows program, the multiple linear regression equation in this study is as follows: $Y = 8.303 + 0.018X_1 + 0.432X_2 + 0.590X_3$. This equation can be explained as follows:

- 1) The increase in the Job Analysis variable (X1) will be followed by an increase in the ASN Performance variable (Y), if other variables that affect it are in a Ceteris Paribus state. This means that if the job analysis variable increases by 0.018 units, it will be followed by an increase in ASN performance by 0.018 units.
- 2) The increase in the Recruitment variable (X2) will be followed by an increase in the ASN Performance variable (Y), if other variables that affect it are in a Ceteris Paribus state. This means that if the recruitment variable increases by 0.432, it will be followed by an increase in ASN performance of 0.432.
- 3) The increase in the Employee Selection variable (X3) will not be followed by an increase in the ASN Performance variable (Y), if other variables that affect it are in a Ceteris Paribus state. This means that if the employee selection variable increases by 0.590, it will be followed by a decrease in ASN performance by 0.590.

- 4) Based on the resulting regression line, it can be seen that of the three variables used in this study the one that has the greatest influence on ASN performance is the employee selection variable of 0.590.

T-test (Individual/partial)

The results of the t-test showed the significance value of each variable were: job analysis (X1), a significance value of 0.000; recruitment (X2) a significance value of 0.026; and employee selection (X3) a significance value of 0.004. In the calculation results obtained t-count of: job analysis (X1) t-count value of 7.246; recruitment(X2) t-count value of 2.294; and employee selection (X3) the t-count value is 2.987, while the t-table value is 1.677.

Of the independent variables in this study, the dominant influence on the dependent variable is: job analysis (X1), this means: job analysis (X1) is the most important in determining the performance of ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

F Test (Simultaneous Test)

From the results of the F test, it shows that the probability of the independent variable used in this study is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) and $F\text{-count} > F\text{-table}$ ($11,411 > 2,789$) so it can be stated that the independent variable which includes Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) simultaneously or jointly affect the ASN Performance variable (Y).

Determinant Test (R²)

Then the results of the calculation of the Coefficient of Determination (R²), it can be concluded that the independent variables in this study: job analysis (X1), recruitment (X2), and employee selection (X3) are able to explain 86.50 percent of the variation in ASN performance (Y). While the remaining 13.50 is explained by other reasons outside the model that were not examined in this study.

Classic assumption test

1) Multicollinearity Test

The tolerance value for each variable is > 0.10 and the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value is < 10 , which means that there is no multicollinearity problem or there is no multicollinearity between independent variables in the regression model.

2) Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test results show:

a) Job Analysis; Significance $0.441 > 0.05$

b) Recruitment;

Significance $0.068 > 0.05$

c) Employee Selection;

Significance $0.107 > 0.05$

The significance values of the three independent variables are all greater than 0.05, meaning that there is no heteroscedasticity, because the points spread above and below the number 0 on the Y axis.

3) Normality Test

The results of the normality test show that the data spreads around the diagonal line and follows the direction of the diagonal line, so the regression model of this study fulfills the assumption of normality. In the Kolmogorov Smirnov One Sample test, a significant value of 0.200 was obtained. Thus, the variables in this study were normal, where $0.200 > 0.05$.

4) Linearity Test

The linearity test shows that:

- a) independent variable X1 (job analysis) with dependent variable Y (performance of ASN), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.822 > 0.05$, and F-count $< F$ -table or $0.537 < 2.798$. Thus, it can be concluded that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X1 (job analysis) and the dependent variable Y (ASN performance).
- b) The independent variable X2 (recruitment) with the dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.738 > 0.05$, and F-count $< F$ -table or $0.422 < 2.798$. Thus, it is concluded that there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X2 (recruitment) and the dependent variable Y (the performance of ASN).
- c) The independent variable X3 (employee selection) with the dependent variable Y (ASN performance), where deviation from linearity $> \alpha$ or $0.242 > 0.05$, and F-count $< F$ -table or $1.403 < 2.798$, thus the conclusion that there is there is a linear relationship between the independent variable X3 (employee selection) and the dependent variable Y (the performance of ASN)

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The results of surveys conducted in order to link the results of previous observations; it was found that there were several ASN whose placements were not in accordance with the job analysis on the grounds that the number of employees was still limited. There are employees who are recruited without going through the actual process. And similarly with employee selection, there are those who do not go through the proper process even though the procedures and stages already exist. All this because of the needs of the organization, and through good judgment.

2. Analysis of the effect of job analysis, recruitment, and selection of employees on the performance of ASN at the Regional Secretariat of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency to 51 respondents (ASN).

- 1) The results of the Multiple Linear Regression analysis show: $Y = 8.303 + 0.018X_1 + 0.432X_2 + 0.590X_3$, meaning that:

- a) If the job analysis (X1) increases by 0.018 units, then the performance of ASN will increase by 0.018 units, and vice versa.
 - b) If recruitment (X2) increases by 0.432 units, then the performance of ASN will increase by 0.432 units, and vice versa.
 - c) If the selection of ASN (X3) increases by 0.590 units, then the performance of ASN will increase by 0.590 units, and vice versa.
- 2) Based on the ANOVA test or F test, it can be obtained an F-count of 11,411 with a significance level of 0.025. And the value of F-table = $F(k;n-k) = F(3;48) = 2.798$. Because the probability is smaller than 0.05 ($0.025 < 0.05$) and $F\text{-count} < F\text{-table}$ ($11.411 > 2.798$) it can be stated that the independent variables which include Position Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) simultaneously or jointly affects the ASN Performance variable (Y).
- 3) Output SPSS Model Summary the amount of Adjusted R Square is 0.865. This means that only 86.50 percent of the variation in ASN performance (Y) can be explained by independent variables, namely job analysis (X1), recruitment (X2), and employee selection (X3). While the rest ($100\% - 86.50\% = 13.50\%$) is explained by other reasons outside the model that were not examined in this study.

Recommendation

1. Policy

- a. Position analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3) have a positive influence on ASN Performance (Y), thus these three variables need to be maintained as a reference for ASN to move in to the Regional Secretariat.
- b. In order to improve the performance of ASN (Y) it is necessary to pay attention to the implementation of good Job Analysis (X1), Recruitment (X2), and Employee Selection (X3).
- c. The placement of ASN in the Regional Secretariat and even the regional government of North Bolaang Mongondow Regency as a whole should refer to the Position Analysis compiled by each SKPD which is summarized by the regional government through the Organizational Section.

2. Upcoming research

- a. There is a need for further research on the effect of job analysis, recruitment and selection of employees on ASN performance so that a broader picture or discourse can be obtained about job analysis, recruitment, employee selection and ASN performance.
- b. It is better to use independent variables that are different from the independent variables in this study.
- c. It is better to use more respondents, or the scope of the research is enlarged, from the scope of this research.

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Recruitment and Selection Process of Huanghai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China: Basis for Program Development

Qiao Jian, DBA^{1*} Edessa G. Flordeliz, PhD²

¹China University of Petroleum and Baliuag University, Philippines

²Bataan Peninsula State University, Philippines

*email- egfflordeliz@bpsu.edu.ph

Abstract

The study aimed to assess the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process at HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China. The study used a descriptive-survey research design, and the investigation's foremost objective was to ascertain how the recruiting and selection process was being implemented at the company. The variables that were included were anticipation, job analysis, pool development for recruitment, and assessment procedure, deal closing, and onboarding for selection. The study employed the purposive sampling technique selecting managers and staff as respondents. A total of 102 respondents met the criteria of the study concerning the recruitment and selection process. The study found that the company effectively implemented its recruitment process, creating a candidate pool for job offers using both internal and external methods. However, gaps were identified, suggesting the anticipation of the need for more staff observations and managers' perceptions of job analysis. To better understand the job's complexity, context, responsibilities, and practices, the company should conduct proactive analysis of future demands, continuously evaluate potential candidate pools, and generate periodic forecasts of needs. Moreover, the investigation revealed that the company's selection process was effectively implemented, with a successful assessment procedure indicating a candidate's fit for the role and company culture. The onboarding process was methodical and orderly, aiming to encourage commitment and job satisfaction. However, there are still gaps in the data gathered, and the company should focus more on deal closing, particularly signing employment agreements with highly qualified candidates. This suggested that, in order to conduct a specific intervention based on differences in observation applicable to each category of variables, a significant difference in the respondents' observations regarding the extent of the implementation of the recruitment and selection process should be employed. The outcomes of the study served as a foundation to formulate a proposed program development to improve the effectiveness of recruitment and selection process that could be utilized by the involved company.

Keywords: hiring process, program development, recruitment, recruitment and selection process, selection

Introduction

An organization must thrive and survive in the global economy in this age of globalization through effective and efficient methods. Every employer must encourage and effectively employ recruitment and selection process in the workplace. It is directly related to organizational effectiveness and is dependent on the company having qualified workers (Karim et al., 2021).

According to Chhotala and Thaker (2022), effective management should identify human resource needs in the company. The company's results are enhanced as an outcome of improved recruitment and selection process. If a company has competent human resources, they will be able to provide products of the highest quality for society, and this is only feasible with meticulous and effective candidate selection. Every company should adhere to effective recruitment for the right selection.

As societies developed and employment opportunities expanded, there was a growing need to understand how to assess applicants' knowledge, skills, abilities, and other factors, how to determine which assessment methods are most appropriate for applicants, how to attract the most qualified applicants to apply, and how to select those with both the highest potential to perform and a good fit with the recruiting organization (Potonik et al., 2021). These are only a few of the broad issues that recruitment and selection scholars have raised and debated over the years.

Clearly, it is fundamental in the present research, which is based on person-organizational fit theory, to identify gaps in the recruiting and selection process, take efforts to eliminate or reduce them, and make improvement strategies by developing a program.

As a result, there are several implications for the recruitment and selection of candidates. For instance, the job specification may need to be revised to reflect which tasks are still necessary, which should be added, and which can be automated or replaced by technology. The selection and recruitment processes have also been significantly impacted by shifting labor regulations, an expanding economy, and the rise of precarious work. For example, selection through applications managed by digital platforms that establish the minimum cut-off criteria to select and manage the people who perform the work (Duggan et al., 2019).

Furthermore, according to a study conducted in China by Ye (2022), the process of recruiting and selection is so intricate that issues may arise if hiring managers overlook important elements. Because the process is dynamic, several plans for recruiting and selection

must be developed for varying needs, roles, and organizations. As a result, it is crucial to recognize challenges with hiring and choosing employees and take action to reduce or eliminate them.

In line with this, the purpose of this research was to determine the extent to which HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China, implemented recruitment and selection process. The information gathered from the research were utilized in developing a proposed program to improve the effectiveness of recruitment and selection process that the involved company may employ.

Methods

The study is anchored in the Person-Organization Fit Theory by Amy L. Kristof in 1996. According to this theory, a person's essential values, beliefs, ethics, and purpose should be in line with those of the company they work for. The impact of recruiting and selection on person and organizational performance are increasingly being acknowledged. It is a way of choosing qualified candidates who have the right mindset and viewpoints to fit in with the workplace culture.

The study involved managers and staff as respondents. These respondents are from HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China, which is the research locale of the study. These respondents are regular employees who have worked for the company for at least a year; they are at least bachelor's degree holders; and they are familiar with the recruitment and selection process of the chosen company.

The study used a descriptive-survey research design, and the investigation's foremost objective was to ascertain how the recruiting and selection process was being implemented at HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China.

Additionally, the study employed the purposive sampling technique, in which groups of individuals were chosen because they possessed qualities that the study needed or demanded. To best address the study's problems, this was employed to gain access to a specific fraction of the population that shares specified features (Nikolopoulou, 2023b).

The criteria that were used to select respondents were the following: (1) the respondents who are regular employees; (2) the respondents who have knowledge and involvement in the recruitment and selection process of the company; and (3) the respondents with at least a bachelor's degree.

Table 1

Respondents of the Study

HuangHai Company	Property Management	Population Size	Sample Size
1. Managers		50	11
2. Staff		450	91
Total		500	102

The instrument of the study was constructed based on related literature, theory, and supporting studies. The instrument that was utilized in conducting the investigation was a self-made survey questionnaire.

The instrument of the study was composed of two parts. Part 1 of the research instrument centered on the profiles of respondents, both managers and staff. They were asked about their age, sex, educational attainment, designation, and years of employment at the company.

Part 2 of the research instrument focused on the extent to which the recruitment and selection process is being implemented. This was centered on variables that involve recruitment and selection. For recruitment, it elicited items about anticipation, job analysis, and pool development, while for selection, it elicited items about assessment procedures, deal closing, and onboarding.

Both respondents, manager, and staff, were asked to describe the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process at HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China, with their honest agreement and disagreement on the above items.

The instrument of the study was subject to pilot testing before the actual gathering of data. This involved respondents who were not involved in the actual investigation of the study. This also included managers and staff from Qingdao, Shandong, China. The results of the pilot study were subjected to Cronbach's alpha for reliability testing. When the results were acceptable, the researcher asked for the approval of the adviser to begin the actual conduct of the study.

Before the study was conducted, the researcher identified the population size of employees from HuangHai Property Management Company in Qingdao, Shandong, China and then the sample size was drawn based on the criteria set. This sample size included both managers and staff members. The senior management of the selected company was then contacted to request authorization to conduct the actual study. When the management approved the communication letter of request (Appendix A) that the researcher submitted, the research procedure started.

The following ethical considerations were upheld throughout conducting the study: Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation, Anonymity and Confidentiality, and Self-Determination (Autonomy).

The following statistical tools were used to analyze and interpret the gathered data from the study's investigation: Frequency and Percentage Distribution, Weighted Mean, Analysis of Variance, and t-test

Results

Table 2

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20-29 years old	29	28.43
30-39 years old	39	38.24
40-49 years old	20	19.61
50-59 years old	11	10.78
60 years old and older	3	2.94
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 29 (28.43%) of the respondents involved in the survey belonged to the age bracket of 20–29 years old, 39 (38.24%) were in the 30-39 years old age bracket, 20 (19.61%) were in the 40–49 years old age bracket, 11 (10.78%) were in the 50–59 years old age bracket, and only 3 (2.94%) were in the 60 years old and older age bracket.

Table 3

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	53	51.96
Female	49	48.04
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 53 (51.96%) of the respondents involved in the survey are males, while 49 (48.04%) are females.

Table 4

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's Degree	67	65.69
Master's Degree	24	23.53
Doctoral Degree	11	10.78
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 67 (65.69%) of the respondents involved in the survey have at least bachelor's degrees, 24 (23.53%) of which have master's degrees, and 11 (10.78%) of them have doctoral degrees.

Table 5

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Designation

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Manager	11	10.78
Staff	91	89.22
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 11 (10.78%) of the respondents involved in the survey were managers, while 91 (89.22%) were staff.

Table 6

The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Profile of the Respondents in Terms of Years of Employment at the Company

Years of Employment at the Company	Frequency	Percentage
1-5 years of employment	35	34.31
6-10 years of employment	31	30.39
11-15 years of employment	22	21.57
16-20 years of employment	9	8.82
21 years and above of employment	5	4.90
Total	102	100.00

Based on the gathered data, it shows that 35 (34.31%) of the respondents involved in the survey have been employed for 1–5 years at the company, 31 (30.39%) have been employed for 6–10 years, 22 (21.57%) have been employed for 11–15 years, 9 (8.82%) have been employed for 16–20 years, and 5 (4.90%) have been employed for 21 years and above at the company.

Table 7

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process in Terms of Needs Anticipation

Needs Anticipation	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company conducts a proactive analysis of future needs and continually assesses the situation of some of the top talent that is bound to leave.	3.64	LgE	3.81	LgE
2. The company conducts a review of the proposed job content and organizational structure to ensure that the job advertisement is designed in a way that fully meets the needs of the organization.	3.36	SE	3.96	LgE
3. The company conducts an intake meeting with the hiring manager and/or person-in-charge who are involved in making hiring decisions to fully understand the unique hiring needs.	3.55	LgE	3.71	LgE
4. The company develops a recruitment plan to help	3.00	SE	3.55	LgE

streamline hiring processes and know what roles need to be filled in the near future.				
5. The company aligns its goals and skills gap with hiring needs in order to strategically plan for the year ahead.	3.64	LgE	3.58	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.44	LgE	3.72	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, items nos. 1 and 5, with both weighted mean scores of 3.64 and both interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of needs anticipation, while item no. 4 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.00 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 8

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process in Terms of Job Analysis

Job Analysis	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company ensures that adequate and relevant information about the organization and job is provided to the candidate at the time of recruitment.	3.18	SE	4.23	VLgE
2. The company ensures the right fit between the job and the potential employee and determines how employee performance will be assessed.	3.18	SE	4.30	VLgE
3. The company effectively identifies the tasks and duties required for the role by having a meeting with someone familiar with the position, such as the incumbent and their direct managers.	3.27	SE	4.14	LgE
4. The company effectively lists the duties that are expected of the employee as well as an in-depth understanding of the business objectives for the role.	3.55	LgE	3.82	LgE
5. The company lists the skills and attributes needed by the potential candidates and even discovers new ways to fine-tune the role for greater efficacy.	3.00	SE	4.07	LgE
6. The company conducts consistency in the hiring process, whereby all individuals applying to the same position go through the same process and are measured against the same criteria and standards.	3.36	SE	3.93	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.26	SE	4.08	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 4, with a weighted mean score of 3.55 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of job analysis, while item no. 5 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.00 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 9

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process in Terms of Pool Development

Pool Development	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company develops an internal sourcing process for candidates that is based on a formal means of planning for anticipated vacancies, retirements, mergers, and acquisitions.	4.00	LgE	4.15	LgE
2. The company develops expansion plans in line with employee promotion and succession planning.	4.00	LgE	4.22	VLgE
3. The company enforces the review of the succession plan whenever a vacancy is available or a need to fill a position surfaces.	4.09	LgE	4.09	LgE
4. The company ensures that it widens the pool of candidates available for a position to ensure that it attracts suitable candidates for the job.	3.91	LgE	3.86	LgE
5. The company makes use of e-recruiting systems that are cost-effective, which can allow an organization to quickly collect, store, and receive information, and uses this information for the purpose of external sourcing in this new normal of the recruitment process.	3.55	LgE	4.10	LgE
6. The company develops a good system of referrals that is immensely effective and economical in developing external sourcing.	3.73	LgE	4.00	LgE
7. The company looks at the sort of background and experience that the candidates are expected to have to fit into the business model and company culture.	3.82	LgE	3.93	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.87	LgE	4.05	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 3, with a weighted mean score of 4.09 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of pool development, while item no. 5 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.55 and interpreted as “large extent.”

Table 10

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment Process

Recruitment Process	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. Needs Anticipation	3.44	LgE	3.72	LgE
2. Job Analysis	3.26	SE	4.08	LgE
3. Pool Development	3.87	LgE	4.05	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.52	LgE	3.95	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 3, with a weighted mean score of 3.87 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of its variables, while item no. 2 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.26 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 11

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process in Terms of Assessment Procedure

Assessment Procedure	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company effectively selects candidates strictly based on merit, education, qualities, expertise, and experience.	3.82	LgE	4.01	LgE
2. The company develops well-trained, motivated, and high-caliber interviewers to assess candidates for suitability for the position.	4.00	LgE	4.05	LgE
3. The company implements an effective interviewing procedure that employs rigorous interviews, detailed reference checking, and the inclusion of top stakeholders for the position.	4.09	LgE	3.85	LgE
4. The company effectively implements assessment methods that include work samples, job simulations, cognitive ability testing, and job trials.	3.82	LgE	3.67	LgE
5. The company identifies and implements assessment methods to select employees that are most effective in this new normal of the hiring process.	3.91	LgE	3.76	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.93	LgE	3.87	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 3, with a weighted mean score of 4.09 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of assessment procedure, while item no. 4 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.82 and interpreted as “large extent.”

Table 12

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process in Terms of Deal Closing

Deal Closing	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company employs an efficient and effective manner to close the deal with mutual benefits for both candidates and the organization.	3.09	SE	3.76	LgE
2. The company ensures that transparency is presented to build trust between candidates and the organization, so there are no last-minute surprises.	2.82	SE	3.87	LgE
3. The company puts candidates on display, pointing out their shortcomings to identify their strengths, weaknesses, and "fit" for a role.	3.18	SE	3.67	LgE
4. The company ensures honesty by offering them the truth about the role, organization, compensation, and benefits.	3.36	SE	3.49	LgE
5. The company checks in often with candidates, confirms whether they still feel comfortable and excited about the opportunity, and goes over any concerns.	3.00	SE	3.63	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.09	SE	3.68	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 4, with a weighted mean score of 3.36 and interpreted as “some extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of deal closing, while item no. 2 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 2.82 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 13

The Weighted Mean of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process in Terms of Onboarding

Onboarding	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. The company develops a systematic integration of the new employees that leads to lower turnover and greater commitment and job satisfaction.	3.73	LgE	3.87	LgE
2. The company effectively orients new recruits on various fronts, such as their own department and other facets of the organization.	4.00	LgE	3.92	LgE
3. The company implements detailed orientation programs with specific milestones and regular progress reports as part of their integration programs.	3.45	LgE	3.78	LgE
4. The company effectively assigns top performers as mentors for new recruits so that their development and satisfaction levels can be elevated.	3.55	LgE	3.56	LgE
5. The company leverages new hire feedback and analytics to inform the human resources	3.55	LgE	3.66	LgE

department about its recruitment plan and optimize it accordingly.

Overall Weighted Mean **3.65** **LgE** **3.76** **LgE**

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 2, with a weighted mean score of 4.00 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of onboarding, while item no. 3 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.45 and interpreted as “large extent.”

Table 14

The Summary of the Extent of Implementation of the Selection Process

Selection Process	Managers		Staff	
	WM	QI	WM	QI
1. Assessment Procedure	3.93	LgE	3.87	LgE
2. Deal Closing	3.09	SE	3.68	LgE
3. Onboarding	3.65	LgE	3.76	LgE
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	LgE	3.77	LgE

Note. Legend: 4.21-5.00 (Very Large Extent-VLgE); 3.41-4.20 (Large Extent-LgE); 2.61-3.40 (Some Extent-SE); 1.81-2.60 (Little Extent-LtE); 1.00-1.80 (Very Little Extent-VLtE)

Based on assessments of the managers, item no. 1, with a weighted mean score of 3.93 and interpreted as “large extent,” obtained the highest extent of implementation of the selection process in terms of its variables, while item no. 2 received the lowest rank, with a weighted mean score of 3.09 and interpreted as “some extent.”

Table 15

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Age

Age	Ave.	SD	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
20-29 years old	3.73	0.17	1.82	0.165	Accept Ho	Not Significant
30-39 years old	3.76	0.14				
40-49 years old	3.49	0.19				
50-59 years old	3.64	0.26				
60 years old and older	4.00	0.58				
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
20-29 years old	3.94	0.22	5.95	0.002	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.97	0.19				
40-49 years old	4.08	0.15				
50-59 years old	3.95	0.22				
60 years old and older	4.44	0.27				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
20-29 years old	4.09	0.12	16.71	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	4.03	0.17				
40-49 years old	4.00	0.17				

50-59 years old	3.79	0.19
60 years old and older	4.57	0.25

Age	Ave.	SD	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
20-29 years old	3.99	0.17	8.73	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.79	0.18				
40-49 years old	3.87	0.26				
50-59 years old	3.69	0.31				
60 years old and older	4.53	0.30				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
20-29 years old	3.55	0.25	3.40	0.028	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.74	0.16				
40-49 years old	3.48	0.15				
50-59 years old	3.51	0.17				
60 years old and older	4.07	0.55				
<u>Onboarding</u>						
20-29 years old	3.68	0.20	3.54	0.024	Reject Ho	Significant
30-39 years old	3.91	0.21				
40-49 years old	3.68	0.22				
50-59 years old	3.44	0.28				
60 years old and older	3.93	0.28				

Note. The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed p -values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis [$p = 0.002$], pool development [$p = 0.000$], assessment procedure [$p = 0.000$], deal closing [$p = 0.028$], and onboarding [$p = 0.024$] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [$p = 0.165$] is above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 16

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Sex

Sex	Ave.	SD	t	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
Male	3.63	0.19	-1.15	0.287	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Female	3.76	0.14				
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
Male	3.83	0.18	-3.21	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant
Female	4.17	0.19				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
Male	3.90	0.13	-3.61	0.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Female	4.17	0.16				

Sex	Ave.	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
Male	3.80	0.13	-1.49	0.181	Accept	Not Significant Ho
Female	3.96	0.19			Ho	
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
Male	3.57	0.06	-1.40	0.220	Accept	Not Significant Ho
Female	3.68	0.17			Ho	
<u>Onboarding</u>						
Male	3.64	0.17	-2.14	0.065	Accept	Not Significant Ho
Female	3.86	0.15			Ho	

*Note. The *p*-value is significant below alpha 0.05*

Based on the gathered data, the computed *p*-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis [*p* = 0.009] and pool development [*p* = 0.004] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [*p* = 0.287], assessment procedure [*p* = 0.181], deal closing [*p* = 0.220], and onboarding [*p* = 0.065] are above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 17

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Ave.	SD	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	3.80	0.16	7.25	0.009	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.38	0.20				
Doctoral Degree	3.69	0.18				
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	4.12	0.19	15.32	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.86	0.11				
Doctoral Degree	3.52	0.25				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	4.10	0.15	11.99	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.80	0.15				
Doctoral Degree	4.13	0.12				
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	3.99	0.22	6.27	0.014	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.58	0.16				
Doctoral Degree	3.80	0.16				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
Bachelor's Degree	3.83	0.18	56.26	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Master's Degree	3.40	0.13				

Doctoral Degree	2.82	0.14				
Onboarding						
Bachelor's Degree	3.82	0.15	3.06	0.084	Accept	Not Significant
Master's Degree	3.63	0.21			Ho	
Doctoral Degree	3.55	0.18				

Note. The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed p -values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of needs anticipation [$p = 0.009$], job analysis [$p = 0.000$], pool development [$p = 0.000$], assessment procedure [$p = 0.014$], and deal closing [$p = 0.000$] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the onboarding [$p = 0.084$] is above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 18

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Designation

Designation	Ave.	SD	t	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
Needs Anticipation						
Manager	3.44	0.27	-2.03	0.082	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	3.72	0.17			Ho	
Job Analysis						
Manager	3.26	0.19	-7.83	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
Staff	4.08	0.18				
Pool Development						
Manager	3.87	0.19	-2.10	0.060	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	4.05	0.13			Ho	
Selection Process						
Assessment Procedure						
Manager	3.93	0.12	0.65	0.534	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	3.87	0.16			Ho	
Deal Closing						
Manager	3.09	0.20	-5.36	0.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Staff	3.68	0.14				
Onboarding						
Manager	3.65	0.22	-0.88	0.408	Accept	Not Significant
Staff	3.76	0.15			Ho	

Note. The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed p -values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis [$p = 0.000$] and deal closing [$p = 0.001$] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [$p = 0.082$], pool development [$p = 0.060$], assessment procedure [$p = 0.534$], and onboarding [$p = 0.408$] are above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Table 19

The Significant Difference in the Assessments of the Respondents in the Extent of Implementation of the Recruitment and Selection Process When Grouped According to Years of Employment at the Company

Years of Employment at the Company	Ave.	SD	F	p	Decision	Interpretation
Recruitment Process						
<u>Needs Anticipation</u>						
1-5 years	3.80	0.22	0.95	0.455	Accept Ho	Not Significant
6-10 years	3.58	0.14				
11-15 years	3.78	0.11				
16-20 years	3.56	0.32				
21 years and above	3.48	0.59				
<hr/>						
Recruitment Process						
<u>Job Analysis</u>						
1-5 years	3.96	0.23	1.99	0.128	Accept Ho	Not Significant
6-10 years	4.01	0.18				
11-15 years	4.13	0.22				
16-20 years	3.85	0.28				
21 years and above	3.77	0.29				
<u>Pool Development</u>						
1-5 years	4.23	0.10	13.46	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
6-10 years	3.90	0.18				
11-15 years	3.94	0.13				
16-20 years	3.68	0.20				
21 years and above	4.43	0.35				
<hr/>						
Selection Process						
<u>Assessment Procedure</u>						
1-5 years	3.98	0.25	3.33	0.030	Reject Ho	Significant
6-10 years	3.76	0.18				
11-15 years	3.93	0.21				
16-20 years	3.58	0.14				
21 years and above	4.12	0.41				
<u>Deal Closing</u>						
1-5 years	3.78	0.20	16.86	0.000	Reject Ho	Significant
6-10 years	3.51	0.11				
11-15 years	3.52	0.17				
16-20 years	3.33	0.08				
21 years and above	4.12	0.23				
<u>Onboarding</u>						
1-5 years	3.77	0.18	1.89	0.152	Accept Ho	Not Significant
6-10 years	3.84	0.18				
11-15 years	3.73	0.17				
16-20 years	3.44	0.30				

21 years and above	3.68	0.33
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Note. The p-value is significant below alpha 0.05

Based on the gathered data, the computed p-values for the recruitment and selection process in terms of pool development [$p = 0.000$], assessment procedure [$p = 0.030$], and deal closing [$p = 0.00$] are below the level of alpha at 0.05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis and showing a significant difference, while the needs anticipation [$p = 0.455$], job analysis [$p = 0.128$], and onboarding [$p = 0.152$] are above the alpha level of significance, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Discussion

The majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were 30-39 years old, while the minority were 60 years old and older; the highest proportion of the respondents were in their 30s. Moreover, the majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were predominantly males, while a minor proportion were females.

In terms of the respondents' educational attainment, the majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were bachelor's degree holders, while the minority were doctoral degree holders and the highest proportion of the respondents were college graduates. The majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company were predominantly staff members, while a minor proportion were designated with management responsibilities.

The majority of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process of the company have predominantly been employed for about 1-5 years, while a minor proportion have been employed for 21 years and above. The highest proportion of the respondents were in the early stages of their employment at the company.

The findings in the recruitment process' implementation were to an acceptable standard, that the company made sure to consistently carry out a proactive study of future requirements and continuously evaluate the status of some of the best personnel that is certain to depart. Furthermore, the results demonstrated that, to plan strategically for the year that lies ahead, the company also examines the proposed job description and structure of operations to make sure that it fully satisfies the needs of the company and that hiring needs and goals are aligned.

Nevertheless, both managers and staff pointed out that there are still gaps in the facts provided above, indicating that the company should concentrate more on establishing a recruitment plan to help expedite the hiring process and identify positions that would require encompassing soon. This is an opportunity to combine company goals and skill gaps with hiring actions in order to proactively plan for the upcoming year. It goes considerably beyond simply knowing what roles need to be filled soon. This suggested that in order to

meet the demands of modern business objectives, the company should utilize the results to improve the way its recruitment practices are implemented in terms of needs anticipation.

The findings demonstrated also how the company decided how to evaluate employee performance and made sure the position and the prospective employee were a good fit. Furthermore, the managers' observations indicated that the company additionally performs an adequate task of outlining the responsibilities of the role and has a thorough grasp of the business aims related to it.

The company should, however, continue putting an emphasis on the lists of qualities and skills required by potential applicants and even find innovative methods to fine-tune the function for improved efficacy in spite of the aforementioned facts. Essentially, the extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of pool development obtained overall weighted means of 3.87 and 4.05 as assessed by the managers and staff, respectively, and both were interpreted as "large extent.". The findings demonstrated that the company made sure to align its expansion strategies with employee advancement and succession planning. Additionally, the results of the investigation demonstrated that the company additionally placed importance on reviewing the succession plan each time a job becomes open or a need to fill one arises.

Even so, both respondents (managers and staff) pointed out that there are still gaps in the information provided, which means the company should emphasize more on expanding the pool of candidates for a position in order to attract qualified applicants. It should focus on the use cost-effective e-recruiting systems, which enable an organization to gather, store, and process information quickly and use it for external sourcing in this new normal of the recruitment process. This agrees to the conclusion made MBA Knowledge Base in 2021 that company can use e-recruiting to swiftly gather data, store and retrieve information, and then utilize this information for external sourcing as needed (MBA Knowledge Base, 2021). Recruiters for human resources can broaden their prospect pool by doing this. They may access a wider pool of possible candidates when they publish about a job opening, which also broadens their selection process. They are therefore able to choose the right applicants (Khanna, 2021). This emphasized that in order to cope with the demands of present-day business targets, the company should apply the pool development findings to strengthen the way its processes for recruiting employees are implemented.

Overall, the extent of implementation of the recruitment process in terms of its variables obtained overall weighted means of 3.52 and 3.95 as assessed by the managers and staff, respectively, and both were interpreted as "large extent."

The study's findings revealed a satisfactory level of implementation of the recruitment process. According to both respondents, the results showed that the company made sure that a candidate pool for a job offer or opportunity was routinely developed by using both internal and external methods of discovering prospects.

Closing is a crucial step in the hiring process. The company should make it a point to find out what matters most to the best applicants (McConnachie, 2019). One of the most rewarding and difficult parts of recruitment is closing top applicants in a highly competitive environment. Convincing the top personnel to join the company is a blend of abilities, tactics, and mentality. It is important to fully understand their expectations, preferences, and motivations. This meant that to meet the company's present demand, it would be necessary to use the results to enhance the way its selection process operates.

Moreover, for comparisons, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those respondents belonged to 60 years old and older [60 years old and older>other age groups] perceived a higher extent of implementation across variables of recruitment and selection process compared to other age groups.

Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the respondents in the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis, pool development, assessment procedure, deal closing, and onboarding when they were grouped according to age.

Moreover, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those female respondents perceived a higher extent of implementation in terms of job analysis and pool development compared to the male group of respondents.

Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the respondents in the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis and pool development when they were grouped according to sex.

Moreover, for comparisons, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those respondents with bachelor's degrees in terms of needs anticipation, job analysis, assessment procedure, and deal closing [Bachelor's degree>other groups] as well as those respondents with doctoral degrees in terms of pool development [Doctoral degree>other groups] perceived a higher extent of implementation compared to other educational attainment groups.

Furthermore, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those staff respondents perceived a higher extent of implementation in terms of job analysis and deal closing compared to assessments made by the managers. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in the assessments of the respondents in the extent of implementation of the recruitment and selection process in terms of job analysis and deal closing when they were grouped according to designation.

Likewise, for comparisons, as can be gleaned from the average means, it showed that those respondents who have been employed for 21 years and above perceived a higher extent of implementation in terms of pool development, assessment procedure, and deal closing [21 years and above>other groups] compared to other years of employment at the company groups.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the above findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn by the researcher:

The study showed that the highest proportion of the respondents involved in the recruitment and selection process were in their 30s, females, holders of bachelor's degrees, staff members, and were in the early stages of their employment at the company.

The study found that the company effectively implemented its recruitment process, creating a candidate pool for job offers using both internal and external methods. However, gaps were identified, suggesting the anticipation of the need for more staff observations and managers' perceptions of job analysis. To better understand the job's complexity, context, responsibilities, and practices, the company should conduct proactive analysis of future demands, continuously evaluate potential candidate pools, and generate periodic forecasts of needs. This will help the business adapt to the current environment and improve its recruitment process.

The investigation revealed that the company's selection process was effectively implemented, with a successful assessment procedure indicating a candidate's fit for the role and company culture. The onboarding process was methodical and orderly, aiming to encourage commitment and job satisfaction. However, there are still gaps in the data gathered, and the company should focus more on deal closing, particularly signing employment agreements with highly qualified candidates. Respondents noted that the results could be used to enhance the selection process to meet the company's current demand. This would require addressing the data gaps and improving the selection process.

The study found that, when respondents were categorized based on their profiles, there was a substantial difference in the assessments provided by the two groups of respondents (managers and staff) regarding the extent of the recruiting and selection process's implementation. This suggested that, in order to conduct a specific intervention based on differences in observation applicable to each category of variables, a significant difference in the respondents' observations regarding the extent of the implementation of the recruitment and selection process should be employed.

The following recommendations were proposed based on the findings and conclusions of the study:

1. It is recommended that future research address the shortcomings of the current study, potentially including the inclusion of more companies in various Chinese regions for comparative analysis and broader study conclusions. Also, it must be noted that that strategy development and post-hire evaluation be developed to fill up the gaps found and improve the company's recruitment and selection process over time.
2. Future research should employ qualitative approaches through interviews and focus group discussions to elucidate distinctions based on respondents' observations to confirm the various points of view conveyed by the respondents.
3. The study recommended utilizing the proposed program development to improve the effectiveness of the recruitment and selection process for the company.

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Satisfaction to the Front Liner Student Services: A Basis for the Service Improvement of Student Affairs and Services

Lou S. Hualda^{1*} Ronald Q. Quinto²

^{1,2}Bataan Peninsula State University, Balanga Campus, College of Arts and Sciences,
Philippines
rqquinto@bpsu.edu.ph

Abstract

Student affairs and services play an essential role in the holistic development of students within an academic institution. The overall educational experience and well-being of each student are influenced by the quality of services offered by the various units operating under the Office of Student Affairs and Services (OSAS). Thus, this study aimed to assess the satisfaction levels of Bataan Peninsula State University students regarding the services provided by the frontline offices supervised by the OSAS. To evaluate the performance of each office, the study employed a descriptive research design utilizing survey questionnaires. The findings revealed that the majority of services provided by the frontline offices were satisfactorily implemented, particularly those offered by the Scholarship office. However, certain aspects contributed to students' dissatisfaction, including the inefficiency and lack of organization in enrolment procedures, insufficient ventilation, chairs, and tables in the canteen, and the absence of a drinking fountain and dressing room within the campus. Furthermore, despite the university's regular evaluation of various units, it is imperative to consider but disseminate the results to the respective units to ensure that they are informed about their performance and encourages them to develop improvement plans in response to identified areas of concern.

Keywords: students affairs, frontline services, student satisfaction

Introduction

The Bataan Peninsula State University–Student Affairs and Services is committed to student-centered education which involves in providing quality support and development services to assists students to achieve their potential in their academic endeavors and succeed in their chosen career. Essential to the attainment of this goal is the assessment and evaluation of the performances of student services provided by frontline service offices for the continuous improvement of Student Affairs and Services unit. Since the quality of student support services has a strong influence on student retention, student’s learning and positive experiences within the University (Mahan 2001), it is necessary then that student services programs must be properly responsive to the needs of the students and the challenges of fast changing socio-economic and technological condition of our society.

Student services in higher educational institutions refer to the divisions that provide services, programs, and resources that help students learn and grow outside of the classroom (NASA, 2012). Generally, the services include enhancing student learning, providing guide academic and career decisions, mentoring students, promoting leadership skills, counselling students through crises and others. Frontline services in higher education institutions, on the other hand, refer to services directly provided to the students that may involve direct contact with them; these are admission services, registrar/record services, finance services, library, maintenance services, security services, guidance services, health services, and food services.

In compliance with the requirement of Policies and Guidelines on Student Affairs and Services (CMO N0. 9, s. 2013) by the CHED, every semester, the Office of the Student Affairs and Services of each campus of BPSU is tasked to undertake an evaluation of these services provided by the following offices: Registrar’s Office, Guidance Office, Cashier’s Office, Library, Clinic, School Cafeteria, Security, and Maintenance Services Unit. Most of these frontline services are under the supervision of the Office of Student Affairs and Services (OSAS) as indicated in its mandate. This segment of the University (OSAS) is commissioned to provide services and programs that are concerned with academic support experiences of students in attaining holistic student development. Academic support services are those that relate to student welfare, student development and those that relate to institutional program and services (CMO No. 09 s2013). As such, it supervises the following units or services: admission, guidance, health clinic, and school cafeteria.

Evaluating the performance of the frontline services by the students is very useful for the institutions to help responsible units identify their strengths and pinpoint areas that could be improved thereby providing excellent services to the most important client of the University, the students. The regular evaluation of the OSAS to the said offices serves as an instrument to measure the efficacy and assess their performance in order to know their strong and weak points in the delivery of their services. Results and findings provide feedback to the

staff regarding their performance thereby help them to make progress as they perform their specific job.

Hence, this research work intended to examine the satisfaction of the students to the services provided by frontline units as reflected in the evaluation of student services conducted by the OSAS, as well as to scrutinize the items in the evaluation tool to pinpoint the strength and weaknesses of delivery of services by each unit. Findings of this work can be used as basis for the Office of the Student Affairs and Services to designed more responsive programs of concerned units under its supervision and provide recommendation to other concerned units for improvement and better delivery of services.

Methods

The study used the descriptive research design to assessed the level of satisfaction of the students in Bataan Peninsula State University Balanga Campus to the Front Liner Student Services provided by OSA Practitioners during the Academic Years 2015-2018. The study utilized a convenient sample particularly the quota sampling. Participants were selected based on their availability during the scheduled conduct of survey by the researcher. On quota sampling, the researcher picked 360 students which are divided equally based on college and year level. Available personnel of frontline servicing units were also interviewed to elicit further information, clarification, and suggestions to contextualize the findings in the data analysis and discussion. Since, this research utilized previous data (Evaluation of Student Services 2015 – 2018) from OSAS, it is then worth to mention that participants during the time these evaluations were conducted and these were students currently enrolled during the time period and were also selected using convenient sampling. In determining the level of satisfaction, frequency count and weighted mean was utilized. To discriminate items along each of the services, the mean of each item was also supported by percentile rank to describe the strength of each item and the standard deviation to describe the homogeneity or heterogeneity of the responses. the Kruskal Wallis and the Mann Whitney U Test were utilized to determine the significant difference of the level of satisfaction along the Frontline Student Services and personal profile.

Results

There are ten units of the student services considered in this study namely: registrar, guidance, admission, scholarship, library, cashier, clinic, school cafeteria, security, and maintenance. Table 1 reflects the level of satisfaction of each unit based on how well it conducts and implement their duties, responsibilities, and programs.

Table 1. The Level of Satisfaction to the Frontline Service

Summary of the level of satisfaction to the frontline service from 1st semester of 2015 to 2nd semester of 2018

	2015-2016		2016-2017		2017-2018		MEAN	SD
	1st Sem SY 2015-16	2nd Sem SY 2015-16	1st Sem SY 2016-17	2nd Sem SY 2016-17	1st Sem SY 2017-18	2nd Sem SY 2017-18		
Student Services								
Registrar's Office	2.49	2.64	2.85	2.74	2.78	2.79	2.715	0.130
Guidance Office	2.14	2.31	3.09	3.01	3.02	3.21	2.797	0.452
Admission Office	2.66	2.78	2.95	2.87	2.99	2.98	2.872	0.130
Scholarship Office	2.65	2.78	3.12	3.16	3.18	3.25	3.023	0.246
Library	2.79	2.81	2.88	2.76	2.97	3.12	2.888	0.136
Cashier's Office	2.77	2.80	2.99	2.77	2.88	2.91	2.853	0.089
Clinic	2.68	2.51	3.03	2.98	3.04	3.08	2.887	0.234
School Cafeteria	2.45	2.63	2.57	2.55	2.70	2.63	2.588	0.086
Security	2.55	2.70	2.67	2.53	2.91	2.81	2.695	0.147
Maintenance	2.25	2.40	2.26	2.38	2.73	2.36	2.397	0.175
Gen Average	2.543	2.636	2.841	2.775	2.920	2.914	2.772	0.153

Interpretation: 3.25-4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.24 = Agree; 1.75-2.49 = Disagree; 1.00-1.74 = Strongly Agree

Registrar Office

For the period SY 2015- 2016 to SY 2017-2018, the registrar was able to maintain its level of performance which is “satisfactory” in providing to the students with minimal improvement or an increase of 12%. With an average mean 2.79 or ‘satisfactory’, respondents demonstrate satisfaction with the services provided by the unit particularly in terms of information dissemination and informing students regarding their deficiency. However, they are least satisfied with the order and efficiency of enrolment procedures.

Guidance Office

There is a significant improvement in the performance of the Guidance office from 2.14 (fairly satisfied) in the 1st semester of SY 2015-2016 to 3.21 (satisfied) in the 2nd semester of 2017-2018. This entails a 50% development in the delivery of services of the Guidance as one of the OSA frontline services. The respondents are generally satisfied with the performance of the Guidance office, with an average mean of 3.21 interpreted as satisfied. The respondents expressed higher satisfaction on items involving the skills of the guidance counselor in

accommodating and assisting students in their guidance-related needs. Respondents are least satisfied in terms of giving feedback on personality tests and career guidance counseling.

Admission Office

There is a minimal improvement in the performance of the Admission Office though remained in a satisfactory level, from an average mean of 2.66 to 2.98. With an average mean of 2.98 interpreted as satisfied, the respondents express satisfaction with the services of the admission office, especially about the accessibility of the results of exams. However, respondents are least satisfied with the items related to assistance in career planning during the admission process.

Scholarship Office

The improvement in the performance of the Scholarship office ranges from the average mean of 2.65 (satisfied) to 3.25 (very satisfied). The improvement is attributed to the substantial increase of several scholarship programs offered by the University. With an average mean of 3.25 interpreted as very satisfied, respondents express higher satisfaction with the services of the Scholarship office. Particularly, respondents are very satisfied with the various scholarships offered by the University and the monitoring of the welfare of the scholarship grantees. The respondents are least satisfied compared to other items in the Dissemination of information such as posting on bulletin boards, brochures, and leaflets.

Library

The improvement in the performance of the Library is rated “fairly satisfied” with an average mean of 2.49 to “satisfied” with an average mean of 3.12. This registered a 25.3% increase. The respondents are generally satisfied with the services of the Library as it registered a rating of 3.12 with a descriptive rating of “satisfied”. Respondents express higher satisfaction on items related to the physical facilities of the Library such as adequate ventilation and furniture. On the other hand, they are least satisfied with the characteristics of library staff.

Cashier Office

There is a sustained average level of performance of the cashier within 3 years with an average mean of 2.8 with a descriptive rating of “Satisfied.” No noticeable improvement within the 3-year covered period. With an average mean of 2.91, the respondents demonstrate an average satisfaction with the services of the Cashier's office. The item that ranked first is the convenient location of the Cahier’s office with a mean of 3.16, while the lowest in rank is the item relating to staff’s courteousness and accommodation.

Clinic

There is a slight increase in the performance of the Clinic within the three-year covered period, from a mean of 2.68 to 3.08 which are both in the descriptive rating "Satisfied". The respondent's level of satisfaction with the service provided by the Clinic is descriptively rated as "satisfied" with a mean of 3.08. The item in which respondents were most satisfied was "clinic staff can provide emergency clinic" with a mean of 3.22 descriptively, while the item they were least satisfied with was "As a student I undergo medical check-up as the need arises" with a mean of 2.84. Both items are descriptively rated as "satisfied".

School Cafeteria

There is an almost stationary performance of the school cafeteria, from a mean of 2.45 to a mean of 2.63 both descriptively rated as "satisfied". No noticeable improvement was registered within the three covered years. The respondents have an average level of satisfaction with the services of the school cafeteria with a mean of 2.63. Respondents were highly satisfied with regards to the neat and courteous food handler with a mean of 2.86 descriptively rated as "satisfied", while they expressed least satisfaction in the items related to physical facilities like inadequate ventilation, chairs, and tables which are rated as "fairly satisfied".

Security

There is a slight improvement in the performance of security services as its average satisfactory rating within three years progressed from a mean of 2.55 to 2.81. The rating however did not move out of its rating satisfied. The respondents expressed an average level of satisfaction through a mean of 2.81 descriptively rated as "satisfied". Respondents were most satisfied with the item "I feel safe at BPSU" with a mean of 3.11, while expressed lowest satisfaction in item "All students receive equal treatment from the guard" with a mean of 2.48 descriptively rated as "fairly satisfied".

Maintenance

There is a sustained "fairly satisfied performance" of the Maintenance with a mean of 2.40 for three years, though it was able to reach a satisfactory rating with a mean of 2.73 during the 1st semester of SY 2017-2018. With a mean of 2.36, the respondents were fairly satisfied to the services of the Maintenance. Respondents were most satisfied with the items "Waste cans are located in accessible places on campus" and "Cleanliness of the School Areas" with a mean of 2.72 and 2.64 respectively. On the other hand, they were least satisfied with the items on the availability of drinking fountain and faucets and dressing room for PE and sports purposes, with a mean of 1.74 and 1.96, both with descriptive ratings "fairly satisfied". expressed higher satisfaction while the fourth-year respondents manifested higher level of satisfaction compared to other real levels.

Table 2. Summary of the Difference in the Level of Satisfaction to Frontline Services

	Colleges	Year Level	Age	Academic Performance	Sex	Civil Status
Registrar	1	1	0	0	0	0
Guidance	1	0	0	0	0	0
Admission	1	0	0	0	1	0
Scholarship	0	0	0	0	0	0
Library	1	0	1	0	1	0
Cashier	0	1	0	0	1	0
Clinic	1	0	0	0	0	0
Cafeteria	0	1	1	0	0	0
Security	0	0	0	0	0	0
Maintenance	1	0	0	0	0	0

Interpretation: 1 = Significant; 0 = Not Significant

The study examined satisfaction levels among respondents in various student affairs services, analyzing different profile variables. The Registrar's office revealed significant differences in satisfaction based on college and year level. Respondents of the College of Education (CoEd) and fourth-year respondents exhibited higher satisfaction. In Guidance services, only the College variable showed a significant difference, with CoEd respondents expressing higher satisfaction. Admission services displayed significant differences based on College and Sex, with CoEd and male respondents reporting higher satisfaction. Scholarship and Security services showed no significant differences. The library services exhibited significant differences based on college, age, and sex, with CoEd, '25 and above' age group, and male respondents reporting higher satisfaction. Cashiering service had significant differences in year level and sex, with third-year and male respondents expressing higher satisfaction. The Clinic displayed a significant difference based on the college variable, with CoEd expressing higher satisfaction. School cafeteria services showed significant differences in year level and age, with first-year and '25 and above' age groups reporting higher satisfaction. Maintenance services exhibited a significant difference based on the college variable, with CoEd respondents expressing higher satisfaction.

Discussion

The rating of the registrar's services showed that respondents are generally satisfied with the services provided by the registrar. Among the services provided that showed very good performance is the prompt dissemination of information especially regarding students' deficiencies and other important information. However, it is noteworthy to mention that there is a need to address the inefficient enrolment process as items on enrolment procedures consistently obtained the lowest rank. According to the registrar during the interview, perception of the inefficiency and disorganized enrolment procedures can be attributed first to the leniency of students in following the enrolment procedures like the "first come first serve" and "one transaction one student" rules; second, to the late encoding of grades by the instructors causing the tendency of students to revisit the registrar office multiple times.

The figure shows that there is a remarkable improvement in the performance of the Guidance Office with a six-semester period as it grew from 2.14 to 3.21 or a fifty percent increase, and nearly reaching a "very satisfied" rating. The progress of its ratings illustrates that the office was consistent in its intent to improve its services to the students. According to the guidance counselor, this was also the result of the regular conduct of orientation and seminars to the students. Students' negative perception or the stigma related to the guidance office has changed as they become more aware of its true functions and goals. Moreover, respondents were almost very satisfied with the performance of the guidance office particularly in their dealings with the guidance counselor. The "very satisfied rating" of the guidance counselor in terms of accommodating students and giving them advice illustrates the counselor's people skills such as good communicator and a good listener. On the other hand, the lower rank obtained by items on the interpretation of personality tests and having felt relieved after counseling sessions might be caused by a lesser number of students availing these types of services. It was possible that the majority of the respondents did not visit the guidance to take a personality test or for guidance counseling. Furthermore, some students who took personality tests did not take time to visit again the office to know the results of their tests according to the guidance counselor. Among the colleges, it was the COED that showed higher satisfaction compared to others. This higher level of satisfaction can be attributed to a higher number of education students availing guidance services and participation in other services like orientation, seminars, and training.

The figure on scholarship services shows a significant improvement in the services provided by the scholarship office as the rating upgraded from satisfactory to very satisfactory. This could be explained by the substantial increase in the number of scholarship programs offered by the University within the covered period. This has led to an increase in number of students availing scholarship form private and public organization through effort of the office. The higher rating given to the office by the respondents was also expected since this is the services that provide direct and tangible benefit to the beneficiaries of scholarship programs, according to the interview with student affairs personnel. In particular, the

University grants full and partial scholarship to those students who excel in their academics. Scholarship was granted also to members of arts and cultural groups such as the theater group and different dance group. Varsity players, student leaders and the staff of student publications were also granted institutional scholarship. Moreover, numerous scholarship both from public and private organization were being enjoyed by substantial number of students. Though still in the level of satisfaction rating, dissemination of information regarding scholarship, however must be given consideration as it got the lowest rank among the items.

The respondents were generally satisfied with the performance of the admission office but showed higher satisfaction on the accessibility of test results through tarpaulin and online website. The accessibility of information from the internet such as admission results proved to be a good practice as more and more people today rely on internet for easy and fast transactions.

The figure on the library services shows that was very little improvement in the services provided by the library throughout the 3-year covered period but the presence of declining performance in the midperiod (2nd semester of SY 2016-2017). This implies that either no significant change has occurred in the library within a covered period or any effort in improving the services has not been recognized by the students. However, the findings imply that the library provides a conducive physical environment for studying as items with adequate ventilation and library furniture that contribute to comfortable library work gained the highest rank among other items. Furthermore, the perception that library staff are strict, unapproachable, and unfriendly, according to the librarian, could be attributed to reminding and reprimanding students exhibiting boisterous behavior inside the library. Among the three colleges, respondents from the CoEd were more satisfied with the services provided by the library and this could be attributed to the number of CoEd students visiting the library. According to library staff, most students who visit the library come from the College of Education. Furthermore, they usually tend to have partnerships with CoEd student organizations in the implementation of their activities for promotion and other strategic activities.

The findings on cashiering services imply that the Cashier is on the right strategic and conspicuous location which can be easily accessed by the students, moreover, the waiting area with enough available seats for students waiting for their turn could also be attributed to the satisfaction of the students. On the other hand, respondents showed less satisfaction with regards to staff's conduct specifically of giving prompt service, and of being courteous and accommodating. This is confirmed by some comments from students stating that some cashier staff are not welcoming. Among the personal variables, only age and sex have a significant difference about the respondents' level of satisfaction, with "third-year" and "male" respondents showing higher satisfaction compared to other levels and females respectively. This implies these groups demonstrate patience and understanding in spite of waiting for

many hours due to long queuing. Further, cashier staff attested that they seldom encounter problems in their dealings with male students compared to female.

The findings on the services of the clinic imply that the staff have been very responsive to the immediate and emergency needs of the students. This also indicates that clinic personnel particularly nurses as well as emergency medicines and equipment are always available at any time. This could be justified also by the correct/proper schedule being set up by the nurses. The Office of Student Affairs always makes certain that clinic hours extend up to the last scheduled class of the day from Monday to Saturday. On the other hand, items that obtained lower satisfaction levels ("I undergo medical and dental check as the need arises) would imply that some students would tend to tolerate their medical and dental problems either because they are not aware of the free services provided by the clinic or they thought that will not be attended anyway due to unavailability of medical personnel. The latter however is understandable and expected as explained by clinic staff since both the dentist and doctor are also assigned at other campuses, hence would only be available for one or two days per campus. Among the personal variables, only the college variable has a significant difference in the satisfaction of the respondents with the services of the clinic. And it is the respondents from CoEd that expressed a higher level of satisfaction. This could mean that CoEd students are more aware of the services provided by the clinic and thus more of them are availing the said services. This claim was also attested by the nurses. They also stated that since CoEd students conduct more student extracurricular activities that require them medical certificates, naturally clinic visitors mostly come from the said college.

The figure on the school cafeteria indicates minimal improvement in the performance of the school cafeteria which would imply that no significant effort was extended to improve the quality of services provided by the canteen. It has been observed also by the respondents that the quality of service, the food being served, and the physical condition have not changed for several years. The findings imply that food handlers have been following the criteria in preparing and serving food as such as safety and sanitary conditions and the quality of food choices. It is expected however that safety and sanitary conditions are being satisfied by the canteen since the Office of Student Affairs requires the canteen a semi-annual sanitary permit from the Municipal Health Office as well as a health certificate from the food handlers. Moreover, the Clinic through the assigned doctor regularly checks the quality of food being served in the canteen.

Item referring to physical facilities and conditions of the canteen both obtained fairly satisfied rating, the lowest among all the items, this implies that students were not comfortable with the canteen's physical environment. Not only inadequate chairs and tables were the problem but also the lighting, ventilation and its location as it is situated at the far corner and darker side of the campus. The canteen staff however reasoned out that they cannot do something about the location and the inadequacy of equipment as they only depend on Administration's decision on where to place them inside the campus.

The figures on security services imply that the unit was able to maintain its performance on a satisfactory level but no significant improvement in its services has been observed. Based on interviews, there has been no modification in the way security personnel conducted their duties. However, the findings imply that respondents are generally satisfied with the services of the security unit except in an item referring to equal treatment of the guards to the students which implies that the guards might have been inconsistent in the implementation of rules and regulations and might have been playing favorites as also attested by the comments of some respondents.

The figures on maintenance services indicate that there is a slight improvement in the unit. Though the rating moved from fairly satisfied to satisfied in three covered periods, the movement was very minimal as it registered a 4.9% increase only. This implies that maintenance personnel conduct their activities the usual way and that no innovative ways of promoting cleanliness inside within the vicinity of the campus were introduced. The findings indicate that respondents were generally satisfied with the way the maintenance personnel performed their duties in upholding and preserving the cleanliness of the campus. However, they demonstrated little contentment about essential physical facilities that could attend to their needs such as comfort rooms, dressing rooms, and drinking fountains. This would mean that part of the problems encountered by students on campus is how to address their basic needs such as a clean comfort room and potable water to drink.

Among the personal variables, only the college variable has a significant difference, and it is the respondents from the COED that expressed higher satisfaction to the services provided by the maintenance. It has been observed by maintenance personnel that COED buildings and classrooms are generally cleaner compared to other colleges. This could be attributed, according to the head of maintenance, to the initiative and effort of COED particularly the student leaders through their projects and activities that uphold and preserve the cleanliness of the classrooms.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings and analyses of the study, it was found that:

1. Most of the services provided by the frontline units in BPSU Balanga Campus were satisfactorily implemented as eight out of the ten units garnered "satisfactory" rating from the respondents of the study. Scholarship is exemplary performing among the frontline servicing units since most of its indicators were rated "very satisfactory". Maintenance unit, on the other hand, was rated "fairly satisfied" in terms of its delivery of services.
2. Considering the entirety of the services provided by all the units, the items in which the respondents showed higher satisfaction are: the on-time and wide dissemination of information on academic records of the students and admission exam results; the

availability of numerous scholarship opportunities in the University; the skills and very welcoming attitude of the guidance counselor; the conducive venue for learning and study work in the library; the accessibility of the Cashier office; the prompt response of the Clinic on the emergency needs of the students; and the accommodating and kind behavior of canteen personnel.

The items that contributed to the dissatisfaction of the respondents, on the other hand, are: the inefficiency and lack of order of enrolment procedures; the seemingly no welcoming attitude of the library and cashier staff; the unequal treatment of the security personnel among the students; the inadequate ventilation, chairs and tables in the canteen; and the lack of drinking fountain and dressing room within the campus.

3. COED students were found to be more significantly satisfied in the services of the frontline servicing units than those from CBA and CSBS. This could be attributed to their active participation to the activities such as orientation and seminars given by the guidance office, clinic and library; and at the same time, they tend to avail more the services offered by these units. Hence, the extend of attendance and participation to the programs and activities provided frontline servicing units contributes to students' satisfaction to their services.

Male respondents were generally highly satisfied than their female counterpart in relation to the services provided by the Admission Office, Cahier Office and the Library. They were however satisfied similarly with the services of the rest of the frontline servicing units.

4. There is only incremental improvement in the delivery of services of almost frontline servicing units except the guidance office which progressed from the rating of "satisfactory" to "very satisfactory". Generally, all the units were able to perform at "satisfactory" level within the three-year covered period.

Upon a thorough consideration on the findings and conclusions derived from this study, the following recommendations were drawn as follows:

1. It would be worthwhile for all units of frontline services to consider the results of the semi-annual frontline services evaluation conducted by the Office of the Student Affairs and Services to analyze determine the effectiveness and efficiency of their service delivery and reflect on what they can do more to deliver quality services to the students.
2. Training on stress management and trainings that cultivate soft and people skills such as communication and listening skills, self-control, and positive attitude must be provided to the personnel of frontline offices. Being in the frontline service, they are expected to provide quality and positive experience to the clientele.
3. Frontline servicing units particularly the guidance office, clinic and library should develop plan such as extensive orientation and information dissemination on how to increase awareness, active participation and availment of services of students from the CBA and CSBS.
4. It is recommended that the frontline servicing units should be evaluated individually and not collectively. This is to ensure that each unit will be evaluated thoroughly by

covering all the areas/aspects of the unit concerned. To achieve this purpose, there is need to revise the present instrument since the items in the survey questionnaire per unit concerned are insufficient to generate more extensive and valid evaluations. Further, by evaluating all the units individually rather than collectively comparison between units would be sidestepped, consequently, the concerned can focus on its deficiency rather being more busied in comparing its performance with other units.

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Performance Analysis of Modern Management-Based Village Officials in Bube Village, Suwawa District, Bone Bolango Regency

Dityawati .A. Ingopo¹ Anis Naki² Djamila Podungge^{3*} and Siti Noviana Djou⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Bina Mandiri University Gorontalo

Correspondance Email: milapodungge@yahoo.com*

Email: ingopoditya@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to describe the performance of village officials who apply the principles of office management to achieve the goals of effective governance, where previously there was a lack of training provided to Village Officials regarding the use of modern-based applications such as the application of the Village Financial System (Siskeudes), and the Village Asset Management System (Sipades) and lack of office facilities that support performance in meeting work needs.

This research method uses a descriptive type with a qualitative approach, through the interview, observation, and documentation techniques. As informants in this study are the Village Head, Village Secretary, Head of Village Financial Affairs, and Head of General Planning and Administrative Affairs.

The results showed that: 1) Assessment of the performance of village officials containing modern management principles, namely discipline the performance appraisal of an employee in the Bube villages, discipline has not gone well, some of the village apparatuses that rarely enter, 2) the application of modern management in the management of the administration system in the Bube village government, has been implemented and at the end of each month a meeting is held for performance evaluation even though in reality some village officials do not carry out their duties and responsibilities optimally, 3) There has been no in-depth training on the Sipades application due to the lack of budget for training for the village asset processing system in 2020.

Keywords: Performance of Village Officials, and Modern Management

1. Introduction

Village Officers are employees of the lowest level of government administration who have obligations and responsibilities to provide services to residents, and assist the Village

Head in carrying out his duties to distribute services in accordance with the wishes of residents, therefore Village Officers are required to have commitment, expertise, skills and feelings of sincere attention and want great empathy in carrying out their duties to serve residents. It is hoped that residents will feel secure and satisfied with the services of Village Officers in resolving all administrative cases in the Village.

In the application of a development in this post-renewal period, the government has intended to increase the effectiveness and efficiency and productivity of its apparatus as well as mandated by the outline of the national development program, if our Government system adheres to the principles of decentralization, deconcentration, and medebewind, as a result of the position of Government as an instrument of state administration in carrying out the allocation, regulation, and stabilization of the national energy base can be carried out to the lowest level of government.

The government has a pioneering identity in implementing development programs, as a result, it requires public administration that can carry out government tasks and development tasks.

In creating the mandate, the application of Modern Management is necessary as a stage of utilization of the state apparatus. The main root that does not change is that the Village Government as the executor of the Government at the Village level with the attached authority is also currently regulated by government regulations. Many aspects can affect the capacity of the Village apparatus to perform their duties, for example, the lack of a base of data access and communication such as the current situation where the Village apparatus does not receive technical education, training nurseries, or careful data related to the management of Government administration, most notably in using applications that are modern technology platforms.

The results of the monitoring that was attempted, researchers saw that some Village Officers felt difficulties in handling the profession, this management was due to the lack of nursery training accompanied by Village Officers and the lack of adequate office facilities. Not only that, sluggish services, for example, in the administration of message records such as for the needs of E-ID cards, birth certificates, and others, are far from perfect, technological capabilities, lack of insight caused by the lack of data, nursery training or technical education accompanied by Village Officers Bube can cause the management to be intertwined. Data disclosure in an open way of industrial affairs is very meaningful for the kurusanayak industry. This management is attempted as a form of clarity and accountability of industry management to stakeholders.

The continuity of data from the industry can be used as estimation material for stakeholders in the collection of decisions. The application and management of good corporate governance better known as good corporate governance is a plan that emphasizes the meaning of the rights of shareholders to get data correctly, carefully, and at the right time. Not only that, GCG also proves the role of the industry to say (disclosure) all data on the financial and non-financial capabilities of the industry in a careful, timely, and transparent manner. Therefore, both public and private industries must view good corporate governance (GCG) not as an accessory, but as an effort to increase the industry's capabilities and numbers. Going from that view, when dealing with the situation in the research position that the researchers tried, precisely in Bube Village, Suwawa Subdistrict, Bone Bolango Regency, it is

not yet categorized as advanced, the village officials are not well versed in the regulations from the upper levels and the operating system of applications with modern technology platforms, as a result, the Government activities are not running optimally. Based on the researcher's early observations, it is evident that the base of people's energy and the ability of the Bube Village apparatus in managing the administration of the village government is not yet maximum, as a result an in-depth observation is needed to recognize the position of Village Officers in carrying out the Government system in the village which is based on industrial functions and practices the principles of Good Corporate Governance.

Particularly in creating good governance rules and supporting national development in the maximum way is the availability of a base of energy of professional people and modern technological office facilities. An office must have a variety of various overall activity facilities such as office buildings, PCs, desks, benches cabinets, and other supporting facilities such as bureau transportation. Activity facilities are a form of service to employees in supporting abilities. Periset concludes that the availability of a base of people energy and activity facilities has an important impact on the capacity of Village Officers in Bube Village, Suwawa Sub-district, Bone Bolango Regency.

Analysis

The analysis comes from the English word analysis which means: to peel, describe, discuss, and review. Analysis is a way of breaking down something into separate factors to understand the character, relationship, and contribution of each factor. In linguistics, analysis or analysis is an observation carried out on a language to research the structure of the language in an in-depth way. For KBBI, analysis is the tracking of an incident (essay, action, and the like) to recognize the real conditions (causes, reasons, reasons, etc.); the decomposition of something into its various parts, and the study of the parts themselves and the bonds between the parts to get the right interpretation and description of the meaning of the totality; (Management).

Performance

The interpretation of Ability is the result obtained by an agency that is profit-oriented and non-profit-oriented that is produced throughout duration. Ability is the result of the interaction or functioning of the elements of motivation, expertise, and assumption in a person. Ability is about what a person does and wants to bring about a result. Ability is the result of activities by way of quality and amount obtained by an employee in performing his duties following the responsibilities distributed to him. Ability is the production power resulting from the number of objects and services produced with the amount of activity power, capital, and energy base utilized in the creation.

Village Apparatus

The Village Apparatus is one of the tools of the Village government, not only the Village Head. According to the conclusion of Article 1 point 3 of the Village Law, the role of the Village Officer is to 'assist' the Village Head in carrying out the functions of the Government. The Village Apparatus or Officer is regulated in Articles 48 to 53 of the Village

Law. In a nutshell, these articles organize the roles and obligations of Village Officers; promotion and dismissal; income; and prohibitions in carrying out obligations.

Financial Management

Financial Management is a part of the industry's directive obligations with important responsibilities in the form of significant decisions regarding the capitalization and financing of the industry. [When connected with the principle of management, the acquisition, and use of the budget in the sense that it must be carried out efficiently and efficiently. Financial management is the entire activity of bonding with some goals. Therefore, the decision-making purpose of the financial administrator can be divided into 3 zones, namely decisions with capital, funding, and assets."

Operations Management

Based on the book Operation Management Operation is part of a business field agency that works to produce objects or services. Objects are physical equipment that includes anomalous materials. parts, subassemblies such as motherboards that are part of a PC, as well as final products such as a telephone head. On the other hand, a service is an activity that shares a numerical mix of duration, position, and intellectual numbers. On the other hand, surgical management is a system or method of management that produces objects or distributes services.

Modern Management

Modern management is management that in its period is characterized by having studied management as a science that has the basics of objective common sense, as a result of which many associate management experts or economists to carry out research on management which creates various philosophies or management movements. These theories were initially pioneered by Robert Owen, Adam Smith, Charles Babbage and Max Weber. Next are the claims that describe this type of management, namely: management cannot be viewed as a technical method with a fast way; management must be systematic, and the approach used must be with careful estimation; the body as a totality and the approach of individual administrators to supervision must be with atmosphere; an encouragement approach that creates employee commitment to the goals of the body is needed. Modern terminology, in The Contemporary English- Indonesia, is expressed most recently; modernism: modern actions, thoughts, popular actions; renewal: renewal to fit the current era. Modern interpretation proves that there is an exchange of something that was previously an approved method of doing something. Modern management is management based on a number of perspectives, such as: system design, analysis of provisions, the meaning of people and the social responsibility of people in the organization. Modern management is also being constantly derived from the best views of management. Modern management is formed based on the best practices of management, which are assisted by the latest approaches, guidance, methods and actions.

Definition of Management

Management is a special way consisting of actions of planning, organizing, mobilizing, and regulating to ensure and achieve goals through the exploitation of the energy base of people and other energy bases."

Definition of Human Resource Management

Management of the energy base of people is something planning, organizing, coordinating, implementing, and supervising the logistics, development, provision of responding services, integrating, and dividing resource activities in the chart of achieving agency goals.

Definition of discipline

Kedisiplinan is a tool that a superior uses to talk to his subordinates so that they want to change an attitude as an effort to increase the understanding and willingness of a person to obey all industry regulations and legal question norms. From that interpretation, it can be concluded that an activity order is an action of sold actions and actions that are following the rules, whether written or not recorded, and violations will have consequences for violations.

Definition of Modern Management

Modern management is management based on how much management is based on how much view, sort, system design, analysis of provisions. This means that the aspects of people and social responsibility of people in modern management bodies are also being constantly derived from the best views and management of modern management is built based on the best practices of management which are helped by the latest guidance approaches, methods, and actions.

Principles of Modern Management

- 1) Management cannot be looked at as a method in a tight way (share, method, and principle).
- 2) Management must be systematic and the approach used must be carefully estimated.
- 3) The agency as a totality and the individual administrator's approach to supervision must match the situation.

A motivational approach that creates employee commitment to agency goals is essential—benefits of modern management on village governance. Modern management will not be of much use if it is not assisted by elements that have influenced its success in its implementation. In many cases, the successful implementation of Modern Management success will be greatly influenced by various factors, including the Energy Base of People, infrastructure, and Data Systems. In connection with that, continuing to be a modern office continues to be a lot of data that can be accessed, and continues to be a great opportunity that can be used for the needs of the agency or institution. Modern offices today continue to approach the atmosphere and lead to a time when the use of paper is decreasing. Something in the future may be large office correspondence no longer using paper "paperless). Data alteration in its various forms will be carried out via email "electric post" using the internet, BBM, e-mail, and the web, as a result of which the data that is creamed and obtained more quickly, with the cost continuing to be economical.

Village Financial Management

Financial management is a form of administrative activity that is carried out in the form of some steps that include planning, storage of usage, recording, and supervision after which the way the budget goes in an agency. For the regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs (Permendagri) No. 113 of 2014 concerning Village financial management, it is stated

that Village financial management is defined as the totality of activities that include planning, implementation, administration, and accountability of village finances.

Village Asset Management

Law No. 6/2014 on Villages, Article 77 paragraph (1) states that the management of Village-owned assets is undertaken to improve the safety and livelihoods of villagers and to improve the safety and livelihoods of villagers and increase Village revenues. The purpose of managing Village-owned assets is in line with the previous regulation stipulated in Permendagri No.4/2007 in which the Village Administration used all of it for the needs and services of the Village residents.

2. Methods

This research method uses a descriptive type with a qualitative approach, through the interview, observation, and documentation techniques. As informants in this study are the Village Head, Village Secretary, Head of Village Financial Affairs, and Head of General Planning and Administrative Affairs.

3. Results

Work result

The handling of obligations attempted by Bube Village features is a form of obligation that must be completed and must be for all Bube Village officers because, with the handling of obligations, it can be seen that the extent of the level of dedication and can share something good and relieving services for the village community. Not only that but there are many more that are related to each handling of obligations from the leader, such as the superior of the Village government is the Village head and if there are obligations that must be completed by the government above it, it can be from the sub-district government and others. Handling the profession with good and appropriate duration is a measure of success in achieving the profession in the dimensions of expertise, accuracy, and responsibility.

Each employee if there is a profession that is always delayed until the application and handling will cause other professions to be neglected. From the results of questions and answers and observations attempted by researchers to the way obligations are handled by some Bube Village officials is less efficient and efficient. The Village Secretary stated that the handling of obligations from the Village apparatus is not good, such as a lack of energy base of people from the Village apparatus so aspects of expertise in handling obligations. The insight of office administration is one of the views that are very meaningful in distributing services, and administrative progress that results in a necessity regarding the increase in insight and abilities by the actors, namely Village government officials in the management of completing the tasks available, whether it is related to services to local villagers or the government above, The knowledge and skills of Village officials are also caused by the lack of office facilities, which results in the completion of obligations at the Bube Village office being a little slow, the availability of data technology and communication platform tools at the Bube Village office, such as PCs, is not yet in its totality and has not met the analogy with

the number of Village officials available, as a result making its use obligatory to take turns with other officers.

Discipline

Discipline related to the level of discipline possessed by officers includes discipline to the application of any provisions or orders from the leadership mean orders that arrive from a larger government can be from the sub-district office and can also be from the leader is the village head. Actions and obedient attitudes that concern the accuracy of duration in a profession can also be listed among others in the management of carrying out tasks in serving citizens and can also be other obligations, for example from the leadership, discipline in the results of this research is order with the duration of attendance and return of officers from the Bube Village office. Duration is a discipline that greatly influences the ability and action which in turn has a good influence on the effectiveness or efficiency of the results of the activities of the Bube Village officers, not only that, order requires a very large understanding as a result of being able to help in the management of achieving the ability and action and helping in the management of achieving something that is the goal of the body and maximum. The discipline that affects is the discipline of duration and professional discipline and action where both must be able to be in line and harmony if you want to get good results and greatly affect the results to be obtained. Observations and questions and answers carried out by researchers to officers at the Bube Village office, in reviewing from the discipline marker that the orderliness of Village officials to the duration of activities is very poor, including some Village officials who are not often attending activities. The reality that researchers have in the field, that the Village apparatus is in shifts by the Village apparatus, the number of Village apparatus there are 8 people including the Village Head, Village Secretary, Village Head, Village Government Section head of planning, Kasie Kesra, and Village Financial Section head.

Leadership

Leadership is often associated with the position or attitude of a person who can influence and focus others to achieve maximum results from specific goals. The success of a superior Village head is measured by the results achieved and the fulfillment of the goals of the vision and objectives formalized in the Village RPJM deed for 6 years or during the era of the position of the elected Village head, and to achieve the success of that goal, the Village head must play a clear role in focusing his apparatus in carrying out and completing the obligations and responsibilities of each. The results of monitoring and questioning in this research prove that in the application of his duties, the head of Bube Village practices modern management principles to the rules of governance in Bube Village, such as; deciding on the activity of assessing the ability of the Village officers at least once a month to measure and calculate the expertise of his officers in completing their obligations and responsibilities, and practicing obedience to duration and attitude.

Ability

In principle, the application of modern management to the base of people's energy (HRM) is assisted by the clarity of the participating parts or bodies (listed citizens) and the conclusion of the limits of authority, roles, and responsibilities of each part in a real and strong

way. Therefore, modern management cannot be observed as a purely technical method—reliable needs to have technical advantages and be able to cooperate with other bodies. Therefore, if they have good actions, insights, and skills, they can be said to be reliable. In modern management applications, all energy-based people have a great activity ethic, logical actions, analytical and analytical assumptions, respect for duration, cooperation, proactivity, and data figures.

Good insight, insight into the technical tasks to be acquired, as well as leadership skills, must also have technical and administrative skills or expertise, listed management skills, allocation of energy bases, appropriate control, and the use of warm interpersonal ties, without neglecting the goal of achieving the management objectives of the Village Government. A local government body requires the existence of apparatus or local features that have expertise in ties with the profession as a result of creating a maximum. Based on the opinion above, activity expertise is the capacity of people to perform various obligations in a special profession. Based on the monitoring in the square of each Village officer in charge of the Village Government, it has been better than last year, but the expertise of bube Village officers does not mean anything for a profession, if it is not supported by a sense of responsibility and expertise in completing its duties is an illustration that currently the bube Village office lacks facilities in the form of a pc, printer, activity table, and a small activity room.

Employee Discipline

Order is a significant management in people's life factors, and obedience has a relationship with self-regulation (Self-control) which is part of the person's obedience is a condition created using a series of attitudes describing the number of obedience to a provision. By the previous review, it can be concluded that the discipline of employees and the responsibility of Village officials in the implementation of their obligations and uses are lacking, starting from the effectiveness of office hours which should be 07:30 to 16: 00 but in fact on activity days sometimes it is not open and sometimes it is not until 4 pm has closed, want to but if there is a profession pressing Village officers without being obliged to force them to be on duty late into the night especially entering activities on Saturdays and Sundays, but for some Village officers it is very far from being obedient especially responsible with their obligations and functions.

Cooperation

As explained earlier, it can be concluded that cooperation is the willingness to work together with others in a way that is totality and becomes part of a group in dismantling a case, it can also be interpreted those similar activities are activities carried out by each body and have positions and responsibilities that are similar in size and are all tasked with achieving one goal. Observations and questions and answers carried out by researchers to officers at the Bube Village office in reviewing similar activities, if each Village officer has a profession that differs from one another, and is always available to help as long as there is a duration in completing the obligation even though it is not his obligation but helps the power and mind to complete the obligation but, when the officer responsible for the profession is not

located in the office for the duration let alone absent from activities as a result this management greatly affects the way the profession is handled.

4. Discussion

Work Result

Based on the results of interviews with 4 research informants, it can be seen that the results of the work of village officials through the performance assessment of the Bube village apparatus are reported at the end of each month.

According to Mr. AH's statement regarding the work of the village apparatus, namely;

"In managing the administration of the village apparatus, especially the head of affairs (Kaur) and the head of the Section (Kasie) using the application to facilitate the completion of administrative reports, both financial reports, village assets or population, and at the end of each month I as the leader in this office, hold a coordination meeting related to evaluating the performance and work results of my apparatus, and in fact some village officials do not carry out their duties and responsibilities so that as a leader I have to act decisively several times so that the management and completion of the administration is even better."

The next resource person, Mrs. MB, as the village secretary, stated the results of the performance of the village apparatus, namely:

"The village apparatus consists of 8 (eight) people, including the Village Head, Village Secretary, Village Head 1, Village Head 2, Village Government Section, Planning Section, Welfare Section, and Village Financial Section. The ability of the Bube Village Government is lacking, among others, regarding the orderliness of the Village apparatus, some of the Village apparatus that do not often enter activities can be observed from activities in the Village office can be counted how many people show up, often some do not show up at the Village office not only orderliness, such as the handling of obligations is not good, such as the obligation to collect Village profile data that has not been worked on until now".

According to the statement of the Head of Finance

"DK (financial head) the results of the activities of the Village officers the lack of upgrading of the nursery shared by the Village officers related to the use of applications related to the Village financial system and the village legacy management system in the implementation of the siskeudes and sipades applications still often occur trouble and error systems that often make the apparatus have to be extra careful not to mention the limited knowledge and understanding of the bube village apparatus in operating the application in addition they also have not received training or technical guidance on procedures or techniques in managing finances and assets. still not optimal, this affair is influenced by the limited knowledge and understanding of the bube village apparatus in operating the application. "It is still not optimal, this matter is influenced by the lack of knowledge in carrying out each tupoksi and overlapping jobs, such as work that should be done by the Head of Welfare is done by the Head of Government so that their work is neglected, as well as the lack of a sense of responsibility from each of our village officials."

In contrast, Mrs. NB (head of planning) stated that:

"The work of some officials is hampered because of the lack of facilities in the office to support the work to be completed more quickly." And one of them is influenced by the lack of knowledge in carrying out each tupoksi and overlapping jobs, such as work that should be done by the head

of Kasie Kesra is done by the head of the government so that the work itself is neglected, as well as the lack of a sense of responsibility of each of our village officials."

The results of the interview show that in the implementation of tasks and by village officials there is still very little management due to the lack of ability. Sense of responsibility for tasks and also the lack of facilities and infrastructure at the bube village office is a separate obstacle from the apparatus so the output produced is very little and not on time in submitting reports from the results of their work.

Discipline

The results of interviews with each research informant can be found out that regarding the discipline of village officials through the implementation of performance appraisals of Bube village officials.

According to Mr. AH as the head of bube village with the question

"What is the level of discipline of the apparatus in carrying out tasks in the office?"

According to Mr. AH that:

"the discipline of the apparatus in carrying out tasks is considered ineffective due to the lack of a sense of responsibility for their work".

The same matter with the delivery of Mrs. MB as the mother (village secretary), she stated that:

"the discipline of the apparatus is less than the maximum in fulfilling the responsibilities of their work".

And according to Mrs. DK as (head of finance) that;

"the level of discipline of the apparatus needs to be improved both in the punctuality of entering and leaving work or completing work".

Furthermore, according to NB as (head of planning) that:

"It is necessary to evaluate performance every month in order to determine the best steps to maximize the level of discipline of village officials". (Interview October 2, 2021).

The results show that the discipline of the apparatus in carrying out their duties is assessed that employees must gain additional knowledge regarding the implementation of the obligations and responsibilities of each apparatus through technical guidance activities or capacity building training for village officials.

Leadership

Interviews conducted with informants regarding leadership were conducted to obtain information about the ability of a leader within the scope of village government to realize good governance.

According to Mr. AH the head of Bube Village with the question of how the leadership pattern is carried out in the Bube Village office environment, he explained:

"I as the village head fully entrust employees to carry out work by their responsibilities, as a leader I motivate village officials with a variety of strategies so that they are more enthusiastic in doing and completing their work, forms of motivation or strategies that I apply to them such as; giving compensation that is appropriate and balanced and making a good cooperation system, such as helping each other in completing work if the person concerned is sick or dealing and cannot be present at the office."

According to Mrs. MB (village secretary), she stated that:

"Overall, the village government is led by the village head, and as our leader, so far he has tried to run it well, and in the scope of administration I as the village secretary have the responsibility of carrying out and ensuring that village officials fulfill and comply with the policies and orders of the village head."

According to Mrs. DK (head of finance) that;

"The form of encouragement that is very often shown by superiors is to give appreciation or rewards to subordinates who prove more expertise, as a result, we subordinates can do a good job and feel happy with all the obligations they carry.

Next, for NB (head of planning), it's like this:

"For me, our Village Head is a democratic directive person whose ability to influence others to want to collaborate to achieve the goals that have been formalized with the method of various activities that will be tried to be determined together between the directive and subordinates and not only that, the village head also likes to provide assessments and bonuses at the end of the year for village officials who have completed their activity reports on time. Based on the conclusion of the interview above, it shows that in carrying out leadership tasks, the leadership of the Bube village head is seen to have tried to lead well, and as a leader he always motivates his subordinates and also likes to give assessments and bonuses at the end of the year to village officials who have completed activity reports on time.

Factors inhibiting the application of modern management to the performance of Bube village officials

1) Ability

The results of interviews conducted with informants with questions, namely:

"What is the level of expertise of Village officials in performing their obligations and functions?"

Bube Village Head AH, he explained that:

"Indeed, for the past few years, the quality of work or performance of the apparatus has not been maximized, not only because they are inexperienced, but they also have not received training or technical guidance on procedures or techniques in managing administration, both in the field of government administration and the field of development, but recently with the technical guidance on increasing the capacity of village officials, alhamdulillah now village officials are at least able to manage their respective activities, and especially the quality of performance is not good, because there are many shortcomings, especially in actions that always delay work, so that it is often late in the process of completion."

According to the MB Village Secretary that:

"As long as I have been the village secretary, I have understood, if there are also some things that we do not understand, we can ask the village facilitator, and regarding our abilities, alhamdulillah some of our officials are capable and have very good work quality, as evidenced by several documents that were completed and reported earlier than other villages in Suwawa sub-district."

Then the Head of Planning NB said that:

"If it is a question of aspects I have understood, but I am still constrained by my skills in operating Microsoft Office applications, and for that I am still often assisted and guided by our secretary."

The same question was answered by the Head of DK Finance, who explained that

"As for the ability of each village apparatus in working in the village government, for me it has been better than in previous years, at least for this year we have understood and understood each other's main tasks and functions, but the ability here will also mean nothing for a job, if it is not supported by a sense of responsibility and willingness to complete it, there are indeed several obstacles that we feel when trying to fulfill these responsibilities, for example right now we lack facilities in the form of computers, printers, work desks, and narrow workspaces."

He continued that:

From some of the statements above, the description skills, and expertise of some village officials are lacking, both in the orderly administration of the village and skills in using facilities such as computers. (Interview October 2, 2021).

2) Employee Discipline

By observations and interviews with the Head of Bube AH Village, and other informants with questions, namely:

"One form of assessing the performance of village officials that contains modern management principles is discipline, do village officials work with actions and obedient attitudes in the application of their obligations and responsibilities so far?",

he explained that:

"If judged in terms of discipline, the ability of the village apparatus is very lacking, starting from the success of office hours which should be 07.30 to 16:00 but the reality on activity days sometimes not open and sometimes not until 4 pm has closed, but if there is urgent work the village apparatus without having to be urged they will work overtime until the night and even come to work on Saturdays and Sundays, but for some village officials it is very far from the word discipline let alone being responsible for their duties and functions."

According to Mrs. MB (village secretary), she stated that:

"I still have difficulty in coordinating village officials, as a form of my responsibility to the village head, I can only tighten the schedule for completing work, especially reports on activities that have been carried out so that at the time of the inspection schedule by the inspectorate auditor all reports have been completed."

According to Mrs. DK as (head of finance) that;

"As a financial head who is responsible for paying, and making financial reports, I am very difficult to complete quickly, because it is constrained by the implementers of activities who are often not at the office on time, and some are absent from work."

Furthermore, according to NB as (head of planning) that:

"In carrying out the profession, sometimes we can complete the profession according to the duration, related to the submitted profession. sometimes there is a profession that wants a duration of 2 days or 3 days so it cannot be over in 1 day, sometimes there is through duration, related to the submitted profession "

The results of the interview above can conclude that the form of modern management in the management of the Bube village government has not been fully implemented by some village officials in the management of village government. This matter is seen in the statement of the village head, where the discipline and responsibility of village officials in carrying out their duties and functions are still lacking, thus affecting the value of the performance achievements of some village officials.

3) Cooperation

In interviews with informants, namely how cooperation between Bube village officials in carrying out and completing their duties and responsibilities, Mr. AH, he explained:

"Relationships between village officials must be established In carrying out work, sometimes we can handle work that takes a long time, adrift with the work submitted. often there is work that takes 2 days or 3 days so it cannot be completed in 1 day, often there is a long pass, adrift with the work submitted, it's just that some village officials who are not responsible for their work often come late, and some do not enter the office".

According to Mrs. MB (village secretary), she stated that:

"Until now, I have not only coordinated the activities and work of our officials, but also helped in their completion, because they have just attended technical guidance on the implementation of their respective duties and functions, so they are still in the process of learning both administratively and technically."

According to Mrs. DK (head of finance);

"As long as there is a duration of availability to help and our obligations have ended, even though it is not my obligation if it is needed, we are ready to help, but sometimes those who are helped are not located in the office."

According to NB (head of planning) that:

"Each officer has their duties and functions but other features may want our power and mind to be available to help".

The results of the question and answer above can be concluded that each Village officer has a different profession from one another, but Village officers can carry out good cooperation, but the aspect of managing abilities related to cooperation is, when the officer responsible for the work is not in the office on time, even absent from work so that this matter greatly affects the process of completing work.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the research conducted in the matter of analyzing the ability of village officials based on modern management at the Bube Village Office, Suwawa District, Bone-Bolango Regency, the following conclusions can be drawn

1. The performance of village officials in the Bube village office has not been maximized because some village officials are not disciplined in terms of time, both in terms of attendance, as well as timeliness in completing tasks and responsibilities, but with the existence of a firm leadership spirit by the village head and guidance carried out by the village secretary in handling delays in the work of village officials, as well as cooperation carried out by several village officials in helping complete the work of other officials so that these jobs can be completed simultaneously. Improved performance of village officials is also influenced by several modern management principles related to performance evaluation conducted by the village head at the end of the month is a form of application of the government management function itself, where the goal is to obtain better results by making improvements and improving performance, thus the ability of village officials will increase.

2. Factors inhibiting the performance of village officials

a. Ability

The way of handling obligations by some Bube Village officers is less efficient and efficient, a kind of lack of energy base of people from the village apparatus so the aspect of expertise in handling the obligations and responsibilities of each village apparatus.

b. Employee Discipline

The form of modern management in the management of bube village government has not been fully implemented by some village officials in the management of village government. This matter is influenced by the discipline and responsibility of village officials in the implementation of their duties and functions which are still lacking, thus affecting the value of the performance achievements of some village officials.

c. Cooperation

Village officials are able to establish good cooperation, but what is a factor inhibiting performance related to cooperation is when the apparatus responsible for the work is not in the office on time, even absent from work so that this matter greatly affects the completion process.

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Influence of Teacher Certification Benefits and Discipline Toward Teacher Performance in Elementary Schools of Gorontalo City

Ningsih Amuja¹, Azis Rachman², Imam Mashudi^{3*}

¹Gorontalo City Education Office

^{2,3}Bina Mandiri Gorontalo University, Indonesia

e-mail: imam.mashudi@ubmg.ac.id*

Abstract

The research aims to investigate the influence of teacher certification benefits towards teacher performance in elementary schools of Gorontalo City, the influence of discipline towards teacher performance in elementary schools of Gorontalo City, and the influence of teacher certification benefits and discipline teacher performance in elementary schools of Gorontalo City. This research uses a quantitative method with a descriptive approach, revealing one variable's influence on another. The population in this research are teachers receiving certification at the Elementary School of Gorontalo City, consisting of 523 people, while the sample was 130 people. Data is collected through the distribution of questionnaires. The findings reveal that the independent variables obtained information that the teacher's certification benefits (X1) have an influence toward performance (Y) of 0.2452 or 24.52% and discipline (X2) has an influence toward teacher performance (Y) of 0.2072 or 20.72%. Simultaneously (X1) and (X2) have an influence toward (Y) of 45.24%. This research concludes that teacher certification benefits and discipline partially and simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance in elementary schools in Gorontalo City. With the evidence that certification and discipline can improve teacher performance significantly, it is suggested (1) that the Gorontalo City Education Office is more intense in socializing and overseeing the implementation of teacher professional allowance criteria. (2) The school implements a teacher attendance system using fingerprints to obtain authentic data regarding attendance. (3) Teachers can improve the implementation of their duties as educators.

Keywords: Performance, Certification benefits, and Discipline.

Introduction

High-quality education is an integral concept encompassing diverse aspects to ensure that the education provided not only imparts knowledge but also shapes the character, skills, and values necessary for leading a meaningful life. The relevance of quality education to SDGs' fourth goal (Quality Education) is key to achieving overall sustainable development objectives. Quality education can contribute to realizing other SDG goals, such as reducing poverty, narrowing inequalities, and improving health and well-being.

Table 1: Quality Achievement in Literacy Aspect

	% Students in education units		Bobot	Index	
proficient	4.44%	0.04	3	0.133	2,10 - 3.00
capably	51.11%	0.51	2	1.02	1,80 - 2.09
Basic	35.56%	0.36	1.5	0.53	1,40 - 1,79
PIK	8.89%	0.09	1	0.09	1,00 - 1,39
	1.00	1.00		1.78	under minimum competence

Source: Education Office of Gorontalo City

The teacher is an important executor of learning because the teacher's will be directly related to students. about Teachers and Lecturers, states "Teachers are professional educators who have the main obligations of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, and assessing students in the early childhood learning process in official learning channels, basic learning, as well as intermediate learning (*Undang-Undang RI No. 14 Tentang Guru Dan Dosen*, 2005). 1.00 1.00 1.78 Below minimum competency. Reliable teachers must have a minimum academic qualification of expert, be competent, physically and mentally healthy, and have expertise in creating learning goals nationally. For teachers to be able to carry out their duties well, performance must be improved. teacher performance comes from the word job performance or actual performance (the results of activities achieved by a person). So according to the language ability can be meant as a visible result as a form of successful activity in a person.

However, if you look closely, there are still many teachers who have abandoned efforts to improve their performance. This matter applies to elementary school teachers in the City of Gorontalo. The problems that occur in the City of Gorontalo :(1) the lack of teacher seminar activities regarding the curriculum because each teacher can only conduct seminars every year; (2) the limited infrastructure tools cause teachers to be less competent in studying learning; (3) Government Regulation No. 53 Regarding Discipline not implemented; (4) some

teachers have not been able to carry out the programming process; (5) teacher professionalism is still lacking in the learning process; and (6) there is an assumption that the teacher's work is only a means of earning income, the less than the optimal ability of teachers can be seen in the results of the 2021 National Assessment as follows:

Table 2: Quality Achievement in Numeracy aspects

	% Students in education units		Bobot	Index	
proficient	0%	0.000	3	0	2,10 - 3.00
capably	33.33%	0.333	2	0.67	1,80 - 2.09
Basic	62.22%	0.622	1.5	0.93	1,40 - 1,79
PIK	4.44%	0.044	1	0.04	1,00 - 1,39
	1.00	1.00		1.64	under minimum competence

Source: Education Office of Gorontalo City

The achievement of the assessment results for literacy and numeracy is still very low at the minimum competency, this shows that teacher performance still needs to be improved. Various aspects affect teachers' abilities, one of which is teacher certification assistance. Derived from the government's goal of creating a national learning system in the maximum way, it requires teachers to have good competence and professionalism. This is also stated in Law No. 20/2003 concerning the National Education System article 39 part 2, RI Law No. 14/2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, and PP RI No. 19/2005 concerning National Education Standards which underwent the last transformation to become PP RI No. 57/2005. 2021. Based on this regulation, the teaching staff must have minimum expert learning qualifications and obtain a professional teaching certificate. These 2 indicators, especially professional certificates, are an important perspective in measuring the level of readiness and professionalism of a teacher. The presence of a teacher, especially a teacher contributes to improving the quality of learning. This will happen when teachers have good quality, are prosperous, dignified, and reliable.

As a form of appreciation and appreciation, the government provides a special budget to teachers who meet the requirements of being professional teachers. The appreciation is certification assistance. Certification or professional assistance is one type of income that is given to teachers who already have a teaching certificate.

According to the information obtained from the manager of the teacher certification fund, namely the personnel development sector of the Gorontalo City Education Office, the data above all receive certification benefits, because they can administratively fulfill the requirements in eligibility to receive these allowances. Meanwhile, in reality, it is assumed that not all of the recipients of certification have met the performance standards, as the results

of an interview with (A; Principal of SDN 60 Kota Gorontalo) informed that the professional allowance will still be received because remembering that the Principal does not want problems with the recipient and does not even want to be considered by the Principal too harshly, The point is that professional allowances have not had a positive impact on performance and discipline results, and he suggests that there can be teacher transfers taking into account the zoning of residence. This statement was reinforced by (D.H; Principal of SDN 82 Kota Gorontalo) that in terms of giving grades, conflicts often occur when there are teachers who are not qualified to object and want the principal to give good grades. To avoid conflicts, sometimes the school principal immediately gives good grades to all certification recipients (assessment is still subjective).

Various attempts have been made to overcome the above problems, especially in improving discipline, including through the school principal's supervision program, especially teaching attendance in class. This responsibility is generally the principal's role as a top leader, although each individual has a role. Efforts to improve discipline can be carried out by the school through 1) supervising work rules for teachers, 2) strict application of discipline and imposing sanctions, 3) exemplary discipline in attitude, and 4) providing facilities to support teacher discipline (Tatoe, 2019). However, the problem of discipline is still a problem that is difficult to resolve, the statement (A. Principal of SDN 60 Kota Gorontalo) informs recipients that they are often late for the reason that they live far away so the impact of being late learning services and the community is often highlighted, furthermore from D.H. Principal of SDN 82 Information was obtained from the City of Gorontalo that the recapitulation of monthly attendance reached 85%, meaning that 15% of teachers were absent due to illness and a little undisciplined.

Teacher discipline data from observations at schools include; SDN 41 Hulonthalangi, City of Gorontalo, the number of teachers is 29 people. From the attendance list in 1 month, it can be seen that 18 people are often late, or around 62%, 24 people often do not fill in the morning and evening attendance list, or around 82%, and go home early, 18 people go home quickly; SDN 91 Sipatana, City of Gorontalo, the number of teachers is 11 people, it can be seen that they were listed as attending in June 2022, the percentage of teachers who often asked for permission was around 9.09%, they were sick 2% and for SDN 60 Kota Timur Kota Gorontalo, it was seen that 100% attendance was confirmed. no absences appear to be late and or negligent, according to the statement of the school principal that since there is no longer any enforcement of monthly reports, the attendance list is recapitulated later during the certification filing. This is in line with the statement by the headmaster of SDN 59 Kota Timur that the teacher attendance list was not questioned during school accreditation, so it seemed as if it had gone unnoticed except for the fulfillment of the certification documents.

In addition to time discipline, in reality in the field there are still many teachers who receive certification benefits but have not fully demonstrated administrative discipline, the narrative from (D.H. Principal of SDN 82 Gorontalo City) that teacher performance is measured by making learning tools starting with program planning, learning processes and evaluation, in general, all fulfilled, but there are some teachers who in one indicator are considered less like in the learning process, this is due to the non-linear basic of education, for example, the Physical Education teacher (PJOK) is certified as a class teacher, and a religion teacher is also

a certified class teacher. The second cause is the lack of IT Presidency that the learning process becomes hampered.

Methods

This research is used quantitative research. Quantitative research is a research methodology built on a positivist philosophy to study populations or specific examples, use research tools to collect data, and analyze quantitative or statistical information to measure assumptions made (Sugiyono, 2017) . The research was conducted at Elementary Schools in the City of Gorontalo.

The population obtained in this research is all elementary school teachers who receive certification benefits in the City of Gorontalo. For 2022 there are 523 people. While the sample in this research was 130 people. The sample is representative of the population being monitored. If the total population is not more than 100 people, all samples must be used, but if the total population exceeds 100 people, the sample collection can be 10 to 15% or 20 to 25% of the entire population (Arikunto, 2016). Looking at the overall population of this research, there are 523 people so the sample collection is 25%. The techniques of collecting data in this research used observation, questionnaires, and documentation.

Results

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	1979.20	2	989.60	52.391	.000 ^b
Residual	0		0		
Total	2398.86	127	18.889		
	9				
	4378.06	129			
	9				

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Discipline, Teacher Certification Benefits

The results of the F-count experiment obtained a F-count of 52.391 greater than a F-table of 3.07 and a degree of significance of 0.000. Based on the F experiment it proved a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variables Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
1 (Constant)	5.427	5.922		.916	.361
Teacher Certification Benefits	.471	.078	.428	6.021	.000
Discipline	1.738	.324	.381	5.358	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Performance

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 6.021 which is greater than the table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment, it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variable Teacher Certification benefits

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 5.358 which is greater than the t-table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the Discipline variable (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance

Hypothesis Testing

a. Influence of Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously has a positive and significant influence on performance (Y)

The results of the F-count experiment obtained a F-count of 52.391 greater than a F-table of 3.07 and a degree of significance of 0.000. Based on the F experiment it proved a significance level of $0.000 \leq 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variables Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance.

This means that the reported assumption that Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is accepted.

b. Teacher Certification benefits (X1) Partially Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Teacher Performance (Y)

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 6.021 which is greater than the t-table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment, it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the variable Teacher Certification benefits

(X1) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance.

This means that the reported assumption that the Teacher Certification benefits (X1) partially have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is accepted.

c. Discipline (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Y)

The experimental results obtained by t-count is 5.358 which is greater than the t-table of 1.656, and the degree of importance is 0.000. Based on the t experiment it proves that the significance level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the Discipline variable (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. This means that the assumption that reports that Discipline (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are accepted.

Discussion

1. The simultaneous influence of teacher certification benefits and discipline on teacher performance

Respondents' assumptions about teacher performance variables, in general, are very high, it seems that respondents who respond very highly are able to organize learning concepts well. Respondents who responded very high to be able to do well in learning. Respondents who responded very high to be able to calculate the results of the student or student practice. Respondents who responded very highly were able to follow up on the results of evaluating the results of a student or student practice. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the basic goals of education well. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the learning procedure well. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the level of progress of students well. Respondents responded very highly to mastering the appropriate learning approach to the upgrading module. Respondents responded very highly to practicing cooperation in the profession well. Respondents responded very highly to the use of science and technology developments in learning. Respondents responded very highly to understanding the knowledge and skills according to the upgrading module. Respondents who responded very highly to improve their work well.

The results of the regression calculation between certification and discipline allowance variables and performance variables prove that teacher certification assistance and discipline simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance. This means that the reported assumption that teacher certification benefits and discipline simultaneously have a positive and meaningful impact on the performance of teachers in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is accepted.

The research results match the results of research conducted, stated that there was an important influence of professional allowances and the discipline of teacher activities together on teacher performance (Elien et al., 2020). stated that certification assistance and work discipline affect teacher performance (Nurjannah et al., 2021).

2. Partial influence of teacher certification benefits on teacher performance (Y)

Respondents' assumptions on the teacher certification benefits variable in general, respondents reported as very high. Teacher Certification benefits (X1) Respondents who responded to the amount of certification assistance according to the last level of education, were in the very high category. Respondents responded that teachers who receive certification

benefits must attend competency and certification education and training, which are in the very high category. Respondents who responded to teachers who received certification benefits were viewed based on the length of time being a teacher, which was in the high category. Respondents who respond to teachers who receive certification benefits must have the expertise to organize learning implementation plans (RPP) in an analytical way which is in the Very High category. Respondents who responded that teachers received certification benefits were based on evaluations from leaders and supervisors while in class and in the school area which were in the very high category. Respondents who responded that teachers receiving certification benefits needed to have expertise in improving their quality as teaching staff in the very high category. Respondents who responded that teachers receiving certification benefits needed to explore objective forum activities in the high category. Respondents who responded to teachers who received certification benefits were observed to be based on results and appreciation that were relevant to their academic aspects which were in the high category.

The results of the regression calculation between the certification benefits variable and the teacher performance variable prove that the teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and significant impact on teacher achievement. This means that the assumption that reports that teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are accepted.

This is in line with the study of (Elien et al., 2020) stating that there is a significant impact of professional allowances on teacher performance. Teacher certification has no influence on teacher performance (Bister, 2016). teacher certification benefits can partially explain performance (Noer, 2018). stated that certification benefits do not affect teacher performance (Nurjannah et al., 2021).

3. The influence of discipline partially on teacher performance (Y)

Respondents' assumptions on disciplinary factors, in general, are really big. Respondents reported teacher discipline to school rules in the very high category.

Respondents who responded to the accuracy of the teacher's duration in the school area were in the very high section. Respondents who responded to understanding the teacher in carrying out his duties lie in a very high type. Respondents who responded that teachers are required to have a responsibility in carrying out their duties are in the very high category.

The results of the regression calculation between the disciplinary variable and the teacher performance variable prove that the disciplinary variable partially has a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance. This means that the assumption that reports that discipline partially has a positive and meaningful influence on the performance of teachers in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are accepted.

This is in line with the opinions of stating that there are important consequences of teacher work discipline on teacher performance (Elien et al., 2020). Work discipline has a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance (Bister, 2016). Work discipline

affects teacher performance, state that works discipline has a positive and meaningful influence on teacher achievement (Wiwin & Mukhtar, 2018)

Employee discipline is a form of training that seeks to justify and create insights, actions, and behavior of employees so that employees sincerely try to work cooperatively with other employees and improve their work results.

If discipline is the description and desire of a person to comply with all company regulations and legitimate social norms (Hasibuan, 2019). The explanation is the activity of someone who honestly obeys the rules and remembers the roles and responsibilities. So, he will obey or carry out all his duties properly, not on impulse. Desire is an action, behavior, and behavior of a person in accordance with company regulations, whether registered or not. From this explanation, it appears that discipline must be upheld in an institution. Without the support of good employee discipline, it is difficult for the institution to achieve its goals so that employee discipline is one of the keys to the success of an institution or industry in achieving its goals

Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the results of the data processing carried out, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Teacher certification benefits and discipline simultaneously (together) have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance. Respondents' responses to the questionnaire variables X1 and X2 were in the very high and high categories. SPSS analysis shows that the Fcount value is 52.391 which is greater than the Ftable of 3.07 and has a significant level of 0.000. Based on the F test, it shows a significant level of $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, the statistical variables Teacher Certification benefits (X1) and Discipline (X2) simultaneously (together) have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (ANOVA). This means that the assumption that reports that teacher certification benefits and discipline simultaneously have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City are **Accepted**.
2. The teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and meaningful influence on teacher performance. Respondents' responses to the Certification benefits variable questionnaire were in the very high and high categories. SPSS analysis It can be seen that the results of the t-count test are 6.021, which is greater than the t-table of 1.656 and has a significant level of 0.000. Based on the t-test shows that the significant level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, the statistical variable Teacher Certification benefits (X1) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Coefficients). This means that the reported assumption that teacher certification benefits partially have a positive and significant impact on teacher performance (Y) in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is **Accepted**.

3. Discipline variables in a partial way have a positive and meaningful impact on teacher performance. Respondents' responses to the Discipline variable questionnaire were in the very high and high categories. SPSS analysis results obtained a tcount of 5.358 greater than the ttable of 1.656, and a significant level of 0.000. Based on the t-test shows that the significant level is $0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that at the 95% confidence level, statistically the Discipline variable (X2) partially has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance (Coefficients). This means that the reported assumption that discipline partially has a positive and significant influence on the performance of teachers in Elementary Schools in Gorontalo City is **Accepted**.

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The Influence of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction at Kurenai Beach Tourism

Yohanes Languyu¹ Sudarsono^{2*} Frista Iin Wahyuni³ Sitti Husna Noviana Djou⁴, and Nur Rizky Putri Mahadi⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Bina Mandiri University Gorontalo

*Email: sudarsono@ubmg.ac.id

Abstract

This study aims to determine the effect of service quality on visitor satisfaction at Kurenai Beach Tourism. This study aims to determine whether the effect of service quality on visitor satisfaction is seen from the quality of the product and the quality of service provided by Kurenai Beach tourism officers. This type of research uses a quantitative approach. The type of data used is primary data obtained through observations / observations on the working time of workers at Kurenai Beach tourism and secondary data obtained from data on the number of visitors at Kurenai Beach tourist attraction.

The results showed that visitor satisfaction was more influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables shows there is significance.

Keywords: Service Quality, Visitor Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Tourism is a very reliable field because it can provide and increase regional income. This is evident from the increasing number of new tourist attractions that have sprung up both in terms of relatively affordable prices, to moderate and even at quite expensive rates.

Indonesia is a country with many islands and a tropical climate, where there are tons of attractions ranging from nature tourism, playgrounds and many more. But to support the tourism sector, it takes elements that are closely related in terms of helping the growth and progress of the tourism world.

The development of the business world is now increasingly dynamic along with the increasing public demand for products and services to meet all their needs. In order to maintain business continuity in the midst of highly competitive business competition, a company must provide customer satisfaction by talking outside the main tasks and functions, playing cell phones or watching TV.

The development of economic activities always has an influence on the marketing aspect. Company management is required to have the right marketing concept in order to always be able to overcome competition in the business world. In general, every company adheres to a consumer-oriented marketing system, namely a marketing system that always strives to meet the needs and desires of consumers. In its development, the tourism sector plays an important role in supporting the growth of the national economy because its existence can contribute to the country's foreign exchange earnings, expand employment opportunities, and introduce national culture so that it should be developed.

The focus on building relationship with customers rather than just focusing on transactions is changing how businesses interact with their customers. The number of available choices to customers has grown in recent years. In order to increase the value of the customer asset over time, customer relationship management places an emphasis on two-way communication between suppliers and customers.

Two (2) main factors affect service quality, namely expected service and perceived service. If the service received (perceived service) is in accordance with what consumers expect (expected service), then the quality of the service concerned will be considered good. If the service received (perceived service) exceeds the expected service, then the service quality is perceived as ideal quality. Conversely, if the service received (perceived service) is worse than the expected service, then the service quality is perceived as poor. Tourism objects are service products offered by a service company with the hope that consumers will come to visit and enjoy the tourist objects offered. To be able to attract customer satisfaction, managers must be able to provide the best quality of service to create customer satisfaction [5].

Of the many tourist attractions in Gorontalo, one of the favorite destinations for families is the beach. In Botubarani, precisely in Kabila Bone sub-district, Bone Bolango district, Gorontalo province, there is one of the family's favorite recreational spots, Kurenai beach. Based on observations made by researchers related to the problems in this study, namely, the current conditions at Kurenai Beach tourism are still not in accordance with what visitors expect because there are still some visitors who feel less satisfied with the services at Kurenai beach, the cleanliness of the beach is not maintained causing there is still garbage scattered around the beach area and the lack of supporting facilities such as bathrooms and toilets.

Definition of Human Resources Management

Human resources management is a series of organizational activities directed at attracting, developing, and retaining an effective workforce. In addition) Human Resource Management (HRM) is: "The activities of planning, procuring, developing, maintaining, and using human resources to achieve both individual and organizational goals." [4]

Human resource management is "the science and art of managing the relationship and role of labor so that it effectively and efficiently helps realize the goals of the company, employees, and society" [6]. Human Resource Management (HRM) is: "The process of managing people, through planning, recruitment, selection, training, development, compensation, career, safety and health and maintaining industrial relations until termination of employment in order to achieve company goals and improve stakeholder welfare." [7].

"Human resource management, abbreviated as HRM, is a science or a way of how to manage the relationship and role of resources (labor) owned by individuals efficiently and effectively and can be used optimally so that the common goals of the company, employees and society are maximized."

1) Functions of Human Resource Management

The functions of human resource management are as follows:

1. Managerial function

a) Planning (planning)

Planning is the process of determining goals and guidelines for implementation by choosing the best of the available alternatives. Planning in the HRM process is the recruitment of the workforce needed by the company.

b) Organizing

Organizing is defined as a process of determining, grouping, and arranging the various activities needed to achieve goals. Organizing can be done by placing employees according to their areas of expertise and providing the tools needed by employees to support their work.

c) Supervision (controlling)

Supervision (controlling)

Supervision is the process of regulating various factors in the company so that they are in accordance with the accuracy of the plan. Supervision is defined as the process of monitoring activities; the aim is to determine the expectations that will be achieved and to correct deviations that occur. The expectations in question are the goals that have been set to be achieved and the programs that have been planned to be carried out within a certain period. The main purpose of supervision is to try to make what is planned come true. With thorough supervision, it will be easier for an agency to analyze the obstacles that arise in management. Thus, the solution to the problems that arise will be taken wisely.

d) Motivation

Motivation is a characteristic of human psychology that contributes to a person's level of commitment. Motivation includes factors that cause, channel, and maintain human behavior in the direction of a certain determination. Motivation can also be interpreted as providing driving force that creates work enthusiasm for someone to want to work together, work effectively and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. Basically, companies not only expect capable, capable, and skilled employees, but most importantly they want to work hard and want to achieve optimal work results.

e) Evaluation

Evaluation or also called control is a reporting system activity that is compatible with the overall reporting structure, develops standards of behavior, measures results based on desired quality in relation to goals, takes corrective action, and provides rewards. With the evaluation carried out by the company, it can measure the success rate of an organization.

2) HRM Objectives

The objectives of HRM are as follows:

- a) Determine the quality and quantity of employees who will fill all positions within the company.
 - b) Ensure the availability of present and future labor, so that every job is done.
 - c) Avoid mismanagement and overlap in the implementation of tasks.
 - d) Facilitate coordination, integration, and synchronization (KIS) so that work productivity increases.
 - e) Avoid employee shortages and excesses
 - f) To be a guideline in determining employee attraction, selection, development, compensation, integration, maintenance, discipline, and dismissal programs.
 - g) To be a guideline in carrying out mutations (vertical or horizontal).
 - h) Become the basis for employee appraisal.
- 3) Service Quality

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) service is helping to prepare (take care of) what someone needs.

According to Kotler in Hendro and Syamswana (2017) the definition of service is any action or activity that can be offered by a party to another party, which is basically intangible and does not result in any ownership.

Service quality is the whole of the features and characteristics of a product or service that support its ability to satisfy needs directly or indirectly [9]. So, service quality is an interaction between customers and employees whose results can be directly felt by customers at that time.

a) Service Quality Indicators

There are five dimensions of service that are often used to measure service quality. The five dimensions are as follows:

1. Reliability, namely the ability to provide the desired service immediately, accurately and satisfactorily. Performance must be in accordance with customer expectations which means timeliness, the same service for all customers without any errors, sympathetic attitude and high accuracy.
2. Responsiveness, namely the company's ability to help and provide fast (responsive) and precise service to customers with clear information delivery. Letting customers wait without a clear reason causes a negative perception of service quality.
3. Assurance, the existence of certainty, namely the knowledge, courtesy and ability of employees to foster customer confidence in the services provided.
4. Empathy, which is providing sincere and individual or personal attention given to customers by trying to understand consumer desires. Where a company is expected to have an understanding and knowledge of customers, understand specific customer needs, and have a convenient organizing time for customers.
5. Tangibles (physical evidence), namely the ability of a company to show its existence to external parties of the company. The appearance and ability of the company's physical facilities and infrastructure and the surrounding environment are tangible evidence of the services provided by the company.

4) Service Quality Gap

The dimensions of service quality that have been mentioned must be combined properly because if not, this can cause a gap between the company and the customer [10]. Customer-perceived quality in the service industry, identifies five gaps that cause service delivery failures, namely:

a. Management perception gap

This gap occurs due to a lack of marketing research orientation, inadequate utilization of research findings, lack of interaction between management and customers, inadequate bottom-up communication, and too many levels of management.

b. Quality specification gap Namely the gap between management's perception of service user expectations and service quality specifications. Gaps occur, among others, due to insufficient management commitment to service quality, perceptions of infeasibility, insufficient standardization of tasks, and lack of goal setting.

c. Service delivery gap

This gap is caused by the following factors:

- 1) Role ambiguity is the extent to which employees can perform tasks in accordance with manager expectations but satisfy customers,
- 2) Role conflict is the extent to which employees believe they are not satisfying all parties.
- 3) the suitability of employees with the tasks they have to do.
- 4) kesesuaian teknologi yang digunakan pegawai.
- 5) the suitability of the technology used by employees. control system from superiors, namely the inadequacy of the appraisal system and the reward system,
- 6) perceived control, namely the extent to which employees feel freedom or flexibility to determine the way of service.
- 7) team work, namely the extent to which employees and management formulate common goals in satisfying customers together and integrated.

d. Marketing communication gap

This gap occurs because:

- 1) inadequate horizontal communication.
- 2) there is a tendency to over-promise. What the company faces is if the promises made cannot be fulfilled.

e. Gaps in perceived service

Namely the difference in perceptions between services perceived and expected by customers. If both prove to be the same, the company will get a positive image and impact. However, if what is received is lower than expected, then this gap will cause problems for the company.

5) Visitor or Customer Satisfaction

Satisfaction or satisfaction from Latin "satis" (meaning good enough) and "facto" (doing or making) thus satisfaction can be interpreted as the fulfillment of something or something adequate. Meanwhile, in terms of satisfaction, satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises from comparing the perceived performance of a product (or result) against their expectations. If performance fails to meet expectations, the customer will be dissatisfied. If performance matches

expectations, the customer will be satisfied. If the performance exceeds expectations, the customer will be very satisfied or happy. Visitor satisfaction is the customer's response to the evaluation of the difference in initial expectations before purchase and the actual performance of the product or service as perceived after the service. In the context of tourism, visitor satisfaction is the result of an evaluation after someone visits a destination by comparing reality and desired expectations. Customer satisfaction is an assessment of the customer's use of goods or services based on expectations and reality [3]. Customer satisfaction is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises from comparing the product's perceived performance (or results) against their expectations.

a. Factors Affecting Visitor or Customer (traveler) Satisfaction

Five main factors that need to be considered in relation to customer satisfaction include:

- 1) Quality of Tourism Products Consumers will be satisfied if the results of their evaluation show that the products they use are of high quality. A product is said to be of quality for someone, if the product can fulfill their needs. There are two types of product quality, namely external and internal. One of the product qualities of external factors is the brand image perceived by tourists.
- 2) Quality of Tourist Services Consumers will feel satisfied if they get good service or in accordance with expectations.
- 3) Emotional Image Is the emotional state of a consumer in the form of feelings of pleasure, pride or satisfaction.
- 4) Price Products that have the same quality but set a relatively low price will provide higher value.
- 5) Cost Consumers who do not need to pay additional costs or do not need to waste time getting a product or service tend to be satisfied with the product or service. [8]

b. Indicators of Consumer Satisfaction (Tourists)

- 1) Tourist involvement in evaluating various factors that will significantly affect their satisfaction. These factors are: The hospitality of the local community (host) and the attitude of employees towards tourists. Tourist satisfaction does not only come from beautiful destinations, but also from their encounters with local communities and employees of tourism service providers. Negative host perceptions of tourists can trigger dissatisfaction and deter tourists from returning. Conversely, positive host perceptions can motivate tourists to visit the same destination in the future.
- 2) Service quality relating to politeness, friendliness, efficiency, and responsiveness of service personnel to tourist requests and complaints.
- 3) Accommodation and facilities as a significant factor affecting tourist satisfaction, both physically and psychologically.
- 4) The culture of tourism product consumption behavior is seen as a pluralistic, integrative, and multidimensional social phenomenon. One aspect of culture, such as language, can help facilitate communication between the host and guest and promote the destination as a better place to visit.

- 5) Price (monetary cost) which relates to assessing traveler satisfaction and not knowing whether other destinations' offerings can be exceptional. The performance of tourism dimensions that are rated the same as other destinations (e.g. food quality, service quality, safety, water, sports, comfort, and entertainment) can be both a threat and an opportunity for the company, in the long run, competitive ability may become difficult, unless the destination authority seeks to maintain and improve its destination performance to create clearer differentiation.
- 6) Non-monetary costs. In tourism, the perception of non-monetary costs (in addition to reasonable monetary costs), inherent in-service quality, emotional response, and reputation can extend the vacation period, and are likely to be important determinants of future behavior and intentions.

2. Methods

The research method used in this study is descriptive quantitative. Data obtained from data collection will then be analyzed univariately. Univariate analysis is used because the data contains only two variables and does not relate to cause or effect relationships. The purpose of univariate analysis is to describe the data simply to find patterns in the data. This type of research is associative research, which is research that aims to determine the effect or relationship between two or more variables. This study is to determine the effect of service quality (X) on visitor satisfaction (Y) at Kurenai Beach tourist attraction, the population and sample in this study were all visitors to Kurenai Beach tourist attraction totaling 30 people. The sample size is obtained through calculation with the following formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + (N \times e^2)}$$
$$n = \frac{310}{1 + (310 \times 10\%^2)}$$
$$= 75,61$$

So based on the above results, the sample taken for this study was 76 respondents with an error rate of 10%.

3. Results

This research was conducted from September 2022 to November 2022 Completed.

Table 4.1. Research Instrument Validation Test

Variabel	Indikator	Item	Korelasi	Kesimpulan
Kualitas Pelayanan (X)	Reliability (X.1)	X111	1.000	Valid
		X112	0.920	Valid
		X113	0.888	Valid
		X114	0.906	Valid
	Responstveness (X.2)	X121	0.892	Valid
		X122	0.956	Valid
		X123	0.941	Valid
		X124	0.941	Valid
	Assurance (X.3)	X131	1.000	Valid
		X132	0.920	Valid
		X133	0.888	Valid
		X134	0.906	Valid
	Empathy (X.4)	X141	1.000	Valid
		X142	0.920	Valid
X143		0.888	Valid	
X144		0.906	Valid	
Tangibles (X.5)	X211	0.953	Valid	
	X212	0.939	Valid	
	X213	0.926	Valid	
	X214	0.953	Valid	
Kepuasan Pengunjung (Y)	Kualitas produk (Y1)	Y11	0.920	Valid
		Y12	1.000	Valid
		Y13	0.920	Valid
		Y14	0.953	Valid
	Kualitas Pelayanan (Y2)	Y21	0.926	Valid
		Y22	0.888	
		Y23	0.920	
		Y24	0.953	
		Y25	0.888	
		Y26	0.920	
		Y27	0.920	
		Y28	0.888	
		Y29	0.927	
		Y30	0.926	
Y31	0.926			
Y32	0.920			
Y33	0.926			

Variabel	Indikator	Item	Korelasi	Kesimpulan
		Y34	0.920	
		Y35	0.923	
		Y36	0.888	
		Y37	0.926	
		Y38	1.000	
		Y39	0.920	
		Y40	0.888	
		Y41	0.926	
		Y42	0.926	
		Y43	0.888	
		Y45	0.920	
		Y46	0.888	
		Y47	0.924	
		Y48	0.920	
		Y49	1.000	
		Y50	0.888	

Source: Processed Data 2022

Table 4.1 above shows the correlation value of all question items on the questionnaire for all indicators and items is above 0.3. Thus, it can be concluded that all items have met the validity. The next stage is presented testing the reliability of the instrument. The instrument is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha value is > 0.6 . Complete results are presented in Appendix 3, and summarized in the following table.

Residuals Statistics ^a					
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	20.7279	40.5726	32.3696	7.15776	76
Residual	-1.13787	1.74958	.00000	.58139	76
Std. Predicted Value	-1.626	1.146	.000	1.000	76
Std. Residual	-1.891	2.907	.000	.966	76

The Residuals Statistics results obtained a Std Deviation value of .58139 with an N value of 76. Thus the dependent variable y or residuals meets the criteria.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		76
Normal	Mean	.0000000
Parameters ^{a,b}	Std. Deviation	.58139393
Most Extreme	Absolute Differences	.187
	Positive	.168
	Negative	-.187
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		4.269
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.080

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data.

The analysis results show that the data is normally distributed, this can be seen from the KolmogorovSmirnov test, as well as the probability number or Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.080. This means that the significance value or probability value is more than 0.05 the data distribution is normal.

Scatterplot

The Normal P-P Plot Of Regression Standardized Residual results show that the plotting points in the picture above always follow and approach the diagonal line. Therefore, as a

basis or guideline for decision making in the probability plot technique normality test, it can be concluded that the residual value is normally distributed. Thus, the normalization assumption for the residual value in the simple linear regression analysis in this study can be fulfilled.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95,0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	.856	.413		2.074	.044	.023	1.689
x1	.399	.280	.553	3.731	.001	.461	.137

a. Dependent Variable: X

From the output above, it is known that the significance value of the financing variable (X) is $0.44 > 0.05$, meaning that the significance value or probability value is more than 0.05, the data distribution is normal.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df 1	df 2	Sig. F Change	
1	.497 ^a	.593	.593	.30280	.593	1021.472	1	75	.000	1.029

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The table above explains the percentage of the influence of the independent variable or predictor variable on the dependent variable. The magnitude of the coefficient of determination is 0.593, which means that the influence of the independent variable (independent) is 59.3%. While 40.7% (100%-59.3%) is influenced by other variables. So the effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction is only 59.3% while the influence of other variables is 40.7%. Thus, it means that Visitor Satisfaction is still influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables, it shows that there is significance.

4. Discussion

Based on the results of the study, it shows that simultaneously tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy contribute significantly to visitor satisfaction with an influence of 59.7%. The form of contribution between tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy to visitor satisfaction is a positive influence indicated by the prices of the regression coefficients which are positive. Thus, it can be explained that if the variables of tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy are increased together, it will be followed by an

increase in visitor satisfaction and vice versa if the variables of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy decrease together, it will be followed by a decrease in visitor satisfaction. Partially tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy have a significant effect on visitor satisfaction and for more details will be detailed as follows:

The Effect of Tangibles (Direct Evidence) on Visitor Satisfaction. Tangibles (direct evidence) partially contributed to visitor satisfaction by 2.5%. From the research results it was revealed that 68 70.34% of respondents stated that the tangibles (direct evidence) applied by Kurenai Beach were in the good category, at Kurenai Beach they had implemented direct evidence which included, physical facilities, parking lots and the appearance of good workers so that visitors were satisfied with the facilities provided. The embodiment or physical evidence of services, equipment facilities used and other physical representations affect service user satisfaction [10]. However, the contribution caused is relatively small, namely (2.5%), even though the tangibles (direct evidence) on Kurenai Beach are good, this happens because in making visits the visitors do not always pay attention to the tangibles (direct evidence) applied by Kurenai Beach.

The Effect of Reliability on Visitor Satisfaction Reliability partially contributes to visitor satisfaction by 1.25%. From the research results it was revealed that 69.57% of respondents stated that the reliability applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category, seen from the application of reliability aspects such as the accuracy of service to visitors who need help. Kurenai Beach focuses on effective service aspects so that visitors are satisfied with the reliability that has been implemented by the manager. This is in accordance with the theory that reliability which includes two main things, namely work consistency (performance) and the ability to be trusted (dependability) important factors that affect service life [10]. However, the contribution caused is very small, namely (1.25%) even though the reliability at Kurenai Beach is good, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not always pay attention to the reliability.

The Effect of Responsiveness on Visitor Satisfaction Responsiveness partially contributes to visitor satisfaction with the greatest influence among other variables, namely 7.13%. From the research results, it was revealed that 71.39% of respondents stated that the responsiveness applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category. Kurenai Beach has implemented the responsiveness aspect well which focuses on providing services quickly and the desire of workers to help visitors if they experience problems or need help. This is in accordance with the theory which states that in service marketing there are five important variables that need to be considered in improving service quality, one of which is the responsiveness variable [10]. The main factor determining customer satisfaction is customer perception of service quality [10]. However, the contribution caused by the small relative is (7.13%) even though the responsiveness at Kurenai Beach is good, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not always pay attention to the responsiveness.

The Effect of Assurance on Visitor Satisfaction Assurance partially contributes to visitor satisfaction with an influence of 1.3%. From the research results it was revealed that 80.50% of respondents stated that the assurance applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category. This is because Kurenai Beach has implemented assurance which focuses on assurance regarding the friendliness and politeness of workers in providing services to

visitors, the safety of recreational parks which includes the safety of visitors and the security of parking lots, as well as workers' knowledge of the situation of recreational parks. This is in accordance with the theory that assurance is one aspect of service quality that affects visitor satisfaction [10].

The influence caused is relatively small, namely (1.3%) even though the assurance at Kurenai Beach is good, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not pay too much attention to the assurance aspect. The Effect of Empathy (Empathy) on Visitor Satisfaction Empathy (empathy) partially contributes to visitor satisfaction with an influence of 1.14%. From the research results, it was revealed that 69.92% of respondents stated that the empathy applied by Kurenai Beach was in the good category. In implementing the empathy aspect, Kurenai Beach focuses more on good communication with visitors so that visitors feel more respected and valued. The creation of good communication will provide information to the management so that it can understand the needs of visitors so as to create visitor satisfaction, empathy is one of the service quality variables that affect customer satisfaction [10]. In a service business, service quality plays an important role in explaining whether or not service consumers are satisfied [10]. But the effect caused is small, namely (1.14%) even though the empathy on Kurenai Beach is already in the good category, this happens because in making visits the visitors to Kurenai Beach do not pay too much attention to the empathy aspect (empathy). Meanwhile, seen from the determination test, the percentage of the influence of the independent variable or predictor variable on the dependent variable shows that the coefficient of determination is 0.593, which means that the influence of the independent variable is 59.3%. While 40.7% (100%-59.3%) is influenced by other variables. So, the effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction is only 59.3% while the influence of other variables is 40.7%. Thus, it means that Visitor Satisfaction is still influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables, it shows that there is significance.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the results of the research on the Effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction at Kurenai Beach Tourism, researchers can conclude that service quality has a significant effect on visitor loyalty at Kurenai Beach Tourism with several indicators, namely:

1) Level of service quality

The form of contribution between tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy to visitor satisfaction is a positive influence indicated by the prices of the regression coefficients which are positive. Thus, it can be explained that if the variables of tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy are increased together, it will be followed by an increase in visitor satisfaction and vice versa if the variables of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy decrease together, it will be followed by a decrease in visitor satisfaction. Partially tangibles (direct evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy have a significant effect on visitor satisfaction.

2) Level of Visitor Satisfaction

The coefficient of determination is 0.593, which means that the effect of independent variables is 59.3%. While 40.7% (100%-59.3%) is influenced by other variables. So, the effect of Service Quality on Visitor Satisfaction is only 59.3% while the influence of other variables is 40.7%. Thus, it means that Visitor Satisfaction is greater influenced by other variables. This is only natural, because judging from the magnitude of the correlation coefficient between variables, it shows that there is significance.

The mechanism of how recreation experiences lead to attitude and behavior change is a complex system involving satisfaction, knowledge, place attachment, environmental commitment, and perceived value of destinations. In terms of loyalty, satisfaction positively influences visitors' intentions to revisit, or to recommend a visit to others. Length of stay also appeared to be positively associated with visitor loyalty, which is likely mediated by satisfaction. Visitors who spend more days to stay have more time and opportunities to explore and enjoy the view of Kurenai Beach and likely have higher satisfaction.

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Training Needs Assessment of Coastal Residents of Orani: Basis for Gender-Based Extension Program

Venes A. Santiago, Crisanto P. Vallester, Lydia O. Alipio,
Pablo V. Acuna Jr., Joycelin Ramos
Bataan Peninsula State University
vasantiago@bpsu.edu.ph

Abstract

This study aimed to determine the training needs assessment of the coastal residents in the (4) four Barangay of Orani, Bataan. The research design employed in this study was the descriptive method. The researcher used a random sampling technique. The respondents of the study were the (100) one hundred coastal residents in Orani, Bataan. The data in this study were obtained using the researcher-made questionnaire intended to determine the profile and training needs of the coastal residents. Frequency, percentage, and weighted mean were the statistical tools used to determine the problems proposed. The findings revealed that the respondents wanted to have a skills and livelihood training program in their respective barangay. The majority of the training needs assessment in terms of skills and livelihood training program wished to have training on automotive technology, food processing, basic cookery, Welding, and candle making respectively. The study also revealed that the coastal residents of the selected barangay in Orani, Bataan agreed to support the programs to be conducted by the institution. It was concluded that the coastal residents need the following training based on the result and it was recommended that the institution find ways to develop and implement a viable gender-based Extension Program for the coastal residents, the personnel or extensionists should also work hand in hand in improving the service of delivery of extension services to target clientele, proper monitoring on the financial practices utilized in the project should be done periodically. An intensive monitoring and assessment should be made to meet the standards set by the government with regards to extension services operation reared the welfare of its client.

Keywords: training needs assessment, gender-based extension program, skills and livelihood training

Introduction

According to Bataan Coastal Care Foundation, Inc. (2006), about 1 million coastal residents and their families – about 5 percent of the nation's labor force – earn a living directly from fisheries of the total number of individuals who rely on fish for their livelihood, 69 percent are municipal fisherfolk, 25 percent are engaged in aquaculture, and the remaining 6 percent are involved in commercial fishing.

In many coastal communities, the majority of households depend directly on fish and other coastal resources for their livelihood. Municipal fisherfolks are among the poorest in Philippine society, with an annual average household income of Php70,000, which is about half the nation's average of Php 144,000. Other studies report even lower levels of income among fisherfolk.

Among fishing families, household sizes are generally larger than the national average, and a greater proportion of their income is spent on food. The level of education of fisherfolk household heads is lower than average. In terms of access to basic services, fisherfolk households have lower rates of access. Within the coastal zone, near-shore fisheries are the most heavily exploited. An increasing number of smaller fisher families compete with each other, as well as with commercial fishermen for fishery resources that have experienced serious declines in productivity in the last 10 to 15 years.

The national administration has already initiated livelihood programs and projects to address the issue of poverty and uplift the economic status of the Philippines. Different government agencies were required to anchor their community programs to this national thrust of the government. Livelihood programs are seen to be answers to ease the concurring incidence of poverty among families in different regions especially in coastal areas. Unfortunately, some programs of the government do not directly address the needs of the community making these programs a loss. As such, parts of this venture are Higher Education Institutions (HEI's) in the Philippines whether private or public colleges or universities that are obliged to conduct community extension programs under CHED Memorandum Order No.28 Series of 2006. This call requires all the institutions to include extensions in their school agenda. Bataan Peninsula State University, as one of the State Universities in Region III, fulfills its fourfold functions- instruction, research, extension, and production as a commitment to service to its community. The institution aside from accomplishing its main function is dedicated to creating livelihood programs embodying social responsibility.

This study is an assessment of the coastal residents of Orani to answer the training needs that are of interest and capable of. This study also looked into the available resources within the barangays and utilized them as a means of livelihood. The researchers would be of utmost willingness to recommend to extension educators and implementers a concrete and sustainable project from the results of the assessment to improve the socio-economic capacity of the residents and the standard of living of the local community.

Methods

The descriptive method was used in the study. Ardales (2008) also contends that descriptive research is appropriate for studies that aim to find out what prevails in the present; conditions or relationships held by opinion and beliefs, processes and effects, and developing trends. This type of research describes the data and characteristics of what is being studied. The researchers aimed to identify the training needs of coastal residents in Orani and analyze if these needs will be the basis for implementing a sustainable livelihood extension program for the community. As such, the descriptive method will be most suited for the study to further describe what exists within the barangay. A standard institutional survey questionnaire was used in the gathering of data.

The questionnaire has four main parts. The first part is about the profile of the coastal residents. The second part involves the socio-economic profile of the respondents. The third part includes the identification of all the training needs of the respondents. The fourth was a study on the extent of support given by the residents to community extension programs and services and the last part is the proposal of a livelihood training program and determine the costs and benefits of training.

The respondents of the study are the coastal residents of Orani, Bataan ages 25 to 64 years old only and not holding any position in the LGU. The researcher will use Sloven's formula to get the sample size and random sampling. The researchers used random sampling. The participants in this study were randomly selected. In particular, twenty-five (25) coastal residents in Pantalan Luma, twenty-five (25) in Pantalan Bago, twenty-five (25) Palihan, and twenty-five (25) coastal residents in Tapulao. Frequency counts, percentages, and weighted mean values will be used for the statistical computation of the gathered data. The data will then be gathered, analyzed, and interpreted to arrive at definite findings.

Results and Discussion

The presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the study are categorized based on the methods used and arranged based on the specific questions raised beforehand to arrive at and establish consistency and better comprehension. The data gathered is represented in tabular and textual form with the aid of statistical treatment for analysis and interpretation.

Table 1. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	F	%
25 - 30 years old	6	6
31 - 35 years old	17	17
36 - 40 years old	16	16
41 - 45 years old	33	33
50 and above	28	28
Total	100	100

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The table implies that the majority of the respondents were aged 41 – 45 years old with 33 percent and 25 – 30 years old got the lowest percentage of 6%. In that matter, it can be concluded that the respondents are in their middle adulthood where expanding personal and social involvement and responsibility are present.

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	F	%
Male	50	50
Female	50	50
Total	100	100

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. There is an equal percentage of respondents of both males and females having a percentage of 50% for each sex. Hence, it can be concluded that there is an equal representation of both women and men in this study since there is an equal number of respondents on both women and men participants. Hunt (2004), stated that equal representation of women and men in the study can be used to ensure that men and women are not disadvantaged by development activities, to enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of activities, or to identify priority areas for action to promote equality between women and men.

Table 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of Years of Stay in the Barangay

Years of Stay in Barangay	F	%
0 – 5 years	23	23
6 – 10 years	29	29
11 – 15 years	6	6
15 years and above	7	7
Since birth	35	35
Total	100	100

Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of years of stay in the barangay. It shows that 35% of the families were in that particular barangay since birth. It is followed by those who stay in the barangay for 6 – 10 years with 29% and with the lowest percentage of 11 – 15 years of stay in the barangay.

Table 4. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Members of the Family

Members of the Family	F	%
1 - 3	63	63
4 - 6	26	26
7 - 9	9	9
10 and above	2	2
Total	100	100
Number of Children	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5,6	100	1.20
Number of Members of the Family with job	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4	100	1.24
Number of Members of the Family ages 17 and below	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	100	0.73
Number of Members of the Family ages 65 and above	F	Mean
0, 1, 2, 3, 4	100	0.29
Do you have Members of the Family with a disability?	F	%
Yes	7	7
No	93	93
Total	100	100

Furthermore, Table 4 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of the members of the family. Specifically, the members of the family were also classified or identified in terms of the number of children, number of members of the family with jobs, number of members of the family ages 17 and below, number of members of the family ages 65 and above, and if the respondents have members with disabilities.

In terms of members of the family, 1 – 3 members got the highest percentage of 63%. It was followed by 4 – 6 members with 26% and 10 members and above got the lowest percentage of 2%.

In terms of several children, the overall mean of 1.20 indicates that in totality there is only one (1) child per family. The weighted mean of 1.24, indicates that there is at least one (1) member per family has a job. There is also one (1) member of the family ages 17 and below with a 0.73 weighted mean. Only a few or considered no members ages 65 and above have 0.29 as the mean. Finally, 93% of the respondents declared that they don't have members with disability, and 7% of them have members with disability. Among the disabilities stated by the respondents are as follows: eye disorder, mental illness, and other sickness.

Table 5. Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	F	%
Elementary Undergraduate	25	25
Elementary Graduate	37	37
High School Undergraduate	13	13
High School Graduate	17	17
College Graduate	6	6
Vocational Graduate	2	2
Total	100	100

Table 5 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their educational attainment. Thirty-seven percent of the respondents were elementary graduates. It also shows that there is a lower percentage of college and vocational graduates having 2% and 6% respectively. Truly, education is vital for a highly skilled and productive labor force. This study seeks to quantify the relationships between additional educational attainment and employment opportunities, wage rates, and aggregate economic growth. Holtz-Eakin and Lee (2019) explained that increasing education attainment would have powerful positive effects on the economy. Specifically, as individuals attain greater education, their probability of employment rises; and greater education, including certification for those without a high school or college degree, also increases workers' ability to command higher wages. Thus, post-secondary educational attainment of all types would not just increase employment opportunities and wages in the labor market, but would also spur widespread and stronger economic growth.

Table 6. Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Monthly Income

Monthly Income	F	%
Php5,000.00 and below	26	26
Php10,000.00 – Php15,999.00	20	20
Php16,000.00 – Php19,999.00	51	51
Php20,000.00 – Php24,999.00	2	2
Php25,000.00 – Php29,999.00	1	1
Php30,000.00 and above	0	0
Total	100	100

Table 6 indicates the socio-economic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly income. It shows that the majority of the coastal residents have Php16,000.00 to Php19,999.00 monthly income with 51%. None of the residents acquire Php30,000.00 and above as a

monthly income and 1% have Php25,000.00 to Php29,999.00 as income. According to The Philippines Today (2021), a Filipino family of five's economic standing is based on their monthly income. Data was presented to the Senate finance committee by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) namely: low income but not poor with Php 10,957 to Php 21,914; lower middle with Php 21,914 to Php 43,828; middle class with Php 43,828 to Php 76,669; upper middle with Php 76,669 to Php 131,484; upper but not rich with Php 131,484 to Php 219,140; and rich with Php 219,140. Hence, it can be concluded that the coastal residents of Orani belong to low-income but not poor residents.

Table 7. Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Monthly Expenses

Monthly Expenses	F	%
Php5,000.00 and below	35	35
Php10,000.00 – Php15,999.00	12	12
Php16,000.00 – Php19,999.00	0	0
Php20,000.00 – Php24,999.00	52	52
Php25,000.00 – Php29,999.00	0	0
Php30,000.00 and above	0	0
Total	100	100

Table 7 presents the socio-economic profile of the respondents in terms of monthly expenses. It shows that the majority of the coastal residents have Php20,000.00 to Php24,999.00 monthly expenses with 52%. It was then followed by Php5,000.00 and below with 35%. It can also be noticed that the monthly expenses of the residents were greater than their monthly income. Commission on Population and Development states that the average Filipino family spends nearly half of its resources per month on food. The Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) reported that at the end of the second quarter of 2018, food expenditure stood at 41.5 percent of total household expenditure. In the Philippines, more than half of family members are identified as dependents, based on the Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA) July 2018 overall dependency ratio of 57.7 percent. This means that the total family income is mostly spent on food and less spending is made on clothing and other basic service necessities such as housing, electricity, water, and other social services such as health and education.

Therefore, families with the highest poverty incidence such as those in the fishing and agriculture sectors are hardest hit as the high inflation rate remains unabated, making the daily survival of poor Filipino families hard to address, more so with increasing family size.

Table 8. Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Source of Income

Source of Income	F	%
Crop farming and gardening such as growing palay, corn, roots, vegetables, fruits, nuts, ornamental plants, etc.	1	1
Livestock and poultry raising such as raising of carabaos, cattle, hogs, horses, chickens, ducks, etc., and the production of fresh milk, eggs, etc.	2	2
Fishing activities such as capture of fish; gathering of fry, shells, seaweeds, etc.; culturing fish, oysters, mussels, etc.	27	27
Forestry and hunting activities such as tree planting (falcata, gmelina, rubber trees, etc.), firewood gathering, small-scale logging, charcoal making, gathering of forestry products (cogon, nipa, rattan, bamboo, resin, gum, etc.) or hunting of wild animals/birds, etc.	0	0
Wholesale and retail trade including market vending, sidewalk vending, peddling, etc.	6	6
Manufacturing activities such as mat weaving, tailoring, dressmaking, bagoong making, fish drying, etc.	3	3
Community, social, and personal services such as medical and dental practice, practice of trade, operation of schools, restaurants and hotels, etc.	3	3

Transportation, storage, and communication service such as the operation of jeepneys or taxis, storage and warehousing activities, messengerial services, etc.	15	15
Mining and quarrying activities such as mineral extraction like salt making, gold mining, gravel, sand and stone quarrying, etc.	0	0
Construction like repair of house, building or any structure.	2	2

Activities not elsewhere classified, including electricity, gas and water, financing, insurance, real estate and business services	0	0
Salaries and wages from employed members	44	44
Net share of crops, fruits, and vegetables produced or livestock and poultry raised by other households	0	0
Remittances from Overseas Filipino Workers	0	0
Other Cash receipts, gifts, support, relief, and other income from abroad including pensions, retirement, workmen's compensation, dividends from investments, etc.	0	0
Cash receipts, support, assistance, relief, and other income from domestic sources, including assistance from government and private sources	6	6
Rentals received from non-agricultural lands, buildings, spaces, and other properties	0	0
Interest from bank deposits, interest from loans extended to other families.	1	1
Pension and retirement, workmen's compensation, and social security benefits	0	0
Dividends from investments	1	1
Other sources of income not elsewhere classified	9	9
Total	100	100

Table 8 shows the socio-economic profile of the respondents in terms of source of income. Most of the respondents got their income from the salaries and wages of their employed members. It gathered the highest percentage of 44%. Since they live near the coastal areas, 27% of the respondents' income came from fishing activities such as the capture of fish; gathering of fry, shells, seaweeds, etc.; and culturing fish, oysters, mussels, etc. Fifteen percent of them got their income from transportation, storage, and communication services such as the operation of jeepneys or taxis, storage and warehousing activities, messengerial services, etc. Nine percent of the respondents said that they have other sources of income not elsewhere classified. Wholesale and retail trade including market vending, sidewalk vending peddling, etc. is the source of income for 6% of the residents.

Table 9. Training Needs Assessment

Type of Program	F	%
Health Assistance	35	23.81
Supplemental Feeding	11	7.48
Educational Scholarship	30	20.41
Skills and Livelihood Training Program	71	48.30
Others	0	0
Total	147	100

Table 9 presents the training needs assessment of the different types of programs. It shows that 71% of the respondents want to have a skills and livelihood training program in their respective barangay. Thirty-five percent of the respondents want to have a health assistance program. It is due to the current pandemic that most people are in. The educational scholarship program got 30% and supplemental feeding got the lowest percentage of 11%.

Vale (2016) enumerated the importance of skills and livelihood training programs. According to Vale, the training can create sustainable livelihood opportunities for vulnerable groups particularly young women and men, through skills and entrepreneurship training in identified market linkages. It can also strengthen the community organization and self-management skills by facilitating training and workshops on leadership and value formation as well as community participation in the implementation of various livelihood community projects.

Scrutinizing Table 10 displays that the majority of the training needs assessment in terms of skills and livelihood training programs wished to have training on Automotive technology with 22%. It was followed by the training on food processing with 19.72%. The training in Basic Cookery was 14.085, training in Welding was 9.86%, and training in candle making was 7.04%. Housekeeping garnered 5.63% with 4 respondents. It was then followed by dressmaking and computer programming with 2.81%. Lastly, bread and pastry making, tailoring, basic AutoCAD, electrical, and electronics all got the lowest percentage of 1.41%.

Table 10. Training Needs Assessment in terms of the Skills and Livelihood Training Program

Type of Skills and Livelihood Training Program	F	%
Bread and Pastry Making	1	1.41
Dressmaking	2	2.81
Tailoring	1	1.41
Candle Making	5	7.04
Computer Programming	2	2.81
Housekeeping	4	5.63
Basic Cookery	10	14.08
Food Processing	14	19.72
T-Shirt Printing	0	0
Welding	7	9.86
Basic AutoCAD	1	1.41
Automotive	22	30.99
Electrical	1	1.44
Electronics	1	1.44
Others	0	0
Total	71	100

Table 11. Extent of Support of Coastal Residents

Extent of Support of Coastal Residents	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating
I will attend all meetings held by any program implemented in our village or barangay.	4.44	Extremely Support
I will join in maintaining the peace and order while a project is taking place.	4.10	Support
I will devote time and energy to carry out the activities held in the said program.	3.57	Support

I will be involved in the development of our community.	4.13	Support
I will follow and apply the good things I learn in the program.	4.13	Support
Total	4.07	Support

Table 11 implies the extent of support of the coastal residents for the programs to be launched. With an overall weighted mean of 4.07, the coastal residents of the selected

barangay in Orani, Bataan agreed to support the programs to be conducted by the institution. They agreed to attend all meetings held by any program implemented in their village or barangay with the highest mean of 4.44 interpreted as extreme support. The statement that they will devote time and energy to carry out the activities held in the said program got the lowest mean of 3.57, however, it is still interpreted as support.

Therefore, it can be said that the extent of support has many benefits. The main aim of public support is to encourage the public to have meaningful input into the decision-making process. Participation and support thus provide the opportunity for communication between agencies making decisions and the public. This communication can be an early warning system for public concerns, a means through which accurate and timely information can be disseminated, and can contribute to sustainable decision-making.

Conclusion

1. In terms of the profile of the respondents, the majority of them are 41 – 45 years old. There is an equal percentage of respondents of both male and female. The majority of the families stayed in the barangay since birth. The family has 1 to 3 members. In general, there is one (1) child per family, and at least one (1) member per family has a job. There is also one (1) member of the family ages 17 and below and no member ages 65 and above. Finally, the majority of the respondents declared that they don't have a member with disability. In terms of educational attainment, majority of the respondents were elementary graduate.
2. In terms of the socio-economic profile of the respondents, the majority of them have a monthly income of Php16,000.00 to Php19,999.00. The majority of the coastal residents have Php20,000.00 to Php24,999.00 monthly expenses. Finally, most of them got their income from the salaries and wages of their employed members.
3. In general, the respondents wanted to have a skills and livelihood training program in their respective barangay. The majority of the training needs assessment in terms of skills and livelihood training program wished to have training on automotive technology, food processing, basic cookery, Welding, and candle making respectively.
4. The study revealed that the coastal residents of the selected barangay in Orani, Bataan agreed to support the programs to be conducted by the institution.

Recommendations

1. The institution must find ways to develop and implement a viable gender-based Extension Service Program for the coastal residents.
2. The personnel or extensionists should work hand in hand in improving the service of delivery of extension services to target clientele.
3. Proper monitoring of the financial practices utilized in the project should be done periodically.

4. Intensive monitoring and assessment should be made to meet the standards set by the government with regards to extension services operation reared the welfare of its client.

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Indicators of Successful Weaning from Renal Replacement Therapy in the Intensive Care Unit

Gianna Kalilah T. Roman

University of the West of England, United Kingdom

gkalilahroman@gmail.com

Abstract

This dissertation explores key indicators for the successful weaning of patients from Renal Replacement Therapy (RRT) in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Addressing the complications associated with RRT, the study emphasizes the importance of evidence-based strategies and timely initiation. Acute kidney injury affects a substantial number of individuals, leading to a significant need for RRT in critical cases. The research underscores the risks and potential adverse effects of prolonged RRT, emphasizing the need to identify the optimal time for discontinuation to prevent negative consequences. The methodology involves a systematic review and meta-analysis, examining existing literature to identify markers and predictors of successful RRT weaning. The results highlight urine output as a key variable, supported by multiple studies indicating its significance in predicting successful RRT discontinuation. The study also explores the roles of creatinine levels and diuretic therapy, offering a comprehensive overview of factors influencing the decision to wean patients from RRT. The study synthesizes findings, emphasizing the lack of consensus on certain indicators while underscoring the prominence of urine output. The conclusion highlights the importance of collaborative efforts among healthcare professionals, particularly critical care nursing, in monitoring patients and determining the optimal time for discontinuing RRT. Recommendations include the development of personalized guidelines, continuous education for healthcare teams, and regular monitoring of kidney function and fluid balance. In summary, this dissertation contributes insights into indicators for successful RRT weaning in the ICU, offering guidance for healthcare professionals to enhance patient outcomes and improve the quality of care in critical settings.

Keywords: acute kidney injury, continuous renal replacement therapy, intensive care, weaning, urine output, creatinine

Introduction

The UK Renal Registry (2018) reported that over 550,000 people develop acute kidney injury with approximately 60,000 requiring renal replacement therapy (RRT). This can be life-saving but does have complications associated with the procedure. To counter this measured intervention, approaches are employed to manage these issues (Wald et al., 2015). As new evidence-based research emerges surrounding RRT initiation strategies, such as beginning early versus late, there must also be a discussion on the optimal time to discontinue RRT in critically ill patients, and what markers are there to indicate this (Klouche, Gibney, and Forni, 2018).

After conservative management of fluid resuscitation, RRT is the next line of supportive management for patients who develop life-threatening fluid, acid-base, or electrolyte disorders (KDIGO, 2012). As with all medical interventions there are dangers associated with the treatment, namely the risks of catheter insertion for an extended duration, haemodynamic instability, hypothermia, electrolyte abnormalities, nutrient loss, and haemolytic complications from anticoagulation administration (Sigwalt et al., 2018).

With these prospects in mind, the critical care community must thoroughly assess whether RRT initiation would lead to the best outcomes, especially in patients without urgent indications as once the patient starts undergoing RRT there is a well-defined lead time to ceasing the treatment (Tandukar and Palevsky, 2018). The UK Renal Registry (2016) tallied a total of 592,212 deaths in 2016 from RRT patients. Likewise, in a prospective multicentre cohort study by Bagshaw et al. (2013), it concluded that hospital mortality was significantly higher, almost doubling, for RRT patients in comparison with non-RRT patients (62.4% vs 37.4%).

Given that prolonged RRT can promote poorer patient outcomes, increase hospital costs, and increase the likelihood of encountering adverse treatment effects (Kelly, Waikar, and Mendu 2019), it has also been found that extending the RRT period can potentially postpone kidney recovery increase dependency on medication over time (McCausland et al., 2016). As a consequence, there is an onus to identify when the patient can safely stop the treatment. Regardless, early discontinuation of RRT is not the best option for all circumstances (Frohlich et al., 2012), and early weaning in critically ill patients may contribute to higher mortality if the renal function has not fully recovered leading to systemic effects of ongoing AKI (Gemmell, Docking and Black, 2017).

Methods

The dissertation critically analysed the relevant literature to improve awareness and assess indications on the ideal time of when to safely wean from RRT in practice.

A systematic review and meta-analysis have been utilised to evaluate the ideal markers or predictors of successful weaning of RRT. Databases were searched and studies were screened using predefined keywords and criteria, however, the current pieces of evidence were inhibited by limitations. Studied parameters were included and, where possible, data was analysed to identify variables associated with successful discontinuation and the effect to patient outcomes.

Results

Discontinuing a course of RRT pertains to several different considerations such as biochemical criteria (creatinine, eGFR, and urea), kidney biomarkers (cystatin C), and physiologic characteristics (urine output, diuretic use, haemodynamic stability, and fluid balance) (Schiffl, 2018; Jones and Devonald, 2013). A systematic review and meta-analysis by Katulka *et al.* (2020) involving 23 studies revealed that urine output was the most common variable which suggests the indicator might be a good marker for successful RRT. Lee *et al.* (2017) concluded in a retrospective study including 165 patients that the urine output of the successfully weaned group was significantly higher than the non-successful group (55.7-66.3ml/hr vs 26.6-46.4ml/hr). On a similar note, the Artificial Kidney Initiation in Kidney Injury (AKIKI) trial by Gaudry *et al.* (2016) with 620 patients posited that the withdrawal of RRT once the urine output was 500 ml or higher per 24 hours should be considered, moving to a strong suggestion if the urine output was higher than 1000 ml per 24 hours without diuretics or higher than 2000 ml per 24 hours in patients receiving diuretics.

Further sources of evidence agree that urine output is a determining factor in identifying the optimal time to wean from RRT. Zarbock *et al.* (2016) recognised as urine output greater than 400 ml per 24 hours without diuresis and 2100 ml per 24 hours with diuretic therapy as key renal recovery parameters. Similarly, Viallet *et al.* (2016) concluded that a successful predictor of when to discontinue RRT was a urine output >2300 ml per 24 hours with diuretics. In addition, Katayama *et al.* (2016) established that RRT weaning was strongly associated with the urine output with prediction accuracy of AUROC (area under the curve) 0.814 which is considered excellent.

Another possible gauge for successful RRT weaning is a patient's creatinine level (Dewitte *et al.*, 2015). Gaudry *et al.* (2016) speculated that weaning RRT was necessary if there was an unprompted decline in serum creatinine with enough diuresis. Conversely, a further study by Katayama *et al.* (2016) recognised that although serum creatinine level was noteworthy and acceptable with an AUROC of 0.727, the discrepancy between the success and failure groups in RRT discontinuation was inconsequential. A different approach conducted by Viallet *et al.* (2016) utilised urinary creatine clearance (UCr) as a predictor for discontinuing RRT. The conclusions drawn were that a UCr of ≥ 5.2 mmol in 24 hours was linked with effective weaning in

84% of patients involved in the study. This phenomenon was further investigated in a cohort study by Aniert *et al.* (2016), which observed no difference between serum creatinine concentration and urinary creatinine concentration as a measure of effectiveness. Similarly, Lee *et al.* (2017) found no correlation between serum creatinine as a predictor of weaning RRT because of various factors (age, muscle mass, gender) that may affect the level.

An alternative school of thought on early discontinuation of RRT is the use of diuretic therapy to stimulate urination (Rosner *et al.*, 2014; Nadeau-Fredette and Bouchard, 2013). Jeon *et al.* (2018) revealed that the aggressive use of diuretic therapy was associated with successful RRT weaning. Patients who were treated with diuretics had higher urine output and better serum creatinine versus the non-diuretic cluster (619 vs 557 patients). Another study by Heise *et al.* (2012) concluded that diuretics administration contributed to the enhancement of kidney function while attempting to stop RRT. On the contrary, the use of diuretics to improve renal recovery or to increase RRT-free time was not recommended by KDIGO (2012) as the studies gathered didn't show any valuable improvement of administering diuretics in stopping RRT. To support the KDIGO findings, a study by Wu *et al.* (2012) which involved 572 patients, determined that there was no difference between the renal recovery between the diuretic versus non-diuretic groups. In addition to these findings, the 3-day accumulated dosage of using diuretics while in RRT could increase the mortality risk.

Discussion

In summary, after analysing various sources surrounding the indicators to successfully wean patients from RRT, there are three metrics regarding the health of a patient's renal system that has seen traction in recent times. Decreases in creatinine levels in both urinary and serum were equated to one another, but a consensus has yet to be reached linking this outcome to the optimal weaning effectiveness (Aniert *et al.*, 2016; Lee *et al.*, 2017). Diuretic therapy has been used to stimulate the renal system to demonstrate functionality, but official studies have not observed tangible benefits to the approach and advise against it (KDIGO, 2012; Wu *et al.*, 2012). Urine output was the only indicator to relish support from all sources analysed (Katulka *et al.*, 2020; Katayama *et al.*, 2016; Gaudry *et al.*, 2016; Viallet *et al.*, 2016; Zarbock *et al.*, 2016), with a tiered approach suggested in response to different prior treatments seemingly being adequate evidence for over three quarters of patients to be weaned in the surveyed studies, leading to better overall outcomes.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Currently, the verdict to stop RRT is strongly influenced by several clinical factors (Vanmassenhove *et al.*, 2018). Critical care nursing plays a huge impact on detecting the parameters on when is it safe to discontinue RRT as they are responsible for the 24-hour provision of keeping the patient safe and ensure good quality of care delivery (Richardson and Whatmore, 2015). Collaborative efforts by the multi-disciplinary team are essential to create a protocol on the parameters to consider when it is possible to stop RRT (Bonnassieux *et al.*, 2018). With all the recommendations from the studies, it is best to develop a suitable and personalised guideline or pathway fit and agreed by the whole team (Page *et al.*, 2014). Hourly fluid balance monitoring, taking into consideration the urine output, is a basic nursing intervention, nevertheless acknowledged as a key component in deciding when to wean patients from RRT (Asfour, 2016). In addition, regular monitoring of kidney function through diagnostic tests and checking of acid-base balance are crucial markers of renal function recovery in RRT patients (Wang *et al.*, 2021). As the advances in critical care have transformed into higher odds of survival- not only focusing on merely surviving but to a wider emphasis on quality of life, continuous education and specialised training for the health care teams are essential on striking the optimal time of weaning RRT promoting in-depth progression and evaluation of policies to improve RRT delivery in intensive care unit (Busch *et al.*, 2017; Graham and Lischer, 2011).

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Grounded Theory on the Winning Qualities of Student Athletes

Romeo Nisay Jr.^{1*}

*email: rjsnisay@bpsu.edu.ph

Abstract

Student-athletes acquire qualities like teamwork, time management, and leadership, contributing to their holistic development. Understanding athletes' performance histories, genes, environment, and other characteristics is critical for developing talent. The BPSU Swimming team has consistently excelled in swimming competitions, and this study aims to evaluate the key qualities that lead to the success of student-athletes and provide practical insights for their development. This study used a grounded theory approach to understand the qualities that make student-athletes successful. The study involved fourteen participants, including athletes, parents, coaches, a trainer, and officials, and data was collected through focus group discussions and interviews, following the principles of grounded theory methodology. The study identified several themes that describe the talent development experiences and influences of university swimming athletes. These themes include the role of genetics and physical characteristics, environmental opportunities and personal sacrifices, early successes in swimming, challenges faced by swimmers and coping mechanisms, as well as the role of family, coaches, teammates, and school in nurturing positive influences. These factors together contribute to the success and growth of the university's swimming athletes, highlighting the importance of investigating the combination of experiences and influences in studying talent development. The study also proposes a theory explaining how experiences and influences contribute to achieving swimming excellence and shaping the capacity, skills, values, and emotions of swimming athletes.

Keywords: Student-athletes, Winning Qualities, Sports, Talent Development

Introduction

Sports offers an avenue to explore their potential and strive for physical excellence, as highlighted by Martindale et al. (2014). Participating in sports is not only a significant decision but also a commitment that impacts a student's academic journey. It involves careful consideration of various factors, as it requires dedicated effort. According to MU Health Care (2023), engaging in sports demands a substantial amount of time and energy. Sports necessitate the development of memorization, repetitive practice, and learning abilities, skill sets directly applicable to academic performance. Moreover, the determination and goal-setting skills acquired through sports can be successfully transferred to the classroom environment. That being said, athletic success often necessitates the cultivation of certain personal qualities, such as diligent effort, self-discipline, unwavering perseverance, resolute determination, and unwavering focus. These attributes play a crucial role in enabling athletes to excel in their chosen disciplines.

According to Pinkerton et al. (2010), the pursuit of sporting activities encompasses more than mere physical exertion. Student-athletes acquire essential personal qualities, including teamwork, time management, mental health awareness, work ethic, leadership, and commitment. These attributes contribute to their holistic development as individuals. That being said, student-athletes must exhibit a unique blend of qualities that greatly impact their accomplishments, both on the field and in the classroom. As such, acquiring a comprehensive understanding of these winning attributes can provide educators, coaches, and parents with valuable insights to effectively support the holistic development of student-athletes.

In recent years, there has been a growing appreciation of the way sports are recognized and treasured in society. As a result, institutions have highlighted providing student-athletes with the essential provision to flourish in their athletic pursuits while also maintaining their academic responsibilities. According to Gomez et al. (2018), achieving excellence as an athlete requires significant time, commitment, and well-planned training. It is also crucial for student-athletes to find a balance between training and rest to adapt effectively. Amid a highly competitive environment, student-athletes face the challenge of managing these demands alongside their academic obligations.

Furthermore, Williams et al. (2020) state that psychological traits are now a crucial part of multifaceted models of athlete development. Early studies revealed that

young athletes who performed better than their peers had superior psychological capacities that enabled them to develop more. Throughout the past 20 years, psychological traits have been extensively studied and are important indicators of both development and adult success in addition to being consistently linked to youth players' present performance levels (Murr et al., 2018). Furthermore, a variety of significant psychological traits have been found through psychological research and linked to subjective coach, player, and scout perceptions and objective performance metrics (Williams et al., 2020).

Additionally, in the research conducted by Elferink-Gemser et al. (2012), it was emphasized that talent development programs have a specific objective of fostering players toward achieving a professional level of performance. When identifying, nurturing, and selecting young players, scouts, trainers, and coaches must acknowledge the existing level of their knowledge in their respective sports and the underlying performance characteristics, such as intermittent endurance capacity, as they are expected to improve over time. It is essential to recognize that this factor may have a significant impact on the aspirations of current young players who aim to reach the highest level of their sport in the next ten years. Given this, understanding athletes' performance histories, their genes (Turkheimer, 2000), their environment, and other physical and psychological characteristics are becoming increasingly recognized as critical components of developing a talent development strategy. Thus, it is critical to ascertain the athletes' thorough and practical preparation, family aid, expert coaching, adequate physical services, and psychological traits (Hamrouni et al. (2015). It is vital to explore the relationship between many crucial elements to acquire a thorough knowledge of swimmers' abilities throughout sports activities.

Furthermore, as per Simonton (2001), talent development in sports is a complex and constantly evolving process that involves the interaction of performance, psycho- social, and educational factors. This process encompasses multiple stages within the sport, including initiation, talent development, talent retention, mastery, perfection/elite performance, as well as educational milestones such as elementary school, high school, and college/university/vocational education. Furthermore, making well-informed decisions regarding pursuing an athletic career is crucial, as they have a direct impact on athletes' lives and their academic, sporting, familial, and peer support networks (Ryba et al., 2015). It is important to note that the literature on sports talent identification highlights the significance of key individuals and organizations in facilitating the holistic development of talented athletes. These

influential actors play a vital role in promoting athlete well-being, providing support during stressful situations across various areas of life (e.g., training intensity, competition demands, injuries, social life constraints, and transitions to higher levels of competition and academia). Thus, it is worth emphasizing that by adopting a comprehensive approach to talent development, athletes can optimize their potential while balancing their academic pursuits, personal relationships, and overall physical and mental well-being.

Over the past years, the Bataan Peninsula State University (BPSU) Swimming team consistently garnered more than 30 gold medals each year, which put them ranked number one in the SCUAA SUC III Olympics. Nonetheless, the overarching objective of the esteemed university is to cultivate the proficiency and prowess of our aspiring students, equipping them with the necessary skills to excel and emerge victorious across a diverse range of swimming competitions. That being said, the researcher arrived at this study and examined and evaluated the key qualities that lead to the success of student-athletes. By doing so, this study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the pivotal factors that contribute to their achievements in sports and academics. Through a systematic analysis of these qualities, this research aspires to offer practical and evidence-based insights for educational professionals, coaches, and parents in fostering the holistic development of student-athletes.

Methods

In this study, a grounded theory approach was employed to achieve the research objective of understanding and identifying the winning qualities of student-athletes. Grounded theory is a research method that aims to generate a substantive theory by thoroughly examining an empirical sociological and organizational inquiry (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The use of grounded theory is particularly valuable when investigating social phenomena that have not been extensively studied before. It is also well-suited for capturing the complex dynamics and behaviors within organizations (Locke, 2001).

Moreover, grounded theory generation is based on context-specific and process-oriented explanations of a social phenomenon. This is accomplished through the analysis of representative examples of data, allowing for a deeper understanding of the subject matter (Glaser & Strauss, 1967). The process of theory generation in grounded theory is inductive, meaning that data collection and analysis unfold together, allowing for the emergence of patterns and insights (Strauss & Corbin, 1998).

Through this iterative process, the researchers can uncover and articulate local understandings that would otherwise remain implicit and unexplained.

The aforementioned approach is appropriate to the study since grounded theory is a qualitative research methodology used to develop theories about phenomena in the social sciences. It involves gathering and analyzing data to construct theories that are "grounded" in the data itself, rather than starting with preconceived hypotheses. The process typically involves open coding, axial coding, and selective coding to identify patterns and categories in the data, ultimately leading to the development of a substantive theory. Grounded theory is often used in sociology, psychology, nursing, and other social science fields to explore and understand complex social phenomena.

In addition, there were fourteen (14) participants in the study, four (4) swimming athletes, four (4) parents of the athletes, three (3) coaches, one (1) trainer, and two (2) swimming officials. This sample size allows for in-depth exploration and analysis of the participants' experiences and perspectives, which is fundamental to grounded theory methodology.

Moreover, the qualitative method explored the experiences of participants through focus group discussion. In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted by the researcher through telephone with all participants of the study. Meanwhile, interviews consist of collecting data by asking questions. A structured discussion to stimulate conversation around a specific topic is led by a facilitator who poses questions and the participants give their thoughts and opinions (Abawi, 2013). Additionally, these in-depth interviews were analyzed using analytic procedures used in grounded theory (Strauss and Corbin, 1998).

Result and Discussion

From the two standpoints of the study, several themes that describe the talent development experiences and talent development influences of the swimming athletes of the university emerged from the data analysis.

Under the talent development experiences, themes that were drawn from the experiences of the swimmers include the role of nature (genetics) that includes their physical characteristics; environmental opportunities that focus on the swimmer's geographical location to focus on swimming, personal sacrifices and emphasis on education; early successes in swimming which include lessons learned from competitions and the emotional development towards sport; and the challenges and coping mechanisms of the swimmers which pertain to the adversities during practice

and competitions, development of mindset and discipline to address adversities and increased motivation to succeed in swimming.

According to Simonton (2001), talent development in sports is a multifaceted and ever-evolving process that involves the interaction of performance, psycho-social, and educational factors. This process typically encompasses various stages within the sport, including initiation, talent development, talent retention, mastery, perfection/elite performance, as well as educational milestones such as elementary school, high school, and college/university/vocational education

Under the talent development influences, themes that were drawn from the experiences of the swimmers include the role of nurture (early influences) which include inspiration from family members; building positive influences like support from family members, inspiration from the coaches, love from teammates and logistic from school; enhancing positive influences which contains enhancing positive influences and enhancing coping and relief mechanisms; and nurturing positive influences like learning life skills for adaptation and cultivating positive relationships.

In relation to this, making informed decisions regarding pursuing an athletic career is crucial, as they directly impact the lives of athletes and their academic, sporting, familial, and peer support networks (Ryba et al., 2015). It is important to note that the literature on sports talent identification emphasizes the significance of key individuals and organizations in facilitating the holistic development of talented athletes. These influential actors play a vital role in promoting athlete well-being, supporting them during stressful situations across various life domains (e.g., training intensity, competition demands, injuries, social life constraints, and transitions to higher levels of competition and academia). That being said, by taking a comprehensive approach to talent development, athletes can maximize their potential while balancing their academic pursuits, personal relationships, and overall physical and mental well-being.

Overall, the winning qualities of the swimming athletes of the university are products of factors that influence them and the experiences that made them over the years since childhood. Their rich experiences which combined the role of nature (genetics), environmental opportunities, early successes in swimming, and the challenges and coping mechanisms of the swimmers and the combined force of influencing factors like the role of nurture (early influences), building enhancing and nurturing positive influences are influential in their talent development and growth as successful swimmers in the university. As such, it is essential to investigate the

combination of factors of experiences and influences when studying talent development that may create the winning qualities of student-athletes. From this combination of factors, one grounded theory was developed to explain how experiences and influences produce winning qualities in swimmers. This theory on the role of experience and influence towards achieving swimming excellence provides a bigger picture in understanding the role of experiences and influences in harnessing the capacity, skills, values, and emotions of swimming athletes.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The swimming athletes of the university experiences of the swimmers develop their winning qualities in swimming due to their experiences that were brought by their nature (genetics), environmental opportunities, early successes in swimming, and the challenges and coping mechanisms of the swimmers. Also, building, enhancing, influencing, and nurturing positive influences in their life from childhood to the present help enhance their talent in swimming.

From these experiences and influences, theory showing a path to a successful college swimming career was concluded. This theory on the role of experience and influence towards achieving swimming excellence provides a bigger picture in understanding the role of experiences and influences in harnessing the capacity, skills, values, and emotions of swimming athletes.

This theory of experiences and influence toward swimming excellence may be used by the university especially the Office of the Sports and Development in designing a comprehensive talent development plan for future swimming athletes of the university and can even be applied to other competitive sports being participated in by the university. This will help maintain a reputable standing in the region as one of the powerhouses in swimming.

Also, the findings of the study may be used by the university in building a talent identification program that will help identify and scout prospective athletes at the elementary and secondary levels. These students who will be scouted based on the criteria mentioned in the theory of experience and influence towards achieving swimming excellence will be placed under the university's watch and be provided with ample support until the time they enter the university to become its athletes.

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Analysis of Profitability Ratio to Business Risk at Toko Sunrises After Pandemic Covid-19

Idul Adha Y Djangga¹ Titin Dunggio^{2*} and Fibriyanti S. Lakoro³

^{1,2,3}Bina Mandiri University Gorontalo

ubmgorontalo@ubmg.ac.id*

Abstract

This study aims to determine the profitability risk at Sunrises Stores based on the ratio of profitability to sales value after the covid 19 pandemic. The research method used in this research is the mixed method. The data analysis technique used is explanatory *sequential mixed methods*, namely the combination method data analysis technique is carried out in two stages. The first stage was carried out qualitatively using data analysis carried out at the time the data collection took place. The second stage of data analysis was carried out quantitatively, namely the process of analyzing the data using descriptive statistics, which was carried out to find the strength of the relationship between variables to understand the phenomenon of what was experienced holistically, and using descriptions in the form of words and language, in a context. specifically, to provide solutions or input for problems that are appropriate and related to the problem. The results of the research are Sunrises Shop, the risk of profitability is quite fluctuating from 2019-2021 which experienced ups and downs in sales value by Sunrises Shop owners during the post-covid-19 pandemic, but with good sales management so it can provide good results on profitability ratios with a GPM value in 2021 of 0.14 from the previous year's GPM value of 0.09

Keywords: Profitability Rasio, Profitability of Sunrice Store, Business Risk Analysis

Introduction

The real thing from economic growth due to the globalization of the world economy is the increasing need for capital companies and this need requires a more complex capital structure. One of the breakthroughs made by business people is informal capital participation, namely the development of the *profitability* of a business. The current economic position has also been greatly affected due to the COVID-19 virus pandemic, which has been increasing in number in Indonesia since February 2020.

Many economic activities have stopped all over the world, and this impact has been felt in Indonesia, both large companies and start-ups, as well as companies with a stockist business model.

Currently, the outbreak of a virus called COVID-19 has disrupted the global economy (McKibbin & Fernando, 2020) and has had an impact on Indonesia which has affected the economic sector. The COVID-19 pandemic has an impact on the threat of a major economic crisis marked by the cessation of activities production in various countries, declining levels of public consumption, loss of consumer confidence, and a crash in the stock market which ultimately leads to uncertainty. The COVID-19 pandemic situation provides challenges and opportunities for the Government of Indonesia to maintain the existence of community businesses.

Therefore, there is a need for a short-term solution for SMEs and workers who are members of it. Sunrises Store is one of the businesses engaged in wholesale which is located at Tabongo Barat Village, Tabongo District, Gorontalo Regency. To run a post-pandemic business like this, risk management is needed to achieve its goals.

This condition is indeed different when compared to large companies because in terms of information resources and human resources, these businesses still have weaknesses, namely limited information regarding knowledge in dealing with a pandemic when connected to *Profitability* before and after Covid-19. Risk management is an attempt to find out, analyze, and control risk to obtain high effectiveness and efficiency for every activity in a company (Darmawi, 2016). Risk management will assist business owners in identifying risks that can occur when running their business so that they can remain competitive, especially during the current COVID-19 pandemic. The implementation of well-managed risk management can contribute.

Based on initial observations made at the Sunrises Store Business, several risks affect business profitability, namely, the first is the risk of purchasing where the presence of the Covid-19 pandemic has a significant effect on purchasing activities in 2020 which causes a lack of purchasing stock of goods due to the availability of previous stock of goods, which second is the risk of price fluctuations caused by the covid-19 pandemic so that supply is not elastic and causes a lack of demand from customers, the third is the risk of profit arising due to purchase risk and risk of

fluctuation so that the potential benefits generated have a very drastic reduction during a pandemic.

In addition, some risks also affect business profitability after the COVID-19 pandemic, namely technical risks and risks, where the Sunrises Shop business experiences termination of employment with third parties who are also large customers to market merchandise.

Therefore this business needs a more in-depth analysis related to profitability risk, while the profitability ratio used for that is first Gross Profit Margin this ratio shows the relative value of gross profit to sales value, the second profitability ratio is Net Profit Margin this margin measures the level of profit that can be achieved by a business in connection with sales, the third profitability ratio is Return On Assets this ratio shows the return on the total assets used by the business, the last profitability ratio is Return On Equity to measure net profit after tax with own capital.

It can be seen that there is a significant difference in sales at the Sunrises Store between 2019 - 2021, where at the beginning of 2019 sales were Rp. 1,130. 949,864 assets at the Sunrises' Store are still in normal condition so a large amount of income is earned. In 2020, sales decreased by Rp. 613,116,974 of the total sales of Rp. 1. 130,189,864 in 2019 compared to 2020. This is because the implementation of activity restrictions is still in effect, but in 2021 the government has been intensively carrying out COVID-19 vaccinations so that activities can still be carried out, and this of course has a positive impact on sales in stores Sunrises. It can be seen at the beginning of 2021 that the turnover has reached Rp. 844,749,464, if the Sunrises Store succeeds in maintaining its sales target, it is certain that sales turnover at the end of 2022 will increase compared to 2020 and 2021. This is because the imposition of restrictions on community activities is no longer as strict as in previous years so sales activity continues.

Financial Management

Management has been defined in many ways "*Finance can be defined as the science and art of managing money*" means "Finance can be defined as the art and science of managing money". From this definition, it can be developed that finance as an art means involving expertise and experience, while as a science means involving principles, concepts, theories, proportions, and models that exist in science finance (Rosita & Nilasari, 2022).

Financial Management can be interpreted as good fund management related to allocating funds in various forms of investment effectively as well as collecting efforts to finance investment or learning efficiently (Sartono, 2015).

Financial management is one of the management functions of all company activities related to the activities of obtaining sources of funds, using funds, and managing assets to achieve company goals, in other words, financial management is

the art and science of managing company funds, both obtaining funds and allocating company funds (Musthafa, 2017).

Profitability

Ratios Profitability ratios are ratios used to measure a company's efficiency in utilizing assets and managing its operations. Profitability ratios are a group of ratios that show the combined effect of liquidity, asset management, and debt on operating results. This ratio is also used to determine the company's ability to generate profits (Riyanto, 2018).

The profitability ratio is a ratio to assesses the company's ability to make a profit. This ratio also provides a measure of the effectiveness of a company's management. This is indicated by the profit generated from sales and investment income (Kasmir, 2017).

Based on some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that the profitability ratio is the ratio used to assess a company's ability to earn profits at the level of sales, assets, and capital.

Business

Risk is a hazard, result or consequence that may occur as a result of an ongoing or future process. Risk can be interpreted as a state of uncertainty, where if an unwanted condition occurs it can result in a loss (Sutrisno, 2017).

Risk is a situation where the possibility of loss or harm can be predicted in advance by using reliable or relevant data or information available. Risk has two meanings, namely:

- a. Business risk, is the risk of not being able to pay the company's operating costs.
- b. Financial risk, is the risk of not being able to pay maturing fixed obligations associated with debt, leasing, and preferred stock financing.

Financial

Risk is an uncertainty experienced by a company as a result of ongoing business activities (Dewi, 2019). If the company is unable to overcome the various risks that exist, the company will certainly experience bankruptcy risk. Risk is the possibility of a loss, or the variability of income associated with certain assets [10]. In general, everything has a risk, but the size of the risk depends on the results we expect, the greater the results to be obtained, the greater the risk that must be faced, therefore the success or failure of the risk is faced depending on how we manage existing risks to generate profitable opportunities.

Business

Risk Business risk can be interpreted as uncertainty in the estimated profit or loss of the company's operations in the future. The company's business risk affects the survival of the company and where the company is able to pay its debts.

Companies that have high business risk tend to be less able to use large amounts of debt in corporate funding because they avoid non-payment of debt in the future.

Business risk is a risk for the company because it cannot cover its operational costs. In general, the greater the company's operating leverage, the use of fixed operating costs, the higher the business risk (Gitman, 2015).

Methods

The research method used in this study is the mix methods method. The data analysis technique used is explanatory *sequential mixed methods*, namely the combination method data analysis technique is carried out in two stages. The first stage was carried out qualitatively with the Miles and Huberman model, namely data analysis was carried out when data collection took place and was carried out interactively by Huberman by means of data reduction, data display and conclusions or verification (Sugiyono, 2017).

While the second stage of data analysis was carried out quantitatively, namely the process of analyzing the data using descriptive statistics, namely statistics used to analyze data by describing or describing the data that has been collected (Sugiyono, 2017). In statistical analysis *descriptive* is also carried out to find the strength of the relationship between variables. The quantitative data obtained will be calculated using this ratio analysis technique used to measure or assess the effectiveness of business working capital over a certain period. This means how much the company's working capital rotates in a certain period or in a period.

The profitability ratios used in this study are as follows:

1) *Gross Profit Margin (GPM)*

$$\mathbf{GPM} = \frac{\mathbf{Sales - HPP}}{\mathbf{Sales}}$$

2) *Net Profit Margin (NPM)*

$$\mathbf{NPM} = \frac{\mathbf{Net Profit}}{\mathbf{Berth Sales}}$$

3) *Return On Assets (ROA)*

$$\mathbf{ROA} = \frac{\mathbf{Net Income}}{\mathbf{Total Assets}}$$

4) *Return Of Equity (ROE)*

$$\mathbf{ROE} = \frac{\mathbf{Bersth Profit}}{\mathbf{Capital}}$$

Results

- 1) Descriptive Analysis of Research Selection of Sunrises Store due to several risks which affect the profitability of the business at the Sunrises Store, namely, the first is the purchase risk where the co-19 pandemic has a significant effect on purchasing activity where in this study analyzes financial reports from 2019 to 2021 to be able to determine the profitability of the Sunrises Store business. Based on the annual financial report, it will be analyzed using the Profitability risk formula, financial risk and business risk.
- 2) Profitability Ratio Analysis
 - a. Analysis *Gross Profit Margin (GPM)* *Gross Profit Margin (GPM)* or gross profit is used to determine a company's gross profit that comes from the sale of each of its products. This ratio is strongly influenced by the value of cost of goods sold Sunrises Store. *gross profit margin* is an indication that the greater the return on gross profit earned by Sunrises Stores on its net sales. The more efficient the costs incurred by the company to support sales activities so that the income earned increases. By using the formula:

$$GPM = \frac{\text{Sales} - \text{HPP}}{\text{Sales}}$$

Table 1. Gross Profit Margin (GPM) Toko Sunrises

No	Period	Gross Profit (Rp)	Income (Rp)	GP M (%)
1	2019	266,103,47 0.00	1,130,499, 464.00	0.24
2	2020	115,720,98 0.00	612,716,9 74.00	0.19
3	2021	188,563,47 0.00	844,199,4 64.00	0.22

Source: Processed Data 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Sunrises Store in 2019 earned a gross profit of IDR 266,103,470.00 and revenue of IDR 1,130,499,464.00 with a GMP of 0.24, in 2020 it earned a gross profit of IDR 115,720,980.00 and

revenue of IDR 612,716,974.00 with a GMP of 0.19 and in 2021 a gross profit of Rp. 188,563,470.00 and a revenue of Rp. 844,199,464.00 with a GMP of 0.21.

It can be seen that in 2020 revenue has decreased quite drastically from the previous year due to the Covid-19 period but income can be increased again in 2021 even though it is not as high as in 2019 but can be higher than 2020 sales.

Results of interviews with the owner of the Sunrises Store (KR) related d with GPM working as follows:

"In 2020 was a very tough year, because the profits obtained have decreased quite drastically, the lack of buyers making purchases at our stores as well as the lack of sales we make, which is where we usually distribute to shops. small, we didn't do it because of the limitations of activities in accordance with government regulations during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The results of this study are supported by the results of interviews conducted by researchers with shop owners who explained that the *Profit Margin* (NPM) of the Sunrises Store was like that in 2020, indeed a very hard year for the Sunrises Store, even for all business people and traders that year.

From the results of the research above, it can be concluded that the Sunrises Store, seen from *Gross Profit Margin* (GPM), has good financial development after post-covid-19, by having a gross profit that is not large but has an increase in 2021 after 2020 experienced a decrease in revenue which was affected by the covid-19 pandemic.

b. Analysis *Net Profit Margin* (NPM)

Net profit margin is sales profit after calculating all costs and income taxes. This margin shows the ratio of net profit after tax to sales. by using the formula:

$$NPM = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Net Salas}}$$

Table 2. Net Profit Margin (NPM) Toko Sunrises

No	Period	Net Profit (Rp)	Income (Rp)	NPM (%)
1	2019	190,803,470.00	1,130,499,464.00	0.17
2	2020	56,130,980.00	612,716,974.00	0.09
3	2021	114,962,470.00	844,199,464.00	0.14

Source: Processed Data 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Sunrises Store in 2019 earned a net profit of Rp. 190,803,470.00 and revenue of Rp. 1,130,499,464.00 with an NPM of 0.17, in 2020 earned a net profit of Rp. IDR 56,130,980.00 and revenue of IDR 612,716,974.00 with an NPM of 0.09 and in 2021 gross profit of IDR 114,962,470.00 and revenue of IDR 844,199,464.00 with an NPM of 0.14

Profit Margin (NPM), in 2020 the Sunrises Store experienced a decrease in net profit due to the covid-19 period but in 2021 it has increased again because in 2021 the covid-19 period has improved so that the Sunrises Store has experienced a recovery in sales made.

The results of an interview with the owner of the Sunrises Store (KR) related to work NPM are as follows:

"Indeed, at that time we were experiencing sales problems caused by Covid-19 where the government issued a policy of limited activities, so the sales we felt were very disproportionate"

From the results of the research above, it can be concluded that *Profit Margin (NPM)* has significant good results, seen from the results of the analysis of financial statements, sales profits during the Covid-19 pandemic greatly influenced sales that owned by the Sunrises Store, where the sales obtained experienced a decrease in the limited activity pressure factor owned by the owner of the Sunrises Store and customers when making sales or purchases.

c. Analysis Return on Assets (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) is used to measure the financial performance of multinational companies, especially from the point of view of profitability and investment opportunities. ROA is often used by management to measure a company's financial performance and assess operational performance in utilizing

the company's resources, besides the need to consider financing issues for these assets. Using the formula:

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Laba Bersih}}{\text{Total Aktiva}}$$

Table 3. *Return On Assets (ROA) Toko Sunrises*

No	Period	Net Profit (Rp)	Total Assets (Rp)	ROA (%)
1	2019	190,803,470.00	300,000,000.00	0.64
2	2020	56,130,980.00	269,000,000.00	0.21
3	2021	114,962,470.00	284,000,000.00	0.40

Source: Processed Data 2022

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Sunrises Store in 2019 earned a net profit of Rp. 190,803,470.00 and total assets of Rp. 300,000,000.00 with an ROA of 0.64, in 2020 earned a profit net of IDR 56,130,980.00 and total assets of IDR 268,000,000.00 with an ROA of 0.21 and in 2021 earn a gross profit of IDR 114,962,470.00 and total assets of IDR 284,000,000.00 with an NPM of 0.40

Return on Assets (ROA) Sunrises stores have fluctuating total assets went down due to the covid-19 pandemic, but in the third year the sunrises shop experienced an increase, namely in 2021 from 2020 which experienced a decline, this increase was due to good financial management carried out by the sunrises shop owner to be able to overcome the problem of decreasing profits due to there is a covid-19 pandemic.

The results of interviews with the owner of the Sunrises Store (KR) related to work ROA are as follows:

"Right now, I only depend on what I have, always develop the business to be more advanced, as well as always improve in financial management."

The results of this research are supported by the results of interviews conducted by researchers to the shop owner explaining that the *Return on Assets (ROA)* of the Sunrises Store, the total assets they own are in accordance with what is the result of the research, because the assets currently owned are based on the results of the financial statements provided, but for now the shop owner Sunrises will develop a business that is still in the planning stage.

From the results of the research above, it can be concluded that the *Return on Assets* (ROA) at the Sunrises Store was not in good condition during Covid-19, this was due to the lack of buyers buying drinks at the Sunrises Store and the lack of sales made to small shops that had been cooperation with Sunrises Stores, at that time the stores that collaborated with Sunrises Stores also experienced sales problems which impacted sales at Sunrises Stores.

Discussion

Gross Profit Margin (GPM) The results showed that Sunrises Stores in 2019 earned a gross profit of Rp. 266,103,470.00 and revenue of Rp. 1,130,499,464.00 with a GPM of 0.24, in 2020 earned a gross profit of Rp. 115,720,980.00 and revenue of Rp. 612,716,974.00 profit of Rp. 188,563,470.00 and revenue of Rp. 844,199,464.00 with a GPM of gross 0.21.

It can be seen that in 2020 revenue has decreased quite drastically from the previous year due to the Covid-19 period but income can be increased again in 2021 even though it is not as high as in 2019 but can be higher than 2020 sales. The results of this study are supported by the results of interviews carried out by researchers to shop owners who explained that the *Gross Profit Margin* (GPM) results were in accordance with the financial statements owned by Sunrises Stores, because at that time the biggest obstacle faced was the sudden pandemic that affected sales made every day. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a negative impact on the financial performance of retail companies in Indonesia. This is evident in the decline in profitability, as shown by the decline in ROA and ROE, although GPM may not experience a significant decrease (Pratama dan Sherly, 2021).

Net profit margin ratio is also called the sales ratio. The stability of the entity to generate gains at a given level of sales by examining the profit margins and industry norms of a company in previous years, we can judge the efficiency of operations and pricing strategies as well as the competitive status of the company with other companies in the industry. A company will be considered good if the net profit margin is high or close to the sales value they are targeting.

Net Profit Margin (NPM)

The results show that Sunrises Stores in 2019 earned a net profit of IDR 190,803,470.00 and revenue of IDR 1,130,499,464.00 with an NPM of 0.17, in 2020 earn a net profit of IDR 56,130,980.00 and revenue of IDR 612,716,974.00 with an NPM of 0.09 and in 2021 earn a gross profit of IDR 114,962,470.00 and revenue of IDR 844,199,464.00 with an NPM of 0.14

Profit Margin (NPM) an increase during the pandemic period, in 2020 the Sunrises Store experienced a decrease in net profit due to the covid-19 period but in

2021 it experienced another increase because in 2021 the covid-19 period had improved so that the Sunrises Store experienced a recovery in sales made.

The results of this study were supported by the results of interviews conducted by researchers with shop owners who explained that the *Profit Margin* (NPM) of Sunrises Stores was like that in 2020, indeed a very hard year for Sunrises Stores, even for all businessmen and traders in that year.

Net profit margin (NPM) is a ratio that calculates the extent to which a company's ability to generate net profit at a certain level of sales. To measure this ratio is to compare net profit after tax with net sales. Net profit margin (NPM) plays a key role in driving the growth of SME businesses. The findings of this research can help SME managers formulate strategies that can improve NPM and drive the growth of their businesses. (Wang & Chen, 2018).

The net profit margin ratio is a ratio that describes how a company can generate maximum net profit or expected profit when viewed from the level of sales made by the company. The greater the Net Profit Margin, the more efficient the company is in incurring costs related to its operations.

Gross Profit Margin (GPM)

The results showed that the Sunrises Store in 2019 earned a net profit of Rp. 190,803,470.00 and total assets of Rp. 300,000,000.00 with an ROA of 0.64, in 2020 earned a net profit of Rp. 56,130,980.00 and total assets of Rp. 268,000,000.00 with ROA amounted to 0.21 and in 2021 earned a gross profit of IDR 114,962,470.00 and total assets of IDR 284,000,000.00 with an NPM of 0.40.

Sunrises have increased, namely in 2021 from 2020 which has decreased, this increase is due to good financial management carried out by sunrises shop owners to be able to overcome the problem of decreasing profits obtained due to the co-19 pandemic.

The results of this study are supported by the results of interviews conducted by researchers with shop owners who explained that the *Return on Assets* (ROA) of the Sunrises Store's total assets are in accordance with what is the result of the research, because the assets currently owned are based on the results of the financial statements. given, but for now the owner of the Sunrises store will develop his business which is still in the planning stage.

Return On Assets (ROA) is a form of profitability ratios that are intended to be able to measure a company's ability to generate profits with all the funds used for its operations. The greater the value of return on assets, the more efficient the company uses assets in generating profits. This is demonstrated by the profit generated from sales and investment income. The goal is to see the development of the company within a certain time span, either decreasing or increasing profits.

The research by (Sengupta & Bhattacharya, 2017) provides strong evidence that ROA plays a key role in driving the growth of manufacturing firms. The findings of

this research can help company managers to formulate strategies to improve ROA and drive the growth of their businesses. ROA is able to measure a company's ability to generate profits in the past to then be projected in the future. The assets or assets in question are all of the company's assets, obtained from its own capital or from foreign capital that the company has converted into company assets that are used for the company's survival.

Conclusion and Recommendation

From the results of this study, the researcher can conclude that the risk of profitability for Sunrise shops has fluctuated quite a bit from 2019-2021, which experienced ups and downs in the sales value experienced by Sunrise shop owners during the post-covid-19 pandemic, but with good sales management so that it can produce results. a good profitability ratio with a GPM value in 2021 of 0.09% from the previous year's GPM value of 0.09%, NPM value in 2021 of 0.17% from the previous year 0.09% and ROA value in 2021 of 0.64% from the previous year 0.21 % but if assessed by standard profitability ratios do not meet the significant level.

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Design and Experimental Concept for Dissimilar Ultrasonic Welding Joints for Aluminum Alloy to Glass-Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Tubes

Michael de Leon^{1*}, Mark Angelo Diaz², Richard Pascua³, and Gellieca Dullas⁴

*email: deleonmichael@staff.anu.ac.kr

Abstract

This conceptual study explores ultrasonic welding (UW) for creating joints between aluminum alloy A5052-H32 and glass-fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) cylindrical tubes, capitalizing on the method's advantages, such as low energy requirements, minimal heat-affected zones, and direct energy transfer to the weld interface. The research, conducted by the group with extensive expertise in solid-state joining and material deformation under extreme conditions, responds to the growing demand for reliable, fast, and cost-effective joining technologies. The proposed hybrid-UW technique introduces gradient functions at the joint interface, aiming to enhance the performance of Al/GFRP dissimilar joints. The manuscript not only outlines the technical approach and experimental methods employed but also highlights the distinctive aspects of the proposed technology. In addition to detailing the materials used and the design considerations for the ultrasonic welder's horn and anvil, the study provides a glimpse into the practical implementation of the proposed hybrid- UW technique. The limited joints made during the experimental phase serve as a proof-of-concept for the feasibility and potential effectiveness of the approach.

Keywords: Ultrasonic welding, Dissimilar joints, Aluminum alloy, Glass-fiber-reinforced polymers, Hybrid ultrasonic welding, Joint interface, Lightweight materials, Joining technology.

Introduction

The demand for innovative joining technologies capable of joining dissimilar materials with varying properties has surged recently. Lightweight aluminum alloys, known for their structural advantages, and glass-fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites, prized for their high strength-to-weight ratio, present a compelling combination for diverse industrial applications. Joining these materials, however, remains a challenge, and it is this challenge that motivated the current study. This research is based on a comprehensive understanding of solid-state joining techniques, with a particular emphasis on ultrasonic welding (UW). The process of joining materials without the fusion of heat aligns seamlessly with the group's expertise (Shin et al., 2016). Over the years, the researchers have significantly contributed to the field, exploring various materials' deformation behaviors and developing novel joining techniques under extreme conditions (Shin et al., 2008; Shin & Jung, 2008; Shin, 2014, Shin & De Leon, 2015, Shin & De Leon, 2017, Chen et al., 2016). These conditions include high velocity and pressure, cryogenic temperatures, mechanical property testing, and high current conditions, making the researchers' experience different from the conventional studies in the field.

The industry's pressing need for dependable, efficient, and reasonably priced joining technologies designed for construction including fiber-reinforced polymer materials is what encouraged this research. Although mechanical joining techniques such as clinching (Zhang et al., 2016) and self-pierce riveting (Mandel & Krüger, 2012; Lambiase & Ko, 2017) facilitate quick assembly without requiring initial hole drilling (Ucsnik et al., 2010), the problem is that fasteners are prone to corrosion and their mass adds structural weight (Tan et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2013). On the contrary, adhesive bonding has disadvantages such as expensive costs, careful surface preparation, and long cure times even though it works well (Farahani & Dubé, 2017; Lionetto et al., 2017). Appropriate adhesion qualities are dependent on a temperature- and time- controlled crosslinking process (Arenas et al., 2013). Moreover, there are disadvantages to this technology, including the short lifespan of adhesive joints and the release of hazardous compounds into the environment (Lambiase et al., 2016; Pramanik et al., 2017).

Current research worldwide is addressing this need, but the group's advantage lies in the researchers' experience in solid-state joining, especially with dissimilar materials. Ultrasonic welding, chosen as the primary approach, offers distinct advantages, such as low welding energy requirements and minimal heat-affected

zones (Shin & De Leon, 2017). In contrast to other techniques like resistance spot welding, UW and its hybrid variations possibly avoided the liquid phase reactions and directed energy precisely onto the weld interface (De Leon & Shin, 2017; De Leon & Shin, 2023; De Leon & Shin, 2022). This study builds upon the researchers' extensive knowledge and skills gained for several decades in the deformation behaviors of materials and the development of joining techniques under extreme conditions. The integration of ultrasonic welding into the group, extending even to the joining of high- temperature superconducting tapes, showcases the versatility of this technique (Shin et al., 2016; De Leon & Shin, 2020; Shin et al., 2020). The researchers' past contributions, such as investigations into dissimilar friction stir spot welding of metallic glass to lightweight crystalline metals (Shin, 2014) and ultrasonic spot welding of A5052-H32 alloy sheets (Shin & De Leon, 2017), mark steps towards addressing similar challenges. The current study, however, distinguishes itself by investigating the intricate details of ultrasonic welding joints between aluminum alloys and GFRP composites.

The remaining sections of this manuscript will present the technical approach, methods, and experimental, and future industry integration of the study, offering a comprehensive exploration of dissimilar ultrasonic welding joints for aluminum alloy to GFRP tubes. Through this study, the researchers aim to present not only a novel contribution to the field but also a potential breakthrough for industrial applications in the near future.

Methods

The materials selected for these dissimilar UW joints are aluminum alloy (A5052-H32) and GFRP cylindrical tubes. The two primary components, aluminum, and GFRP, represent contrasting yet complementary elements in the structural landscape. The A5052-H32 is chosen for its lightweight properties and favorable mechanical characteristics, and serves as a critical element in the study. Typically provided in coupon-type sheets or cap-structured forms with a thickness not exceeding 2 mm, this alloy exemplifies the type of lightweight materials commonly used in various industrial applications, particularly in the automotive sector for its balance of strength and weight.

The GFRP material takes the form of cylindrical tubes with an internal diameter ranging from 50 mm to 300 mm and a thickness of less than 2 mm. Figure 1 shows the joint concept between these two materials. The joining positions are also indicated in Figure 1 as point A and point B. This configuration mirrors real-world structures, allowing for a representative study of joints that might be encountered in practical

applications. The GFRP, characterized by its enhanced strength through the incorporation of glass fibers, brings a dimension of versatility to the joint configurations, encapsulating the aluminum coupons.

Figure 1. Joint assembly between aluminum A5052-H32 and glass-fiber-reinforced polymer.

The ultrasonic welding process is performed using a specialized ultrasonic welder, carefully chosen to optimize the joint performance. It is a lateral-drive UW machine (KORMAX, model KM-2035) in time control mode, capable of generating the necessary vibratory energy for effective welding. Additional details about this welder are available elsewhere (Shin & De Leon, 2017). This welder has a single transducer system, so oscillating motion is generated on only the horn side of the overlapped sample to be joined. Nevertheless, it has the capability of generating up to 3.5 kW of power at a frequency of 20 kHz. The equipment allows precise control over the welding parameters, including frequency, amplitude, and weld duration.

In addition to conventional ultrasonic welding, a hybrid-ultrasonic welding technique was introduced. This original technology incorporates a gradient function at the joint interface, enhancing the transversal oscillation in the weld zone. The hybrid technique involves several modifications and designs, including specialized horn and anvil configurations, proper mounting, and clamping through a vise tailored for the joint structure. A horn and anvil with a pyramidal tip pattern were used as shown in Figure 2(a) and (b), respectively. The vibration direction was applied parallel to the

surface of the jointed materials. The horn was made of high-speed steel, having circular and square surface shapes on both ends, which had dimensions of 14 mm diameter and 12 mm x 12 mm square shape (please see Figure 2a). Figure 2(b) shows the specially designed anvil with its respective tips and dimensions. The tips' patterns were designed according to the dimensions and physical properties of the materials to be welded through the preliminary test selections and in the researchers' previous study (Chen et al., 2016).

Also, appropriate material interlayers are used to provide gradient functions, and specific pre- and post-processing methods for both samples and joints. The combination of these factors, along with careful selection of machine parameters and material properties, is expected to optimize the hybrid effects on joint performance and quality.

Figure 2. (a) Horn with square and square shape surface and (b) cylindrical-shaped anvil with radius of curvature of 100 mm. Note: all linear dimensions are in mm.

Result and Discussion

From encapsulating GFRP tubes with A5052-H32 caps to integrating A5052-H32 coupons within GFRP structures, the researchers' study pursued to optimize the UW adaptability. Figure 3 shows the cylindrical GFRP- A5052-H32 UW assembly. To provide a uniform and continuous application of ultrasonic vibration, a rotary welding positioner is coupled to the welder setup. This can be controlled at different rotating speeds, making the joint uniform and systematic. By incorporating this hybrid-ultrasonic welding technique, the researchers elevated the transversal oscillation within the weld zone. This approach, achieved through meticulous design

modifications, clamping strategies, and material interlayers, not only optimized joint performance but opened new doors for dissimilar material bonding.

Figure 3. A customized cylindrical-shaped anvil is utilized coupled with the samples' positioner for uniform and continuous application of ultrasonic vibration.

Acknowledging the need for reliable joints, especially in the tensile strength aspect, coupon-shaped sheets were first tried to join. Figure 4 shows the A5052-H32 and GFRP samples with surface modifications through abrasive polishing (Figure 4a) and with an Indium sheet, 100 μm in thickness as interlayer (Figure 4b).

Figure 4. (a) Coupon-shaped A5052-H32 and GFRP samples with polished surfaces and (b) an Indium sheet inserted between the samples as interlayer material.

Two joints with different weld parameters are presented in Figure 5 (a) and (b). The possibility of joining these two different materials was materialized. At different

welding parameter conditions, two distinct welds can be observed after the sample separation, one with a more abrasive joint interface than the other. The use of interlayer material and varying welding parameters affects the joint interface. By further adjusting the welding parameters and finely tuning the interlayer material, an optimized weld can be achieved.

Figure 5. Ultrasonic welded A5052-H32 and GFRP with two different welding parameters. The images on the right show the joint interface after the joint separation.
(a) welding time of 1.3 s, 80% vibration amplitude, and 4.5 bar of welding pressure.
(b) welding time of 0.7 s, 100% vibration amplitude, and 6.5 bar of welding pressure.

In the initial results, the dissimilar ultrasonic welding joints emerged not just as a scientific achievement but as a preparation for potential industrial transformation. The hybrid-ultrasonic welding technique, the adaptability to real-world conditions, and the vision for future advancements collectively provided the possibilities for improvement.

Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion to this study, an investigation into dissimilar ultrasonic welding joints between A5052-H32 and GFRP cylindrical tubes set sights on the future. This study represents more than an achievement, it aligns with the ongoing evolutionary trends in manufacturing and joining technologies. As industries evolve towards lightweight materials and composite structures, the demand for reliable, efficient, and adaptable joining techniques becomes increasingly in demand. The dissimilar ultrasonic welding joints presented here could be promising in transforming industrial practices. With a hybrid-ultrasonic welding technique that enhances joint properties, these joints could become essential in the assembly of structures crucial to sectors such as automotive, aerospace, and renewable energy. This study sets the stage for a future where ultrasonic welding becomes a versatile tool for joining other dissimilar materials across various industries.

As industries embrace the era of Industry 4.0 (What is Industry 4.0 and how does it work?), the adaptability of ultrasonic welded joints to automation becomes a pivotal aspect. The integration of simulation tools for virtual optimization and non-destructive testing procedures that detect faults early in the welding process foretell a future where efficiency and quality intertwine. Crucially, the adaptability of ultrasonic welding in in-line manufacturing assembly suggests reduced setup times, increased weld productivity, and higher-quality joints. The vision of a manufacturing process that predicts failures, configures automatically, and adapts to changes signifies a leap toward a more streamlined and economical industrial future. Although not presented in this study, the concept of broader mechanical property testing involving the joints subjected to adaptive vacuums and varying temperatures could be of importance. Several tests could assess the joints against thermal shock, vibration, and dynamic loading conditions.

The dissimilar ultrasonic welding joints presented here, with their performance, adaptability, and potential for automation, symbolize a stepping stone towards a future where the joining of dissimilar materials is not just a challenge but an opportunity for innovation. As industries increasingly prioritize efficiency, sustainability, and adaptability, the techniques developed in this study could become instrumental. The dissimilar ultrasonic welding joints may well become a cornerstone in the construction of structures that define the future of industries, ushering in an era where innovation and practicality converge for the betterment of industrial practices.

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Implementation of Serving Leadership Style in Dulupi District Office, Boalemo Regency

Hesti Musa¹ Merlan S. Uloli² Imam Mashudi^{3*} and Sitti Husna Noviana Djou⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Bina Mandiri University of Gorontalo

imam.mashudi@ubmg.ac.id*

Abstract

This study aims to determine the style of serving leadership in the Dulupi District Office, Boalemo Regency. The method in this study uses descriptive qualitative methods with data collection techniques by observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of the study show that the leadership style in the Dulupi sub-district office has not been implemented properly, so there are still things that are lacking and need to be improved and developed again. This can be seen from the various characteristics of servant leadership that need to be improved and further developed, namely listening, empathy, predictability, healing ability, and serving ability.

Therefore, the characteristics of leadership need to be improved and developed again. Good characteristics in government, because the presence of leader characteristics can make employees grow in working well in the work environment and government. The leader is an exemplary example and can provide direction and therefore can create a sense of enthusiasm and openness so that teamwork can work well and correctly to achieve common goals

Keywords: Serving Leadership Style

1. Introduction

The human component in the organization is a determining element in the organization because the organization will experience major problems in achieving its goals if it rejects or ignores the human element. One of the human components in an organization is a leader. Leaders must scan the internal and external environment, chart strategic and task objectives, and provide performance feedback. Leadership is important for motivating followers and mobilizing resources towards the fulfillment of the organization's mission, it is also essential for organizational innovation, adaptation, and performance. Effective organizational leadership is not just about exercising influence on an interpersonal level, effective leadership also depends on leader expertise and on the formulation and implementation of solutions to complex social (and task-oriented). Organizational leaders place organizational members in achieving organizational forms. In carrying out activities

influencing others in achieving organizational goals, leaders have different ways or behaviors from one another and this method is better known as a leadership style. With the magnitude of the responsibility of a leader, the mastery of the leader in influencing subordinates, displays a certain leadership style towards achieving predetermined developments. Where is the behavior of the leader This is known as a leadership style, and the achievement of results is called performance. Research on leadership provides an interesting memory research because it always explains how to be a good leader, attitudes, styles, and serving that are by the leadership situation, and the requirements of a good leader, to be able to move his subordinates so they can carry out their duties and responsibilities to participate in government activities. Based on initial observations made at the Dulupi Sub-District Office, the Sub-District Head is still far from being consistent or optimal in carrying out his duties as a leader, so there are still employees who arrive late and leave early, sometimes there are even employees who are late at office hours during the morning assembly, not again Employees who sometimes delay in their work. This leads to people sometimes finding it difficult to approach the employees they are going to meet, so they have to come back another day. This requires the attention of a leader to motivate so that employees can work effectively and efficiently so that organizational goals can be carried out properly. It is proven that leaders must always give authority and responsibility to employees to fulfill work and involve employees in making decisions, and leaders always ask for advice, and even respond properly to suggestions and criticism from their subordinates, it's just that employees need concern from leaders when carrying out his job. Management is a process carried out by someone to manage something done individually or in groups. Management is considered very important in achieving a goal that has been planned or determined individually or as a group. Management can be interpreted as the art of organizing and executing. Management is considered very important in human life, especially in managing personal life and when being part of an organization in schools, campuses, offices, and society. In management there are elements (tools of management) that are often referred to as 6M, each element has its explanation

1) Man (Human)

Human resources are the most important and primary element and are considered very strategic. If human resources will not be easy to achieve.

2) Money

Financial management is also considered very important in the process of achieving targets or goals to support the success of the organization/company. Financial management must emphasize and carry out principles.

3) Materials

Materials or often referred to as semi-finished materials (raw materials) and finished materials. In carrying out an effort to achieve targets or goals, the most important or main thing is human resources who have expertise in their fields and use materials or materials. Because these two things cannot be separated.

4) Methods

To achieve the goals or targets that have been planned, a good method is needed to achieve the targets that have been planned. Therefore, humans are the main element in carrying out a method.

5) Machines

In the world of education, organizations/companies need a machine. Because the use of machines makes a business or process easier. Because work efficiency and effectiveness is the main thing.

6) Market (Market)

Marketing a product or goods is something that needs to be done by existing human resources.

Human resource management is a study in the field of management science (read: Definition of Management) that combines psychological, sociological, and other theories. Its real application includes the design and implementation of planning, staffing, career management, employee development, performance evaluation, and employment relations. Human resource management involves policies and decisions that affect the workforce.

Leadership comes from the words lead (lead), leader (leader), and lead (leading). In KBBI each of these words is defined as follows:

<i>Lead</i>	(in a state of) being guided; led
<i>Leader</i>	The one who leads, the guide, the guide
<i>Leading</i>	Knowing or leading, winning the most, holding hands while walking (to lead, show the way, and so on); guide, guide, train so that they can do it themselves
<i>Leadership</i>	About leadership, how to lead

Source: www.kbbi.web.id

From the KBBI definition above, each of these words has its emphasis. Lead shows the situation or circumstances, the leader shows the subject or person, leads shows the process, while leadership emphasizes the ability and way of a person to lead.

In its development, in terms of terminology, the definition of leadership is quite diverse, put forward by experts according to the discipline and field of expertise the experts come from.

As well as developments from the latest findings which have resulted in different perspectives on leadership.

Leadership Theory

1) Excess Theory

This theory assumes that a person will become a leader if he has an advantage over his followers.

2) Nature Theory

This theory states that a person can be a good leader if he has positive traits so that his followers can become good followers, with general leadership traits.

3) Theory of Heredity

According to this theory, a person becomes a leader because of heredity or inheritance, because his parents are leaders, their children will automatically become leaders and will replace their parents.

4) Charismatic Theory

The theory states that a person becomes a leader because that person has charisma (a very big influence).

5) Talent Theory

This theory is also called the ecological theory, which argues that leaders are born because of their talent. He becomes a leader because he does have the talent to be a leader.

Functions and characteristics of leadership

The leadership function relates to social situations in group/organizational life where the leadership function must be manifested in interactions between individuals. Operationally the main functions of leadership can be distinguished as follows:

1) Instructive Function

This function is one-way communication, the leader as the communicator is the party that

2) Consultative Function

This function is a two-way communication. In the first stage to make decisions, leaders often require material considerations which require them to consult with the people they lead, who are considered to have various information materials needed in making decisions. established and is in progress.

3) Participation Function

In carrying out this function the leader tries to activate the people he leads, both in participating in making decisions and in carrying them out.

4) Delegation function

This function is carried out by providing delegation of authority to make or determine decisions, either through approval or without approval from the leadership.

5) Control Function

The Control Function means that successful/effective leadership can manage the activities of its members in a directed and effective coordination, to enable the maximum achievement of common goals.

Leaders are people who lead groups of two or more people, both organizations and families. Leadership is the ability of a leader to control, lead, and influence the thoughts, feelings, or behavior of other people to achieve the goals that have been set predetermined. Leaders consist of formal leaders (formal leaders) and informal leaders (informal leaders). A formal leader is a person (male or female) who is appointed by a certain organization (private or government) (based on appointment letters from the organization concerned) to assume a position in the existing organizational structure with all rights and obligations related to it to achieve the goals of the organization that were set earlier.

Leadership is an ability inherent in a leader who depends on various external factors. Leadership is a person's skill and ability to influence the behavior of others, both those with a higher or lower position than him in thinking and acting so that behavior that may initially be individualistic and egocentric changes into organizational behavior.

Leadership is a person's ability to control or influence other people or different communities towards certain achievements. So, leadership or leadership are characteristics that must be possessed by a leader, which in practice have consequences for the self, which include the following:

1) Must have the courage to make firm and precise decisions (decision making)

- 2) Must have the courage to accept the risk itself
- 3) Must have the courage to accept own responsibility (The Principle of Absoluteness of Responsibility).

The Scope of Leadership in Organizations

Leadership Theory knows about leader behavior, leadership concepts, main duties and functions as well as professional ethics that leaders need to understand. Leadership Techniques examines the technical abilities and skills of leaders. The application of leadership theories includes the concept of the leader's thinking, the leader's behavior, and the ability to use resources. In general, leadership can be interpreted as a process of directing and influencing the task activities of people in groups. Leadership means involving other people, namely the subordinates or employees who will be led. Leadership also involves the sharing of power (Power). Leaders have more power than those who are led. This power comes from several sources, including Reward power, Coercive power, Legitimate power, Referent power, and Expert power.

Leadership History

In the times, leadership was scientifically developed, along with the growth of scientific management in the early 20th century and later developed into a science of leadership. Then it is no longer based on talent and experience alone but prepares in a planned way, and trains new prospective leaders. Everything is done through systematic planning, experimentation, research, analysis, supervision, and mentoring to awaken the qualities of superior leaders so that they are successful in their duties. The value of leadership is no longer determined by natural talent. However, its ability to move many people to do work together, thanks to influence leadership obtained through training and education.

Leaders and Leadership are like a coin that cannot be separated, in the sense that they can be studied separately but must be seen as one unit. A leader must have a leadership spirit, and a leadership spirit possessed by a leader cannot be obtained quickly and immediately, but a process that is formed from time to time until it finally crystallizes into a characteristic.

Leadership style is the way a person takes to practice leadership. Leadership style is not a talent. Therefore, leadership styles can be learned and practiced and their application must be adapted to the situation at hand. Leadership style can also be interpreted as a behavioral norm that is used by someone when that person tries to influence the behavior of others as he sees it.

Leadership style is the overall pattern of a leader's actions, both visible and invisible to his subordinates. Leadership style describes a consistent combination of philosophy, skills, traits, and attitudes that underlie a person's character. The leadership style that shows directly, a leader's belief in the strength of his subordinates. That is, leadership style is behavior and strategy, as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits, and attitudes that are often applied by a leader when he tries to the performance of his subordinates.

In general, every leader is required to carry out several actions related to his leadership. These actions are very influential for the progress of the organization they lead, these actions are: analyzing the organization or group they lead; fostering organizational structures, taking initiatives, achieving organizational goals, providing facilities for communicating; Creating cohesiveness; Developing a sense of happiness for all members of the organization; Sinality (unify/unify); Must work using the philosophy of the organization

he leads. Activities so that the process of serving takes place routinely and continuously covering the entire life of the organization in society. The process in question is carried out in connection with mutual fulfillment of needs between the recipient and the service provider.[6]

Service is a form of service activity carried out by government agencies, both central, regional, BUMN, and BUMD, which are goods and services to meet the needs of the community following applicable laws and regulations.

Service consists of four factors, namely:

- 1) Systems, procedures, and methods
- 2) Personnel, especially emphasized apparatus behavior
- 3) Facilities and infrastructure
- 4) Communities as customers

The main characteristic that distinguishes servant leadership from other leadership models is the desire to lead.

The six most dominant characteristics of servant leadership are:

- 1) Listening

Traditionally, leaders have been valued for their communication skills and ability to communicate decision-making. Servant leaders must reinforce this important skill by demonstrating a deep commitment to listening intensively to the ideas or words of others. Servant leaders seek to identify and understand the will of the group. They try to listen responsively to what is said (and not said). Listen and understand what the body, soul, and mind are communicating.

- 2) Empathy

Servant leaders strive to understand and empathize with others. People need to be accepted and recognized as special and unique individuals. Each individual does not want his presence in an organization/company to be rejected by others around him. The most successful servant leaders are those who can be empathetic listeners.

- 3) Ability to Foresee

The ability to take into account conditions that have already occurred or predict the likely outcome of a situation is difficult to define but easy to identify. People know when they see it. Foresight is a trait that enables servant leaders to understand the lessons of the past, the realities of the present, and the possible consequences of a decision for the future. This sinks the heart of the matter deep into the intuitive mind. So, the ability to foresee was one of the characteristics of a servant leader that he was born with. All other characteristics can be developed consciously. Awareness and perception). Awareness of self and the presence of others can help strengthen servant leaders. Awareness also helps in understanding issues involving ethics and values. This allows people to view most situations from a more integrated position

- 4) Healing Ability

Learning to heal is a powerful force for change and integration. One of the great strengths of servant leadership is the ability to heal oneself and others. Many people are discouraged and suffer from various emotional problems. Even though this is something that is natural in human life, a servant leader must be able and have the opportunity to move the hearts and give enthusiasm to those who relate to them.

- 5) Ability to serve

Peter Block (author of the book *Stewardship and Empowered Manager*) defines the ability to serve (stewardship) in the sense of "holding something with the trust of others". In an organization, every level of management, from top management to the shop floor all has an important role to play in holding the organization in faith in the greater good of society. Servant leadership, like the ability to serve, is first and foremost a commitment to serve the needs of others. This of course emphasizes openness and honesty, not control or supervision.

a. Forms of Service

General forms of service are divided into three types as follows:

1) Oral service

Oral services are carried out by employees in public relations, information, and other fields who must provide explanations or information to anyone who needs service. For oral services to be successful by expectations, some conditions must be met by service providers, including:

- a.) Understand the problems that exist in their field
- b.) Provide the necessary explanations smoothly, correctly, briefly, and clearly
- c) Be polite and friendly
- d.) Discipline

2) Service with writing

Service with writing is the most prominent form of service in carrying out tasks. Not only in terms of quantity but also in terms of service. Writing services are quite efficient, especially for services that are provided remotely due to the cost factor. Services with writing are divided into two parts, namely:

- a.) Services in the form of information guides and the like aimed at people who have an interest in making it easier to deal with agencies.
- b.) Services in the form of written documents on requests, complaints, grants, reports, and notifications.

3) Services in the form of deeds

Services in the form of deeds are usually combined with verbal services. This is due to most oral relationships being carried out in a service relationship and focus more on the actions awaited by the people concerned. The main goal is to get services in the form of actions or results of actions, not just verbal explanations and/or abilities.

2. Methods

This research method uses a qualitative approach, qualitative research is a type of research whose findings are not obtained through statistical processing or other forms of calculation and aims to reveal symptoms in a holistic-contextual manner through collecting data from natural backgrounds by utilizing the researcher himself as a key instrument. Qualitative research is descriptive and tends to use analysis with an inductive approach. Processes and meanings based on the subject's perspective are highlighted in qualitative research.

Initially, qualitative research methods were used more in the field of cultural anthropology, so they were often referred to as ethnographic methods. Qualitative research

methods are also often referred to as naturalistic research methods because the research is carried out in natural conditions or as it is. Thus, the conditions when the researcher entered the field, while in the field, and after leaving the field, the conditions of the object under study remained relatively unchanged.

The instrument in qualitative research is the researcher himself (human instrument). In this case the researcher is the key instrument. It is the researcher who determines the research focus, selects informants as data sources, selects data quality, interprets data, and draws conclusions based on his findings. Data in qualitative research is descriptive data which is generally in the form of words, pictures, or recordings.

Descriptive research is research that seeks to describe an event phenomenon, an event that is happening now. Descriptive research focuses on actual problems as they were at the time the research took place. Through descriptive research, researchers try to describe events and events that are the center of attention without giving special treatment to these events. The variables studied can be single (one variable) or more than one variable.

3. Results

Listening

Leaders are still not good at being active listeners and are still not effective in providing solutions when problems occur, so there are still several complaints from employees or their subordinates. This needs to be developed more maturely.

Empathy

Leaders have an attitude of empathy for employees, but it needs to be developed further because there are still complaints from employees about the empathy that is owned by the leader.

Ability to Foresee

The leader can also help understand issues involving ethics and values, but few leaders have this, so it needs to be further developed.

Healing Ability

Leaders have shown their ability to heal. The thing that the leader does is to continue to provide enthusiasm even though sometimes the leader feels a lack of enthusiasm, but there is still something lacking so it needs to be developed further in healing so that employees and the organization can run well.

Ability to Serve

Based on the results of the interview above, it can be concluded that the leadership has shown its ability to serve, he is quite good and tries to serve employees. Regarding serving employees and the organization, the leadership has done well, but only a few are lacking in leadership in serving, this needs to be developed further. so that the company runs well again and progresses in the future.

4. Discussion

Leaders' characteristics play an important role in employee engagement, motivation, acceptance, and participation which in the end leads to enhancing performance and creativity. Many researchers have confirmed the positive and significant relationship between

leadership styles and employee creativity. Some studies also indicated the role of a leader in implementing new strategies and how her/his characteristics/charisma impact the innovation in the organization.

Similar to authentic leadership, servant leadership also acknowledges the importance of being authentic in one's interaction with others. For servant leaders, the propensity to operate with a deep clarity of self-awareness and self-regulation might spring from a spiritual and/or altruistic motive to serve others, both of which are absent in the authentic leadership framework. That is, servant leaders are authentic not for the sake of being authentic, but because they are driven either by a sense of a higher calling or inner conviction to serve and make a positive difference for others.

Relative to ethical leadership, servant leadership more explicitly incorporates stewardship as an essential element of effective leadership, this brings a focus on a long-term perspective that takes into account all stakeholders. Leader behavior in line with ethical leadership theory may have a more prescriptive character and be aligned with rules that one should follow in terms of what is good based on innate ethical rules, but servant leader behavior is more flexible and contingent, taking more explicitly both the follower and the organizational context into account.

Listening

In particular, listening is done patiently for any problems faced by employees as well as providing responses and suggestions encountered. As stated by Veri Widodo, leaders are valued for their communication skills and ability to make decisions. Servant leaders must reinforce this important skill by demonstrating deep commitment, in listening intensively to the ideas or words of others. Servant leaders seek to identify and understand the will of the group. They try to listen responsively to what is said (and not said). Listen and understand what the body, soul, and mind are communicating.

Empathy

Servant leaders strive to understand and empathize with others. As a leader, you must have empathy for your subordinates. A person's ability to understand other people's feelings and problems, to think from other people's points of view, and to respect other people's different views on things.

Ability to Foresee

The ability to predict, namely awareness about the future, not to happen as before or in the past. To solve problems in the future that cannot be ascertained, we must always try to solve them with an approach according to actual behavior, as well as in forecasting. Forecasting is the art and science of predicting future events.

Healing Ability

One of the great strengths of servant leadership is the ability to heal oneself and others. A servant leader tries to help people solve problems and conflicts that occur.

Ability to serve

Servant leadership is leadership developed to overcome a leadership crisis experienced by a society or nation. Servant leaders tend to prioritize the needs, interests, and aspirations of the people they lead above themselves.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The implementation of characteristics implemented in the Dulupi sub-district office have not been carried out properly, so there are still things that are lacking and need to be improved and further developed. This can be seen from the various characteristics of servant leadership that need to be improved and further developed, namely:

- **Listening**, in listening there are interview results based on that the leader is still it is not good to be an active listener and still not optimal in providing solutions when problems occur, so there are still several complaints from employees.
- **Empathy**, in empathy there are interview results that show that leaders have an empathetic attitude towards employees, but it needs to be developed further because there are still complaints from employees about the empathy possessed by leaders.
- **The ability to predict**, the results of interviews with leaders can work well and the awareness of these leaders can also help understand issues involving ethics and values, but leaders lack these skills, so they need to be further developed.
- **Ability to heal**, there are results of interviews with leaders who have shown their ability to heal. The thing that the leadership does is to continue to provide enthusiasm even though sometimes the leadership feels lacking in enthusiasm, but there is still something lacking so it needs to be developed further in healing so that employees and the organization can run well.
- **Ability to serve**, there are results of interviews with leaders who have shown their ability to serve, he is quite good and tries to serve employees. Regarding serving employees and the organization, the leadership has done well, but only a few are lacking in leadership in serving.

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Implementation of Training in Improving the Performance of Haimart Store Employess in Kabupaten Boalemo

Hasni Pasingi¹ Soeharto Puluhulawa² Sudarsono^{3*} Sitti Husna Noviana Djou⁴, and Nur Rizky Putri Mahadi⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5}Bina Mandiri University of Gorontalo

Correspondance Email: sudarsono@ubmg.ac.id*

Email: hasnipasingi24@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to determine the implementation of training in improving employee performance at the Haimart Store, through several indicators, namely: training benefits, training infrastructure, training methods, and training materials as well as knowing the factors that affect employee performance at the Haimart Store with indicators, namely: Internal employee factors and organizational internal environmental factors.

The methods in this study uses descriptive qualitative methods with observation data collection techniques, in-depth interviews, and documentation

The result showed that the implementation of training has benefits for employees or trainees, especially in developing the abilities possessed by the instructors or trainers in this training program, who are the owners and heads of Haimart Stores. The method used is to divide the two training implementations, firstly basic training for new employees and the second employee capability development training for employees who have been placed in the existing divisions at the Haimart Store. The materials used in this training are compiled by the owner of the Haimart Store based on the purpose of implementing the training and development of the Haimart Store. The materials used in this training are compiled by the owner of the Haimart Store based on the purpose of implementing the training and development of the Haimart Store. Although the implementation of training is currently running well, there are still factors that affect performance, including internal employee factors, especially minimal knowledge about the training provided and factors of the internal environment of the organization where there is still a lack of facilities used at the time of training.

Keywords: Training implementation, factors affecting Performance

1. Introduction

In today's modern era, business competition is intensifying and technological sophistication is increasingly developing which will cause companies to be threatened towards changes in organizational management both at the national and international levels. This situation is not only felt by large companies, but small companies also feel the impact of today's technological sophistication. So that employee must be able to adjust to technological developments.

Human resources are a useful factor in achieving company expectations. Labor is useful for deciding the chronology of the production process even though the duties and responsibilities of the workforce are transferred with increasingly developing technology. Therefore, companies need to maximize human resources because they describe phenomenal events and asset management for the survival of the company.

One of the factors that can affect the success rate of a company is employee performance. Employee performance is an important component not only because it is directly related to employee income within a certain period, but also because there is life for the survival of the company.

To develop employee performance, one of which is training according to company needs. Training is needed to maximize the quality of employees and is an important factor in business competition. Rapid technological developments within a company must be balanced by developing human resources to overcome the wheels of the company.

One company that is aware of the importance of the training program is Toko Haimart in Boalemo Regency. Toko Haimart is a trading company located in Boalemo Regency, Gorontalo Province. Toko Haimart conducts training programs for all employees. This training program is provided to all employees to maximize their performance. There are two training programs conducted, namely basic training and capacity building training for each employee. Basic training is carried out for approximately one week at the central Haimart Store, this training is mandatory for all new employees. Meanwhile, employee capacity building training is conducted for all employees who are already in their respective departments. This training is carried out so that employees can develop their abilities by the sections that have been determined by the owner of the Haimart Store in Boalemo Regency.

Even though training has been carried out for all employees, there are still some employees who make mistakes in their work. For example, at the cashier's desk there are still employees who are wrong in returning the buyer's remaining money, in the packaging of goods and the placement of goods there are still things that are not neatly packaged and the goods are still not properly placed, then when sending goods there are still things that are not on time, so that at the time of evaluation there are still employees who are wrong in

completing their work. Where, this problem can affect the development of the Haimart Store. Things like this show that the performance of employees at the Haimart Store in Boalemo Regency is still not optimal.

Management is a series of activities consisting of planning, implementing, monitoring, and controlling to achieve a certain goal that has been targeted through the utilization of human resources and other sources.

Management is the art of getting work done through other people [9]. This definition places more emphasis on a manager where a manager is tasked with managing and directing other people to achieve organizational goals using the human resources found in the company or organization.

Management functions, namely as follows:

1. Planning (planning)

Is a process that involves the efforts made to anticipate future trends in determining the right strategy and tactics to realize the goals and objectives of the organization. Among the current trends in the business world, for example, how to plan an environmentally friendly business, how to design a business organization that can compete in global competition, and so on.

The planning function is as follows:

- a. Setting business goals and targets.
- b. Formulate strategies to achieve these business goals and targets.
- c. Determine the resources needed.
- d. Setting standards or indicators of success in achieving business goals and targets.

2. Organizing

Is a process that concerns how the strategies and tactics that have been formulated in planning are designed in an appropriate and strong organizational structure, conducive system and organizational environment, and can ensure that all parties in the organization can work effectively and efficiently to achieve organizational goals.

The organizing function is as follows:

- a. Allocate resources, formulate and assign tasks, and establish necessary procedures.
- b. Establish an organizational structure that shows lines of authority and responsibility.
- c. Recruitment, selection, training, and human resource/labor development activities.
- d. The activity of placing human resources in the most appropriate position.

3. Implementation (Direction)

It is the process of implementing the program so that it can be implemented by all parties in the organization as well as the process of motivating so that all parties can carry out their responsibilities with full awareness and high productivity.

The implementation function is as follows:

- a. Implementing leadership processes and providing motivation to the workforce so they can work effectively and efficiently in achieving goals.
- b. Give assignments and routine explanations about work.
- c. Explain the policies set

4. Control or Supervision (Controlling)

It is a process carried out to ensure that all series of activities that have been planned, organized and implemented can run according to the expected targets even though various changes occur in the environment the business world is facing.

The supervisory function is as follows:

- a. Evaluate success in achieving business goals and targets according to predetermined indicators.
- b. Take steps to clarify and correct any discrepancies that may be found.
- c. Perform various alternative solutions to various problems related to achieving business goals and targets.

Human resource management is the science and art of knowing the relationships and roles of the workforce so that they can effectively and efficiently help achieve company, employee and community goals.

The objectives of human resource management are as follows:

- 1) Provide management considerations in making HR policies.
- 2) Implement and maintain all HR policies and procedures.
- 3) Assist in developing the direction and strategy of the organization or company.
- 4) Provide support from certain conditions that can assist line managers in achieving the goals of an organization or company.
- 5) Handling various crises and difficult situations between workers and companies or organizations.
- 6) Provide a medium of communication between workers and companies or organizations
- 7) Maintaining organizational standards and values in HR management.

Training is part of education that concerns the learning process to acquire and improve skills outside the applicable education system, in a relatively short time with a method that prioritizes training rather than theory .

The training objectives are as follows:

- 1) Improve employee performance
- 2) Employees who perform unsatisfactorily due to a lack of skills are prime candidates for training.
- 3) Updating the skills of employees in line with technological advances
- 4) Through training (trainers) ensure that employees can apply new technology effectively.
- 5) Reducing learning time for new employees to be competent on the job. New employees often do not master the skills and abilities needed to become "job complete", namely being able to achieve the expected output and quality standards.

The training indicators can be divided into five indicators as follows:

- 1) Instructor
- 2) Reminding that training is generally oriented towards improving skills, the trainers selected to provide training materials must have adequate qualifications under their fields, professional and competent, namely training instructors must have adequate qualifications or competence, be able to motivate participants and need feedback come back.
- 3) Trainee

- 4) Training participants must of course be selected based on certain requirements and appropriate qualifications. Here the characteristics of the participants can be seen from how enthusiastic the participants are in participating in the training and how they want to pay attention to every detail of the training provided.
- 5) Method
- 6) The training method will ensure that effective human resource training activities take place if they are appropriate to the type of material and the abilities of the trainees. The training method should be compatible with the type of training and the training material being implemented.
- 7) Material
- 8) Human resource training is material or curriculum following the objectives of human resource training to be achieved by the company. The training material is expected to increase the ability of its employees and the suitability of the training material with the objectives of the training.
- 9) Benefits of training
- 10) Training requires defined benefits, particularly about preparing action plans and setting targets, as well as the expected results of the training being held. The purpose of a training is to improve the skills and understanding of the work ethic of the trainees.

Performance comes from the word Job Performance or Actual Performance, namely work performance or actual performance of an employee or employees, so the notion of performance is the result of work in quality or quantity achieved by an employee or employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him [11].

Performance is the result of work achieved by every employee or employees in developing their duties and work that comes from the organization or company. Performance is also a result of work produced by individuals through the process of an organization or company that can be measured concretely and compared with the standards set by the organization or company.

Factors that affect performance according to include:

- 1) Employee internal factors, namely factors that come from within the employee itself and are divided into competence, knowledge (education), talent, work experience, physical and psychological conditions, work motivation, work enthusiasm, and job satisfaction. After being influenced by the internal environment and external environment, these internal factors determine employee performance. So, it can be assumed that the higher the internal factors, the higher the employee's performance. Conversely, the lower these factors, the lower the performance.
- 2) Internal organizational environmental factors, in carrying out their duties, employees need the support of the organization where they work. This support affects the level of employee performance, for example, the use of technology, otherwise if the compensation and organizational work climate are bad, employee performance will decrease. Other internal organizational environmental factors such as management systems, support resources needed to complete work, leadership, co-workers, and training.

2. Methods

The approach in this study uses a mixed-method research approach. A qualitative approach is research that crosses several disciplines, science, and material, involving a deep understanding of human behavior and the reasons that govern this human behavior.

This research uses descriptive research type. Descriptive research is research that is intended to investigate the circumstances, conditions, or other things that have been mentioned, the results of which are presented in the form of a research report. **Types of descriptive research we used is survey research, collecting data from a large number of respondents using observation, interviews, and documentation.**

3. Results

The research results show that:

- 1) Implementation of training in improving employee performance, with the following indicators:

Training Benefits

"In my opinion, the implementation of a training course has benefits for the employees themselves, because with the implementation of this training program, each employee is given knowledge and experience that is appropriate to their work so that they can increase productivity, quality of work and improve the quality of work results and can reduce errors in carrying out the work done. given"

Training Instructor

"The trainers or instructors for this training program are myself and the shop heads at each Haimart store. I as the owner of the Haimart Store and as a provider of basic training materials for prospective employees and for Shop heads as a provider of employee capacity building training"

Training Methods

"The method we use is to encourage the participants and provide basic training materials for new employees. This training is held for one month to find out the capabilities of each employee or the trainees themselves. This training is provided by the owner of the Haimart Store directly. In the following, we place them according to the section in the Haimart Store that is in accordance with the abilities they have, then provide employee capacity building training according to the section occupied, this training is given by the heads of the Haimart Store"

Training materials

"We provide material to prospective trainees in the form of basic training material because with this training material it can add to the knowledge of employees or the trainees themselves, for example material on packaging and placing goods according to size and type, at the cashier's section the material is given how to find out every inventory of goods in the Haimart Store, procedures for opening and closing the Store, how to serve customers properly and much more according to the sections in the Haimart Store"

Training Participants

"For the training participants themselves, all employees at the Haimart Store, both new employees and existing employees, are in their respective departments. Concerns all employees"

because there are two types of training provided, namely basic training and capacity building training”

2) Factors Affecting Employee Performance, With the Following Indicators:

Employee internal factors

“When carrying out their work there are still employees who make mistakes, this is because at the time of providing material or practice in the training program there are still employees who find it difficult to understand the training material delivered by the instructor or training provider”

Organizational internal environmental factors

“The facilities at the Haimart Store are still incomplete, for example the computer used during the training in the cashier section is still lacking. Where, the trainees only use one computer when participating in the training, this also has an impact on the process of implementing the training because the trainees have to take turns using the computer when attending the training provided”

4. Discussion

Implementation of training in improving employee performance

Based on the results of interviews with several informants, it can be concluded that:

- a. The benefits of implementing training, the implementation of training is very beneficial for the employees themselves, especially in improving the quality of work, abilities or skills possessed by each employee and can increase the knowledge and work experience of employees, especially for new employees who have no experience in completing their work. The benefits of training are not only felt by new employees, but this is also beneficial for old employees, especially employees who have been placed in departments at the Haimart Store. The benefit for old employees is that with this training employees can hone their skills according to the part they have occupied. The implementation of training at Haimart Stores not only has benefits for employees but also benefits for the Haimart Store itself, one of which is that Haimart Stores can produce quality employees who have the ability and have good quality work.
- b. Instructors or trainers, for employee training programs do not bring in speakers from outside but the instructors or trainers in providing this training are the owners and heads of Haimart Stores directly. This is done to reduce additional costs in providing training materials, training is given directly by the owner so that he can find out firsthand the abilities possessed by employees and by what the company wants and can be placed in parts that have been determined according to their abilities and skills possessed.
- c. The method of implementing the training, method used in implementing this training is to divide the training into two parts, namely basic training for new employees and capacity building training for permanent employees. Basic training is given directly by the owner of the Haimart Store to all trainees or new employees themselves, this is done so that the owner of the Haimart Store can find out the abilities or skills possessed by every employee in the Haimart Store. Furthermore, the owner of the Haimart Store places employees in the section according to their abilities to continue further training, namely training to develop the abilities of each employee. This training is given directly by the shop heads at each Haimart Store.

- d. Training material, for the training material itself is given by the existing section at the Haimart Store, in the provision of this training which is carried out first the training participants are given training material as a basis for them to carry out direct practice. The material provided includes material on good packaging of goods and placing them according to their size and type, then training materials on how to find out the hospitalization of each item and how to serve customers properly and correctly. All training provided must be attended by all prospective employees, by carrying out a training both shop owners and heads who as training providers at Haimart Stores can find out the abilities possessed by each employee in completing their work and responsibilities. Furthermore, these employees will be placed in sections according to their abilities. Then this ability will be developed through capacity building training given in accordance with the parts they occupy until they really master the job given. With this capacity development training, each employee can develop the skills they have so that they can affect their performance, this also directly affects the development of Haimart Stores.
- e. Training participants, training participants are people who come or people who take part in the training program at the Haimart Store, this is the training participants in the implementation of the training program who become training participants are all employees at the Haimart Store. Both new employees and employees who have been placed in predetermined sections, this is because there are two types of training provided, namely basic training for new employees, capacity building training for employees who are already in predetermined sections.

Factors Affecting Employee Performance

Based on the results of interviews with several informants, it was found that:

a. Employee Internal Factors

One of the factors that influence performance is the internal factor of employees, especially the knowledge possessed by each employee in a company or organization. However, there are still employees who are still lacking in knowledge after attending the training provided, one of the factors causing the lack of employee knowledge about employee training is that during the implementation of the training there are still employees who have difficulty understanding the material presented by the instructor during the training, so that this can affect its performance. This can be seen from the evaluation of employee performance where there are still employees who make mistakes in completing the work assigned to them. If this is allowed to continue without the right solution, it will directly affect the performance of every employee at the Haimart Store.

b. Organizational Internal Environmental Factors

Organizational internal environmental factors are also included in factors that affect performance. Where, one of them is the completeness of existing facilities and infrastructure in a company or organization. For example, the completeness of facilities and infrastructure is very much needed in the implementation of training, this is certainly very much needed to make it easier for training instructors to provide training materials and provide direct training practice. However, the facilities and infrastructure at Haimart Stores are not fully complete, training facilities, lack of

facilities at Haimart Stores. Among them, a special place has not been held for the implementation of training, there is still a lack of computers used during training and a lack of tools used when packing food or products. This will most likely affect the performance of each individual. If this is left without the right solution from the training provider then this will certainly have an impact on employee performance and employee work quality, for this reason a solution or the right method is needed to overcome obstacles in implementing this training. Especially for the cashier who has to master all the systems on the computer and for the place of implementation it is needed so as not to interfere with the implementation of the training given at that time. With the existence of complete facilities and infrastructure during the training, of course the training will be carried out properly and of course it will definitely affect the performance of each employee.

Several authors (Flint et al., 2008; Gosling et al., 2016; Jia & Lamming, 2012) have explored the effect, motivation and context of sustainability training, knowledge sharing among companies and organizational learning theory. Njuguna (2009) pointed out that knowledge obtained through trainings or other learning activities on an individual level needs to be spread to other team members and to the organizational level. In this regard, according to Probst & Buchel (1997) in Kristina et al., (2023), changes in the knowledge and values to improve a company's capability to solve problems describes the process of intra-organizational learning. Intra-organizational learning can be defined as *the sum total of individual and collective learning through training programs, experience, experimentation and work interactions within the organization*. Thus, sustainability trainings provided by focal companies can be seen as a tool used to generate intra-organizational learning. Mariotti (2012) described inter-organizational learning as a complex phenomenon and distinguishes between the creation of collective knowledge, the creation of network rules of interaction, and knowledge acquisition and transfer.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Training or training is an activity that aims to improve and develop attitudes, behavior, skills, and knowledge so that employees are more skilled and able to carry out their responsibilities better by company standards and wishes. Training is one of the efforts to improve the quality of human resources in the world of work, every employee, both new and those who have worked for a long time, needs to attend training. This is also applied by Haimart store owners who implement training for new employees and old employees, in this case, there is training to improve the performance of employees at Haimart stores and there are also factors that affect performance. Based on the results of the research and the formulation of the research problem, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Implementation of training to improve employee performance:
 - a. The benefits of implementing training, the implementation of training is very beneficial for the employees themselves. Where, can develop the capabilities possessed, and increase the knowledge and work experience of employees.

- b. For the training instructors themselves, they do not bring in speakers from outside but from the Haimart shop itself, namely the owners and heads of the Haimart shop, this is done so as not to increase costs in conducting the training.
 - c. The training method used is to divide the training into two, namely basic training for new employees and capacity building training for employees whose divisions have been assigned.
 - d. The training material provided is by the part that will be occupied when you become an employee at the Haimart Store and is given according to the capabilities of each employee.
 - e. Training participants in the implementation of this training program are all employees at the Haimart Store, both new employees and employees who have been placed in designated sections. This training program must be attended by all employees at the Haimart Store.
2. Factors that influence the performance of Haimart store employees are:
- a. Employee internal factors. One of the factors that influence performance is the internal factor of employees, especially the knowledge possessed by each employee in a company or organization. However, there are still employees who are still lacking in knowledge after attending the training provided, one of the factors causing the lack of employee knowledge about employee training is that during the implementation of the training, there are still employees who have difficulty understanding the material presented by the instructor during the training so that this can affect its performance. This can be seen from the evaluation of employee performance where there are still employees who make mistakes in completing the work given to them. If this is allowed to continue without the right solution, it will directly affect the performance of every employee at the Haimart Store.
 - b. Organizational internal environmental factors. This factor is also included in the factors that affect performance. Where one of them is the completeness of existing facilities and infrastructure in a company or organization. For example, the completeness of facilities and infrastructure is very much needed in the implementation of training, this is certainly very much needed to make it easier for training instructors to provide training materials and provide direct training practice. However, the facilities and infrastructure at Haimart Stores are not fully complete, training facilities, lack of facilities at Haimart Stores. Among them, a special place has not been held for the implementation of training, there is still a lack of computers used during training and a lack of tools used when packing food or products. This will most likely affect the performance of each individual. If this is left without the right solution from the training provider then this will certainly have an impact on employee performance and employee work quality, for this reason a solution or method is needed that is appropriate in overcoming obstacles in the implementation of this training. Especially for the cashier who has to master all the systems on the computer and for the place of implementation it is needed so as not to interfere with the implementation of the training given at that time. With the existence of complete facilities and infrastructure during the training, the training will certainly be carried out properly and of course definitely affect the performance of each employee.

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